

**COVID -19 AND ITS IMPACT ON DIGITAL MARKETING; A
STUDY ON CADET`S DECISION MAKING PROCESS IN
MARITIME EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS**

A Report

Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for Award of

POST DOCTORAL FELLOW

by

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November 2022

Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this Report is original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This Report is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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ABSTRACT

Due to Covid-19's radical transformation of the educational landscape throughout the world, the education sector has been highlighted as one of the most significantly impacted sectors. Since all schools, colleges, and universities were shuttered due to the lockdown, students were unable to attend courses in person, which made the future of their education questionable. In place of the methodical operations of educational institutions, a new phase has begun, including online learning, online evaluation, and indoor activities. Innovative methods for educating students through online stimulated their interests and sustained the academic achievement by schools, colleges, and universities. Although many universities found that taking lessons online was a temporary solution that was effective, it reduced students' learning methodology and their education standards. The study environment at home needs facilities such as internet connectivity, data package, mobile phones and laptop that are not accessible to all the students in India.

This study examined the level of effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 and ascertained the students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions in Chennai. The study also measured the student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai. Thus, the scope of the study is confined to the impact of digital marketing on students' preferences and decision making towards maritime educational institutions during covid-19 pandemic in Chennai. The study has chosen six colleges and universities offering maritime education in Chennai which includes Indian Maritime University - affiliated to Central University, private universities such as AMET University, Vels Academy of Maritime Education and Training and the colleges affiliated to state universities namely GKM College of Engineering and Technology, International Maritime Academy and Southern Academy of Maritime Studies.

The nature of the study adopted by the researcher is descriptive and analytical research design. The population for the study consists of students pursuing final year maritime education in central university, private university and colleges affiliated to state universities in Chennai. The questionnaire was pre-tested with 60 students from a chosen group of six maritime educational institutions in order to assess its reliability, validity, and appropriateness of the data collection instruments. The same size for the study consists of 400 students was chosen based on proportionate stratified random sampling technique. In order to test hypotheses and analyze the data statistically, a

formal standardized tool is used. The scheduled questionnaire is designed by using nominal, categorical, ordinal, rating, Likert and ratio scales.

The data were collected by using both primary and secondary data collection methods. The primary data are collected by using scheduled interview method and the secondary data are collected from the various records and documents, books, journals, articles and through websites. Tabulation and graphical representation is carried out using MS Excel. The data were analyzed by using SPSS which includes descriptive statistics, ANOVA, chi-square, correspondence analysis, bivariate correlation, multiple regression and Friedman test. Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) are applied to find out the reliability and validity of data and the model fit theory.

Hypotheses are formulated to find out the relationship between independent and dependent variables. Based on the ANOVA and t-test, it is identified that there is a significant difference between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. From the analysis of chi-square test and correspondence analysis, it is found that there is a significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education; preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The result of bivariate correlation has proven that there is a significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education. It is also clearly revealed from the multiple regression analysis that there is a significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' decision to pursue maritime education. Finally, it is proven from the Structural Equation Modeling that there exists a perfectly fit model between students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education. The study has made various suggestions to enhance the enrolment ratio of students in maritime education and implications are made to suggest the scope of future research. The study concluded that there is a significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' decision to pursue maritime education.

Key Words

Digital Marketing, Covid-19, Students' Decision Making Process, Maritime Education, Chennai, Tamilnadu.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

At the outset let me express my sincere thanks to the **authorities** of Srinivas University for permitting me to undertake the post-doctoral research work in the Institute of Management & Commerce.

I place on record my sincere, profuse and heartfelt thanks to my research supervisor **Dr.P.S.Aithal**, Professor, Institute of Management & Commerce & Vice Chancellor, Srinivas University, under whose keen supervision and versatile guidance, I have completed this post-doctoral research work. I am very grateful to him for inspiring me with his wise counsel and for suggesting this work.

I deem it a great pleasure to express my thanks to **Dr.Praveen BM**, Director Research & Innovation Council, Srinivas University and other senior professors for having academically enriched me, shaped me in all possible ways during my period as a post-doctoral fellow in the department.

I extend my sincere thanks and heartfelt gratitude to **Mr.Harischandra.P, Editor** and staff members of Srinivas Publication, Srinivas University.

I am immensely grateful to **teaching and non-teaching staff members**, Institute of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University for their valuable help and encouragement, which enabled me to complete the work at the earliest.

Words alone cannot express fully, my sincere and immense gratitude to **my parents, wife, and daughters** for their love and affection, their unstinted moral support, motivation and constant encouragement which have helped me to reach and attain my goal during the course of the study.

Finally, I thank all the people who have contributed in one way or another to the completion of this research, for giving me useful feedbacks about the progress of my work, for providing helpful comments on my work at an early stage and for their suggestions.

(Dr.D.RAJASEKAR)

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Sl. No.	Abbreviation	Word
1.	ARPA	Automatic Radar Plotting Aid
2.	ECDIS	Electronic Chart Display and Information System
3.	GMDSS	Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (IMO)
4.	ROC	Reference Our Cable

CHAPTER I

INTRODUCTION TO ONLINE EDUCATION, SCENARIO OF DIGITAL MARKETING AND MARITIME EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE ERA OF COVID- 19 PANDEMIC

1.1 INTRODUCTION OF THE STUDY

A typical virus, Covid-19, first identified in Wuhan, China in December 2019 has disabled the world and has adversely affected normal life of people in many countries. (Lai C.-C., et al., 2019). The first Covid-19 case in India was discovered in Kerala on 30th January 2020. In March, two people over 65 died associated with Covid-19. (www.who.int., 2020). Due to increase in Covid-19 cases on 25th March 2020, lockdown was announced all over India which affected all aspects human life physically and mentally. In the wake of temporary closures of companies, many people lost their jobs, resulting in financial losses, and most industries struggled and did not know how to deal with financial hardships. (www.wikipedia.org., 2020).

In addition, the education sector has been identified as a key affected sector as a result of Covid-19, since it has fundamentally transformed the educational environment throughout the world. The Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD), Government of India, conducted a survey on higher education and observed that the portal contains 993 universities, 39931 colleges, and 10725 standalone institutions that contribute to educational opportunities. (DNS Kumar, 2020). Due to lockdown, entire schools, colleges and universities were closed and the students could not able to attend the classes in person making their future education uncertain (www.campaignforeducation.org). According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization, more than 60% of students worldwide were affected by the widespread shutdown. A new phase, such as online learning, online assessment, and indoor activities, has begun in place of the systematic operations of educational institutions. (UNESCO 2020).

Schools, colleges, and universities have implemented innovative approaches to educate online, stimulate students' interests, and maintain students' academic

progression. Although many universities found that taking lessons online was a temporary solution that was effective, it reduced students' learning methodology and their education standards. The study environment at home needs facilities such as internet connectivity, data package, mobile phones and laptop that are not accessible to all the students in India. Even though they possess all such facilities and provided with favourable study environment, their mental capacity is not ready to accept the changes provided from offline to online. Due to online examination, lack of control over the students, political pressure to give pass mark to all the students, the education sector finds it difficult to streamline the quality of education (www.oecd.org, 2020). Besides, Indian students enrolled in universities abroad are leaving those countries in large numbers because of the economic crisis during Covid-19 pandemic, particularly in impacted countries. As a result, international higher education demands have declined significantly. (Jena, P.K., 2020).

For engineering colleges that offer practical and technical oriented courses, such as maritime education finds it difficult to deliver their practical sessions and simulation-based training courses like GMDSS, ROC, ECDIS, ARPA, etc via internet. They do not have proper guidelines, tools and training to teach the students virtually and faced difficulties in offering certificates for practical oriented courses which greatly affected the career of marine sector (www.scma.org.sg, 2020). The majority of students has a negative perception of maritime education and is reluctant to enrol in a maritime degree because it is impractical to teach maritime subjects online and there are few professional possibilities as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic shutdown. This reduces the enrolment ratio of students in maritime courses and provided great financial loss for the universities and colleges offering maritime courses especially for private universities and colleges.

They adopted various strategies and applied innovative software-based training facilities to offer simulated training courses through online. Moreover, they also made necessary arrangement to conduct offline classes for students by following strict guidelines of covid-19 measures and physical distancing in order to improve the education quality and to provide complete learning package for students. The significant strategy the education industry adopted to enhance admission to their schools, colleges and universities is that digital marketing to connect with ideal parents and students through Google, social media and e-mail.

Digital marketing is the component of marketing that uses the Internet and online based digital technologies such as desktop computers, mobile phones and other digital

media and platforms to promote products and services (www.wikipedia.org). Maritime universities and colleges promote their courses via digital marketing by offering full information about the course, its scope, career opportunities, their talented faculty members, innovative and updated facilities available in the college to teach maritime course, etc. This study has been undertaken to examine the level of effectiveness of online education during Covid-19 by Central University, colleges affiliated to State Universities and Private Universities and the students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions in Chennai.

1.2 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In the era of Covid-19 pandemic, higher educational institutions use various technologies to offer online classes in the place of offline classes in order to have continuity in education. Teachers used apps like Zoom, Google Meet, Facebook, Youtube, and Skype to conduct lectures and assign homework to students live via the internet. In order to facilitate effective communication, parents, instructors, and kids have Whatsapp groups where they may stay in touch and discuss academically as well as personally. However, many schools and universities struggled greatly, and many ran out of time to prepare their professors and students for the transition to online learning (Schleicher, A., 2020). Due to lack of training and new experience to digital teaching and learning process, it is difficult for the education sector to provide quality education to the students especially for engineering colleges and others offering technical and practical oriented courses. They found greater difficulty to conduct practical examinations, lack of control over students, difficulty in follow up of student's progression and in particular it is difficult for all the private colleges to collect the tuition fees from the enrolled students pursuing education in their colleges (Pravat, 2020).

During the difficult moment of the Covid-19 epidemic, the marine industry plays a critical role in sustaining global supply networks and shipping more than 80% of worldwide trade (Puteri Zarina et al., 2021). On the other hand, Covid-19 pandemic impacted maritime education to the greater extent. 96% of maritime educational institutions used online learning, but the applications of simulator activities and hands-on trainings were not successfully implemented to a considerable level (IAMU, 2020). They adopted innovative and many alternative technologies to improvise the teaching methodology and virtual practical and simulation training session but, the faculty members and students are not aware of the techniques and could not able to adapt themselves to it (Ergun DEMIREL, 2021). Moreover, inability of the faculty members to

have a face-to-face connect and interaction with students and lack of online teaching experience with respect to technical sessions, technological difficulties and low speed internet access are also considered as a drawback for online educators (Arasaratnam-Smith & Northcote, 2017; Claywell et al., 2016; Sun & Chen, 2016).

Conversely, it becomes greater challenge for the universities and colleges to do their admission process without interacting with the parents and potential students in person. Moreover, it is a challenging task for the private colleges to attract the students to choose their college or university. This is because, pandemic lockdown restricted the people to visit the college in person to collect data regarding their courses, its scope, amenities such as canteen, sports, extra-curricular activities, placement cell, facilities for practical oriented courses, competency of faculty members, academic progression etc (www.qaa.ac.uk). Only by collecting the data in person, the parent will get satisfaction and trust to admit their son/daughter in the college or university but, it is not possible in the era of Covid-19 pandemic lockdown.

Hence, they solely depend on the digital media to provide entire information about their college to attract the potential students in choosing their college or university. Digital marketing namely content marketing, search engine optimization, social media marketing, pay-per-click marketing, email marketing, instant message marketing and affiliate and influencer marketing are used by the most of the universities and colleges including maritime educational institutions to attract the students to enrol in their engineering colleges. Digital marketing communication aids the students to make aware of the colleges and universities offering various courses and it is easy for them to compare the tuition fees, facilities, amenities and placement guarantee offered by colleges and universities. According to the report given by A Saviance Technologies Whitepaper in 2018, majority of the students are searching for educational institutions using digital media.

However, the fact is that parents get higher satisfaction only by visiting the college in person than viewing the same through digital media. Many students may make wrong decision as per the information provided by colleges and universities in digital marketing communication. It is also noted that the information provided in digital media may or may not true and it confuses the students to take right decision in choice of colleges or universities. Hence, the colleges and universities should adapt various innovative technologies in presenting their college virtually in an attractive manner and providing all information according to the parents and students perspective in an effective manner(www2.deloitte.com).But, the question is that whether digital marketing

applied by maritime universities and colleges are effective and whether it attracts the prospective students to make decision on their higher education in maritime courses. Thus, the purpose of this study is to identify the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and its impact on students' decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai.

1.3 INTRODUCTION TO DIGITAL MARKETING

1.3.1 MEANING OF DIGITAL MARKETING

Digital marketing is a type of marketing that promotes products and services using the Internet and online-based digital technology such as desktop computers, mobile phones, and other digital media and platforms (Financial Times, 2017 & American Marketing Association, 2019)). It involves advertising delivered through digital channels to increase brand awareness and connect with potential customers through the internet, websites, and social media. (www.marketo.com). In many respects, digital marketing and traditional marketing share many of the same principles, as well as being considered new ways for companies to reach consumers and understand what they want. (www.investopedia.com). There are different specializations and teams within the digital marketing field including design team, copywriting team and performance marketing team, but often digital marketers work together to achieve the best possible ROI for a campaign (www.2stallions.com)

Diagram 1.3.1: Specialized Digital Solutions to Enhance Website and Mobile Applications

Source: www.2stallions.com

1.3.2 EVOLUTION OF DIGITAL MARKETING

Prior to the development of digital marketing techniques, businesses only used offline methods to promote and market their goods or services which includes billboards, TV and radio advertisements, newspapers, direct marketing, telephone conversations, postcards, catalogues, brochures, and other print media, among others. The majority of businesses now have a website, as of the twenty-first century. The first clickable banner for advertising appeared in the globe in 1993, marking the crucial turning point from conventional marketing to digital marketing. Many businesses entered the field of digital marketing the following year (Karan Shah, 2022).

a) Introduction of Yahoo

When Yahoo was initially introduced in 1994, it immediately became incredibly successful, receiving roughly 1 million hits globally. Companies started focusing on effective SEO at this point in order to improve ranks. A few more search engines started to appear in 1996.

b) Launch of Google

The biggest search engine in the world, Google, was introduced in 1998 and then Microsoft released MSN, and following that Yahoo updated their software.

c) Search Engine Competition

The fierce rivalry in the search engine sector by 2000 nearly caused all of the smaller search engines to vanish, leaving just Google and Yahoo to contend as the major contenders.

d) Web 2.0

To compete with Yahoo and Google, MSN introduced Live Search in 2002 and there is a significant improvement in the usage of consumers which was increased to 6.4 million consumers that entered the market. In that year, Web 2.0 also emerged which has experienced great growth and active internet users due to the direct interaction of consumers with companies.

e) Social Media Sites

In 2003, social media site MySpace was launched followed by Facebook in 2004. Many businesses recognized the vast opportunity these websites provided for marketing their goods and services and many of them began to advertise their products and services via social media effectively.

f) Analytics

Web cookies were first introduced in 1994, and as marketers began to see their value in knowing user behaviours and preferences, they began to gain popularity through analytics.

g) Emergence of WordPress

Word Press had been available for ten years at that point, but its 3.0 version (e-commerce plugins) became widely used and well-known among marketers and businesses. It made creating websites simple and did not always require a programmer.

h) Influencer Marketing

Influencer marketing first appeared in the field of digital marketing in 2015 and has continued to expand since that time and has provided companies with high-quality leads. Today, social media platforms like Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, Pinterest, and Twitter are used by 99% of digital marketers to promote their goods and services.

i) Reels and Short-form Content

Reels were launched by Instagram, and they genuinely transformed how social media marketers plan their campaigns. For optimum engagement, everyone now wants to take advantage of 60-second short-form video material.

Phases of Evolution of Digital Marketing in India for 30 years

Web 1.0

- **1993:** First clickable banner in the world was launched. An important milestone in the transition of traditional marketing to digital marketing
- **1994:** Yahoo was launched
- **1996:** Small scale search engines like HotBot and Alexa were launched
- **1998:** Google and MSN by Microsoft were launched
- **2000:** Google and Yahoo were the biggest and most established players in the market
- **2002:** Surge in internet users reached 6.4 million users
- **Web 2.0**
- **2003:** Users and businesses could interact
- **2003:** Social media sites like MySpace were launched
- **2004:** Facebook emerged
- **2004:** Companies understood the importance of web cookies and started applying them to their marketing efforts.
- **2010:** Pinterest and Instagram were launched

- **2016:** Yahoo discontinued some of its services
- **2017:** TikTok was launched
- **2019:** Google+ left the market
- **2021:** 99% of digital marketers use social media sites for marketing purposes

Diagram: 1.3.2 – History and Evolution of Digital Marketing

(Source: www.simplilearn.com)

1.3.3 HOW DOES IT DIFFER FROM TRADITIONAL MARKETING

The primary means through which a target audience is exposed to a marketing message distinguishes digital marketing from conventional marketing. In comparison to traditional marketing, which makes use of print media like magazines and newspapers, digital marketing makes use of online resources like social media or websites. Traditional marketing doesn't imply that it is outdated; rather, it continues to be crucial in people's lives as they increasingly feel the need to leave the digital world. The following are the key differences between traditional and digital marketing (www.geeksforgeeks.org).

Table: 1.3.3 – Difference between Traditional Marketing and Digital Marketing

Traditional Marketing	Digital Marketing
Promoting goods and services via television, the phone, banners, broadcasts, door-to-door sales, sponsorship, etc.	Promoting goods and services through digital media or electronic mediums like SEO, SEM, PPC, etc.
It is not cost-effective.	It is more cost-effective-promotional tool.
It is not so good for Brand building.	It is efficient and fast for brand building.
Due to the absence of analytical tools, it is difficult to measure traditional marketing.	With the support of analytical tools, it is easy to measure digital marketing.
In traditional marketing, it is difficult to calculate the return on investment.	In digital marketing, it is simple to the return of investment.
After the posting of the advertisement, it cannot be altered.	Even after the posting of an advertisement, it can be amended.
It includes advertisement and marketing through Television, Radio, Banner, Broadcast, Sponsorship and through print media.	It includes advertisement and marketing through Search engine optimization (SEO), Pay-per-click advertising (PPC), Web design, Content marketing, Social media marketing and Email marketing.
Interest, Awareness, Desire, and Decision are the four stages of traditional marketing.	Planning, Conversation, Content, and Sequels are the four stages of digital marketing.

Users have no option except to watch the ads.	Users can even skip the ads if they lack interest.
Traditional marketing has local reach and it is limited to particular area.	Digital marketing has global reach which covers wide range of customers all over the world.
There are standardized ways of targeting users.	The targeting here is customized and relies on the type of user.
The market analysis made in traditional marketing takes time to get the results i.e., the company has to wait for weeks or months to get results.	In digital marketing, the market analysis is made through internet which gives quick results.
Traditional marketing typically involves one-way communication because of the inflexible methods used to carry out the process.	In digital marketing, two-way communication occurs that leads to more customer satisfaction.

1.3.4 TYPES OF DIGITAL MARKETING CHANNELS

Traditionally, marketing would be conducted through print media, such as newspapers and magazines, as well as through broadcast media, such as TV and radio, to reach customers in particular geographical areas and classes of people. The development of digital marketing has made it simpler for businesses to sell their goods globally through digital media at low or no cost. Thus, digital marketing is a boom to companies and people to aware of goods and services (www.investopedia.com). The following are the avenues that companies are utilizing to boost their promotion through digital media.

a) Pay-Per-Click (PPC) Advertising

It is a form of digital marketing in which the company has to pay every time someone clicks on their digital advertisement. Thus, instead of paying a set amount to run targeted advertisements constantly on online channels, the company only pays for the advertisements that are interacting with individuals which make it possible for marketers to employ paid advertising to reach Internet consumers across many digital channels (www.mailchimp.com). Marketers may set up PPC campaigns to display their advertisements to users who are looking for phrases related to their goods or services on Google, Bing, LinkedIn, Twitter, Pinterest, or Facebook. PPC campaigns can divide

consumers into groups according to their demographics such as age or gender or even target them according to their specific interests or locality. (www.investopedia.com).

b) Search Engine Marketing (SEM)

Search Engine Marketing also known as Search Marketing is the practice of receiving traffic from search engines either naturally or through paid advertising. It is a type of digital marketing used to make a company's website appear more prominently in search engine results pages (SERPs) ([www. www.optimizely.com](http://www.optimizely.com)). PSAs (Paid Search Advertising) and SEO (Search Engine Optimization) are the two basic forms of search engine marketing. By gaining high positions in the SERPs, SEO is the method for obtaining free traffic from search engines, while paid search advertising is the practice of paying for the appearance of the advertisements on search engine results pages. The overall purpose of SEM is to boost exposure in search engines by gaining higher ranks in SERPs (search engine results pages). (www.reliablesoft.net).

c) Search Engine Optimization (SEO)

Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is the process of obtaining high-quality traffic from free and organic search results on search engines such as Google and Bing (www.convertful.com). SEO frequently aims to increase a page's or website's ranking in search engine results pages without requiring users to pay for it. Google utilizes algorithms, which are continuously updated, to determine how relevant the company's website according to the keywords entered by the user while searching for the results. (www.simplilearn.com). Therefore, search engine optimization (SEO) is the art of comprehending how data is indexed by websites like Google and optimising the page and its content to boost quality online traffic (visitors) (www.futurelearn.com). When businesses are able to integrate SEO into their digital marketing strategy, more customers will be able to see their names and websites. (www.investopedia.com). The level of user engagement, mobile friendliness, and the quantity and grade of inbound links are now the factors to take into account while optimizing a web page for search engines. The business must also improve technical SEO, which includes URL structure, loading speeds, and broken links, to assist search engines better browse and crawl the website. ([www. mailchimp.com](http://www.mailchimp.com)).

d) Content Marketing

It is the type of digital marketing which uses narration and storytelling to share the information and to increase the brand awareness to the customers. An industry leader in marketing automation, Marketo, describes content marketing as a long-term strategy

in which marketers develop a library of content that will drive traffic to their sites via search engines over the long run. Thus, the main goal of content marketing is to initiate the reader or viewer to prefer and to take purchase decision on goods and services. The information provided on content marketing should insist the customer to take action regarding making feedback to the content, requesting for more information and joining the clicking the website to view the goods or services (AlexaGustavsen, 2022). Content marketing is usually published on a website and then promoted through search engine optimization, email marketing, social media or even PPC campaigns. E-books, online courses, blogs, info graphics, webinars and podcasts are the various tools used by content marketing to advertise the products in an innovative way (www.investopedia.com). More than 56% of companies apply personalized content through articles, videos, social updates, blogs and landed pages in order to enhance their brand awareness and potential customers (contentmarketinginstitute.com).

e) Email Marketing

According to Rogers, email is still one of the most efficient marketing strategies applied by all sectors, even after the emergence of social media, mobile applications, and other platforms. In addition to creating effective campaigns, email marketing experts are adept at determining the best way to contact an audience, monitoring consumer interactions and data, and formulating strategic choices based on that information. (www.ama.org). The companies using e-mail marketing earn revenue approximately 40 dollars for every dollar spent on it. Thus, e-mail marketing reaches wider area and it attracts many customers through its personal interaction and continuous correspondence with the customers. (www.lyfemarketing.com). Companies using other digital marketing channels support the email marketing by creating a link to add-on to their email list and through their continuous updation and interaction via email, it transforms their existing customers to loyal customers. (www.investopedia.com).

f) Social Media Marketing

The practice of leveraging social media platforms to draw traffic and attention among the customers and to increase their brand awareness and social trust is known as social media marketing. The marketers may broaden their reach and build sustainable relationships with their clients by utilizing social media. In order to reach customers aged 65 and above, Facebook is the greatest option to be applied by companies and to reach the customers aged between 25 and 29 Instagram is the best platform for it(www.simplilearn.com). Thus, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, LinkedIn and YouTube

are the most significant and popular digital platforms for social media marketing. It is the most popular content medium for B2C and B2B digital marketers (www.mailchimp.com).

g) Affiliate Marketing

Affiliate marketing is considered as one of the oldest forms of marketing and it has been modified and modernized by the internet to bring a new life to it. It is the fast growing digital marketing used by the influencers (usually celebrities or familiar person from any field) who promote and sells the company's products or services to the customers through their account in tiktok, instagram, youtube, blogs and other social media platforms (AlexaGustavsen, 2022). In exchange of this service, they get a commission for every sale made by them. Millions of dollars are paid monthly to websites that sell items via affiliate programmes run by several well-known firms like Amazon and it is expected to raise high in 2022. (www.investopedia.com). Depending on their niche, affiliate marketers may review the products of just one company on their blog or third-party site, or they might review products of multiple companies (Influencermarketinghub.com).

h) Video Marketing

YouTube is one of the most popular search engines which is used by mainstream of customers to get full information about the products including its fair reviews given by existing customers before making a buying decision. Apart from other video marketing platform such as Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, Twitter etc., Youtube is one of the best platform which earns trust and confidence among the customers (www.investopedia.com). Advertisements for online videos are usually divided into three types: pre-roll advertisements, mid-roll advertisement and post-roll advertisement. Pre-roll advertisements are played before the video is watched, mid-roll advertisements are played during the video, or post-roll advertisements are played after the video has been watched (www.pwc.in, 2013). Comparing post-roll ads to the other varieties, it was found that post-roll ads had stronger brand recognition because of its advertisement context which plays a significant role in reinforcing advertising memory of the customers (Basil, Michael D, 1994). The ability for viewers to share these advertising makes this platform much more appealing (Lee, J.; Ham, C.; Kim, M., 2013). Sharing these videos can be equated to the online version of word by mouth marketing, extending number of people reached. The sharing of videos produces is equal to the word of mouth marketing which reaches wide range of customers and produces six different outcomes,

including affection, pleasure, inclusion, relaxation, escape and control. (Li, H. & Lo, H., 2015).

i) SMS Messaging or Instant Message Marketing (IMM)

SMS or text messages is a another significant digital marketing tool used by businesses and non-profit organizations to provide instantly all updated and current promotional messages to their prospective customers. Apart from companies, it is also used by political candidates for campaigning and to spread positive information about their party (www.investopedia.com).After the evolution of Whatsapp, Facebook Messenger, Snapchat etc., it becomes easier for the business people and others to promote their products and services and to have a direct contact with the customers with free of cost via internet. By creating groups and followers, the messages sent through this channel reach wide range of customers. WhatsApp is the most popular messaging app with 1.5 billion monthly users worldwide, followed by Facebook Messenger and WeChat. If information is delivered over a messenger and it is from a trusted friend, people are significantly more inclined to believe it than they are to believe spam emails. (www.convertful.com).

j) Native Advertising

It is most effective advertising when used on digital platforms like emails, websites, and social media channels. In this approach, paid content is placed that that matches the style, format, look, voice of an organic post (Merskin, Debra L., 2019). Native advertising includes things like boosted posts and articles in publications like the New York Times and All birds, which sell shoes. Native advertisements seem just like genuine social material, with the exception that they always include a label that says "sponsored" or "promoted." (www.blog.hootsuite.com).

k) Mobile Marketing

Mobile marketing is one of the significant and influential digital marketing platform that enable the marketers to interact with the target audience via SMS and MMS messages, social media notifications, mobile app alerts etc., on their mobile devices such as smart phones and tablets. (www.mailchimp.com). Around the world, 3.5 billion individuals are estimated to own a smart phone. In a poll performed by Statista in February 2022, 46% of participants said they use their phones for personal usage for five to six hours each day (Alexa Gustavsen, 2022). As a result, marketers employ mobile marketing and concentrate on utilizing a range of techniques to advertise and promote their goods and services(www.futurelearn.com).Through mobile marketing, marketers

can able to tailor their content and offers as per the geographic location of the customers to reach all sorts of customers.

l) Audio Marketing

Since the Golden Age of commercial broadcasting, radio marketing has been considered as the customers' favourite media. Since the 1920s, some individuals have continued to regularly listen to the radio, migrating from traditional radios to internet radio such as Spotify, Amazon music etc. Podcasts and smart home assistants like Google Home and Amazon Alexa are included in the much larger category of audio marketing. Podcasts are increasingly consumed by the people when working out or doing other mechanics (www.simplilearn.com). Radio advertising is inexpensive as it depends on the imagination of the listener. It is important for the company to find its target audience, write a great script, hire a professional voice talent, and advertise at the right time to make a radio advertisement successful (www.convertful.com)

m) Television Advertising

Television advertisement is a piece of television programming produced and sponsored by an organization to promote its products or services to a target audience (www.wikipedia.com). Despite its wide reach, frequency, and effects, television advertising is the easiest and most common way to reach consumers (www.feedough.com). It build brand fame and keep brands alive in the memories of customers for as long as the brand is active and visible than sponsored post or a search result (www.cnbccatalyst.com). Television advertising is "safe" because different mechanisms ensure that the ads broadcast on TV are of good quality, unlike ads shown on the Internet or through apps, which are not always screened (www.blog.realytics.io).

1.3.5 DIGITAL MARKETING IN THE ERA OF COVID-19

The global COVID 19 epidemic has changed how we live and conduct business, compelling us to establish a new normal. People all across the world developed an addiction to the internet for recreational purposes as a result of social distancing and government-enforced lockdown. Nearly 4.57 billion people were regular internet users as of April 2020. Customers are looking for easy and affordable ways to get their daily necessities because they are unable to make their shopping offline. They started using internet shopping to fulfil all of their demands, and their propensity to do so has increased significantly. The pandemic has changed consumer behaviour and marketing tactics. This enables the business to concentrate on digital marketing and apply various

marketing strategies in the digital media to attract wide range of customers. Thus in order to limit the spread of virus, businesses and consumers alike are using the internet not only for marketing and shopping purposes but also for entertainment, work from home, education activities, beauty care etc. (www.oviond.com). Forbes reports that 70% of businesses have implemented and are developing a digital transformation plan, meaning that more than half of businesses have boosted their investment in digital and technological innovation as a result of the epidemic. In order to take advantage of the growing traffic on each platform and improve their chances of being found by a viewer, it has also become crucial for businesses to utilize various digital platforms to increase their sales. Companies using digital solutions can instantly respond to client questions through online, reorganize budget spending, or change the audience targeted by their marketing strategies. Therefore, it is expected that in the future, digital marketing will play a crucial role in every company's commercial plan. Additionally, it is clear that every business must use digital marketing to be flexible in any market environment (www.2stallions.com).

The Impact of COVID-19 on Online Sales

Internet sales as a proportion of overall retail sales were published in a dataset by Retail Sales Index Time Series (DRSI) in June. During the first half of 2020, Internet sales represented 18.9% of total retail sales. By May 2020, it had grown to 32.8%. As a direct response to the increase in online shopping during lockdown, Hermes, a delivery and logistics company, is recruiting more than 10,000 new team members awarding that this shift in online behaviour is not a passing trend (www.innovationvisual.com).

Chart: 1.3.5 – Internet Sales as a Percentage of Total Retail Sales Ratio in Percentage

Source: *Office for National Statistics*

Company's Reaction to Lockdown

In addition to the way consumer behaviour has changed under lockdown, there has also been a step change in how organizations have responded, both in the B2C (business to consumer) and B2B (business to business) sectors. As a result of the March lockdown, businesses had to adapt quickly and shift not only how they communicate with their audiences, but also how they serve and delight their customers, often from a distance. It's imperative for companies seeking to target businesses in the B2B sphere to focus online, as their target audiences are no longer limited to the workplace. A number of major internet businesses, including Google, Twitter, and FreshWorks, have informed its staff that they won't be returning to the workplace until 2020. For many businesses, this change in audience behaviour necessitates a thorough evaluation of their marketing plan and a transition to a digital-first approach. Thus, digital marketing goes beyond the corporate website to effectively sell the detailed company profile, including its products and services, in order to draw customers.(www.innovationvisual.com).

1.3.6 FUTURE OF DIGITAL MARKETING

It is undeniably true that digital marketing has a very broad scope. It offers various advantages for the business people namely targeting wide range of customers, easy accessible and direct interaction with customers, cost-effectiveness and measurable results based on transparent sale data and direct feedback from the customers. With all of these benefits, it is clear that digital marketing has a very promising future. India has the 2nd largest number of internet users. India's internet user base would increase by roughly 666 million users by the year 2023.

Online shopping and product research are becoming more and more popular among customers and the companies have to spend more money on their SEO and other digital marketing platforms to attract customers (Karan Shah, 2022).In 2021, the Indian digital advertising market reached a size of over 200 billion Indian rupees, a significant increase from the previous year. During the past few years, the digital media market in India has grown rapidly, with digital advertising revenues projected to reach nearly 360 billion Indian rupees by 2023, reflecting a continuing trend.

According to IBEF Report, the fastest-growing digital ad medium in India right now is e-commerce platforms, with a US\$ 6–8 billion market by 2030. By 2030, it is anticipated that there will be 300–350 million additional online shoppers from tier 2 economies, outpacing the expansion of search and social media platforms. In the same

period, Redseer, a home-grown strategy consulting firm, forecast that India's digital ad market would reach US\$ 35 billion, with e-commerce platforms driving the growth.

From 15% to 20%, e-commerce platforms have contributed rapidly to the ad tech industry over the last two years; they are expected to contribute between 20% and 25%. By 2030, the total advertising market, including traditional and digital advertising, will reach US\$ 45-50 billion, of which digital ads will account for 70-75%. The growth of India's digital advertising ecosystem is largely due to an increase in digital consumption and penetration in Tier-2 cities.

Chart: 1.3.6.a - Market Size of the Digital Advertising Industry across India from 2016 to 2021, with Estimates until 2023(In Billion Indian Rupees)

Source: www.statista.com

Chart: 1.3.6.b - Digital Advertising Revenue in India from 2018 to 2021, with a Forecast until 2024 (In Billion Indian Rupees)

Source: www.statista.com

The amount of money made through digital advertising in India as of 2021 was estimated to be over 246 billion Indian rupees. India was one of the greatest advertising markets in the world in terms of ad expenditure in that same year, with total advertising revenues exceeding 700 billion Indian rupees.

Chart: 1.3.6.c- Digital Advertising Revenue of Leading Online Companies 2012-2021 (in Billion U.S. Dollars)

Source: *www.statista.com*

Facebook generated more than 114 billion dollars in digital income from online advertising in 2021. Google, the industry leader in search, generated 209.5 billion dollars from online advertising channels in the same time frame. Thus, digital marketing is expanding quickly in India; according to a Goldman Sachs research, the country's digital marketing business is predicted to be worth \$160 billion by the year 2025.

1.3.7 DIGITAL MARKETING AND EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Technology is the primary force advancing humanity. With technological advancement, we have now reached a point where a plethora of possibilities is available. Several new employment categories that weren't even possible a few years ago have been made possible by technology. Higher education itself has changed as a result of this process. For the millions of students who desire to fill these new career responsibilities, universities, colleges, and other educational institutions are offering fresh, interesting, cutting-edge, and pertinent courses. There are several online courses being developed

that are thought to provide students with high income. But it has also prompted higher education institutions to compete more fiercely for students and the finest possible academic services. Due to these factors, higher education institutions turn to digital marketing agencies for help in creating an effective strategy to communicate with potential students, parents, industry experts, and other stakeholders(digitalagencynetwork.com).

Since students use the internet more than any other demographic, digital marketing courses are more pertinent than ever, particularly for the higher education sector. According to the Ericsson Consumer Lab report, Indians students spend more than 6 hours for their online classes and 46% of users engaged with e-learning platforms during Covid-19 pandemic lockdown. Besides finding more information about topics, subjects, syllabuses, assignments, and projects, they also use it to find out about various courses, colleges, fees, admissions, quality of education, infrastructure of colleges, rankings of colleges, placement records, and student reviews before taking decision to pursue their higher education in reputed colleges.

Both student and parents are using the digital media even after making personal visits to an educational institution to search for reviews and other information regarding the top most colleges in India, hundred percent placement details provided by higher education institutions. They depend on digital marketing in order to make assure whether the facilities such as accommodations, hostel facilities, transportation options, school timings, teachers, academic calendars, and curricular and extracurricular activities are offered by colleges in an effective way. Thus by understanding the needs and expectations of the students and parents, the higher education institutions transforming the detailed information about their colleges and universities including the facilities offered in a digitalized manner (www.learningspiral.co.in).

Moreover, marketing through digital media is cost-effectiveness for the higher educational institutions compared to traditional marketing. They just need to update academic information, events, programmes, changes to the pricing schedule, and facilities that they continually improve through digital platform. During the projected period, the Global Digital Education Market is expected to increase from USD 11.5 billion in 2021 to USD 46.7 billion by 2026, at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 32.3%. The main reasons projected to propel the growth of the digital

education market are growing internet penetration, decreased infrastructure costs and better scalability utilizing online learning, increased efficiency, more comfort, and more flexibility, and rising demand for micro-learning (www.marketsandmarkets.com).

Benefits of Digital Marketing Services for Educational Institutions (www.learningspiral.com)

The following are the benefits offered by digital marketing for educational institutions: -

- **Builds Credibility:** The main advantage of an educational institution having an internet presence is that it increases credibility tremendously. The internet has without a doubt replaced other information access methods as the main source.
- **Improves Ranking:** The students, parents, teachers, stakeholders, etc. are one of the main factors take into account when ranking academic institutions and is influenced through digital marketing. The rating of your academic institution will increase if students and other stakeholders have a favourable impression of any educational institution and are publicly discussing it online.
- **Increase in Profit:** Compared to other traditional marketing strategies, digital marketing is cheaper. Consequently, it is a wonderful platform for newcomers or non-profit groups.
- **Easy to Access Target Audience:** It is incredibly simple to reach out to educational institutions' target audiences with digital marketing because practically all of them are most of the time actively alive in internet. Therefore, digital marketing is the method of advertising that best matches the educational institutions.
- **Immediate Feedback:** Instant feedback is possible with digital marketing via social media sites like Whatsapp, Instagram, Facebook and Twitter. As a result, it is easy for the educational institutions to quickly modify their marketing strategies and content provided in digital platform about their colleges and replace it with a superior one. Additionally, it is easy to quickly record the replies and suggestions given by the students and parents and make any necessary modifications to improve the quality.
- **High Conversions:** With the use of digital marketing, educational institutions may connect with prospective students on a larger range of media, including

social networking sites, emails, banner advertisements, and more which ultimately increases traffic and affects conversion rates. Because digital marketing can reach across the whole internet, it has a unique benefit in that it has a high lead conversion rate when used by educational institutions.

1.4 MARITIME EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE ERA OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC (www.dgshipping.gov.in)

It includes history and growth of maritime education in India, Educational methodology offered by Maritime Education and Training (MET), Maritime Education and Training (MET) during the Period of Covid-19 Pandemic and understands the digital marketing platform applied by maritime educational institutions in the period of Covid-19 pandemic.

1.4.1 HISTORY AND GROWTH OF MARITIME EDUCATION IN INDIA

As we reminisce, it becomes evident that the art of sailing or shipping does not require a lot of equipment or knowledge, rather it requires courage and excitement as we play with imminent danger. With time, navigation has changed from an art to a science. Originally the position and time were indicated by the stars and moon, but later they were replaced by the sextant and other chronometers. In the aftermath of the Industrial Revolution, vessel engineering underwent profound changes, vessel sizes increased dramatically, and simple rowing was replaced by engine-driven rowing and propeller-driven rowing. The ship's structural side and its power plant side saw significant changes during the past century, with the steam power plant evolving into a diesel power plant, then a gas turbine plant. Due to these developments, a diverse range of skills has become prevalent among seafarers, which has necessitated the development of formal marine education systems worldwide.

Ismail Yusuf, the owner of the Bombay Steam Navigation Company, founded the first training facility in 1910 at Worli, Mumbai. Later, the facility was moved to Nhava on the outskirts of Mumbai. On April 5, 1919, the first ship owned by an Indian, the S.S. "Loyalty," sailed from Bombay Harbor to London. M/s Scindia Steam Navigation Co. was the boat's owner and the master and the other officers were from the United Kingdom. The Royal Indian Marines' largest troop ship, which underwent several modifications, was transformed into Training Ship Dufferin, a mercantile marine training

ship, in 1972 which had trained 2,656 cadets. In order to replace the outdated "Dufferin," orders were filed with Hindustan Shipyard, Vishakapatnam, for the building of a new training ship. On October 20, 1969, a keel was laid for a new ship. This vessel was given the name T.S. Rajendra.

Later, when it was decided that the production needed to be increased, TS Rajendra was decommissioned in favour of a shore-based building called Training Ship Chanakya, which was built in New Mumbai. The Directorate General of Shipping (DG Shipping), which is our nation's top authority on shipping regulation and is based in Mumbai's Jahaz Bhavan, is in charge of the operational growth of the maritime industry and marine education sector in India. They implemented all the guidelines for the growth of maritime industry and marine education sector. Their continuous evaluation, persistent efforts and guidance have played a significant role in the development of maritime education in India.

The task of accrediting the educational institutions that provide maritime education has been taken on by DG Shipping. It divided the maritime courses three types namely the modular courses, competency courses and various familiarization courses. Due to the necessity of high degree of infrastructure, offering competency courses is a greatest challenge for government offering maritime courses. Hence, in 1997 DG shipping allowed the private players to come into this field who can able to invest huge money to provide innovative and simulated infrastructure for the students pursuing maritime education. Allowing investment from the private sector does not relieve the government from any obligations. In fact its responsibility increases to the extent that it has to supervise the operational methods applied by the educational institutions to offer maritime education both theatrically and practically.

Currently there are more than 57 maritime colleges operating in India offering maritime education and nautical science courses to the students at affordable cost. The top maritime engineering colleges in India offering effective maritime education to students are Indian Maritime University (IMU) Chennai, Vels Academy of Maritime Studies Chennai, Tolani Maritime Institute (TMI) Mumbai, Maharashtra Academy of Naval Education & Training (MANET) Pune, International Maritime Institute (IMI) Noida, International Maritime Academy (IMA) Chennai, Institute of Technology & Marine Engineering (ITME) Kolkata, Coimbatore Marine College (CMC), Academy of

Maritime Education & Training (AMET University) and Samundra Institute of Maritime Studies , Mumbai. It has to be noticed that four among them are in Chennai.

1.4.2 EDUCATIONAL METHODOLOGY OFFERED BY MARITIME EDUCATION AND TRAINING (MET)

In the past, the maritime sector has depended on apprenticeship and unstructured, informal learning obtained via experience on board ships to develop marine competences for its employees (Manuel, M.E., 2017). Developing knowledge and skills in a social and practical setting was encouraged by this apprenticeship concept. MET has evolved from an informal apprenticeship model to a formal, structured, internationally unified education with defined learning outcomes for certification and promotion since 1978 when the Standards of Training, Certification, and Watch keeping (STCW) convention was introduced and adapted by most maritime nations (Weintrit, A., Neumann, T., 2013& STCW, 2011). Due to the STCW's adaption, MET now adheres to the standard of school-based vocational education. The STCW recommends that MET pursue a mix of formal education and on-the-job training. Thus, METs curriculum adopted theory-based education such as classroom, textbook, theory; and practice-based education namely hands-on experience via simulators and at-sea. Over the years, MET has evolved in terms of content and learning outcomes, but training and education seafarers involves combining (i) theoretical knowledge gained from traditional lectures and studies; (ii) practical experience gained through simulator training and seagoing experience (STCW, 2011).

Introduction of simulators in 1950s have developed to become a more and more crucial component of MET and seafarer certification (Sellberg, C., 2017). In order to meet the needs of students and professionals for safety-critical work tasks, simulators have been utilized in various aspects of the maritime industry as a training tool. The training ranges from technical skills for bridge and engine operation, to fire safety, emergency response, crane and winch operations, cargo handling, and non-technical skills for bridge and crew resource management (Wahl, A.M., 2020). Simulations for MET include small single equipment task trainers to full mission engine rooms and 360-degree view bridge simulators, with varying levels of technical sophistication and fidelity. Simulators incorporate realistic physics engines, equipment hardware and wave motions, similar to those experienced at sea, into simulation software (Veritas, D.N., 2011). The importance of simulators for MET is well recognized by the IMO and

educational institutions and they applied the same in an effective and efficient manner to provide successful maritime training to their students.

1.4.3 MARITIME EDUCATION AND TRAINING (MET) DURING THE PERIOD OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC

As the COVID-19 virus spreads worldwide (scientifically referred to as SARS-CoV-2 or SARS-CoV-2), educational institutions have been scrambling to devise new methods and approaches for ensuring that education is delivered uninterrupted despite various levels of lockdown and social distancing. The marine sector as a whole and stakeholders in Maritime Education and Training (MET) has suffered severe effects as a result of these actions. According to the study results made by International Association of Maritime Universities (IAMU) showed that 93% of the educational institutions' regular activities have got affected by Covid-19 pandemic lockdown (IAMU, 2020).

The pandemic has forced them to look into alternative ways of delivering their educational content. It is a greater challenge for the MET to provide effective facilities for the teachers and students to pursue the education through online (Bertram, V., Plowman, T., 2020). Due to the significance of simulators to MET, access issues to these facilities have a substantial impact on how education and training are implemented and, ultimately, how well students learn. Before COVID-19 became widely adopted, MET was already making the shift to a greater use of digitalized solutions, such e-learning, for new students and cadets wishing to enter the business, as well as for professional training and re-training across the maritime domain. But, seafarers find it more difficult to take part in classroom instruction for ongoing education and training than those in centralized shore-based professions because of the nature of their occupation.

Information and communication technologies (ICT) have made it possible to expand the environment for education and training. As a result of the pandemic's proliferation, the maritime domain and MET have been forced to adapt sooner than expected, allowing us to implement solutions that were already in development or were already in use before 2020 (König, J. et al., 2020). It is difficult for new maritime professionals to conduct simulation-based ancillary courses online, such as GMDSS, ECDIS, ROC & ARPA, and so on. It is difficult to complete courses that require the attendance of physical practical sessions, limited guidelines on conducting written and oral competency examinations using virtual tools, and difficulties with certification of completed courses. Despite the need, these difficulties are making it difficult for aspiring

sailors to complete their certification requirements and prepare for entry into the field (Renganayagalu, S.K., et al., 2022).

Diagram: 1.4.3–Online Learning in MET

Source: *online.osu.edu*

Different approaches have been adopted by them to have effective interactive online training namely e-learning and online assessment, remote simulator training and Virtual Reality-based simulators. For continued education during lockdown, several MET institutions have used online platforms to provide maritime education to the students under two categories namely synchronous and asynchronous learning. Asynchronous technique is the most popular e-learning method which includes reading materials, lecture slides, and video recordings of the lectures. Conversely, synchronous is frequently assisted by media like webinars, video conferencing, and live chat. Through online platforms, live lecturing provides the chance for immediate interaction between the professor and student, much like in a live classroom lecture ([www. online.osu.edu](http://www.online.osu.edu)).

1.4.4 DIGITAL MARKETING AND MARITIME EDUCATION

Career opportunities in the maritime industry continue to attract people due to their exciting and diverse nature. In the era of Covid-19, maritime educational institutions struggled a lot to teach courses through online mode. On the other hand, it is a challenging task for them to market their college or university to make the students to

enroll in their colleges. The maritime educational institutions find it easy to draw in new students using traditional marketing techniques, but it is too expensive and limited in its ability to reach a larger market. Hence, maritime colleges concentrated on digital marketing approach to promote their colleges particularly in the period of Covid-19. They designed and updated their website in a user-friendly manner provided with detailed information about their colleges, courses offered including certificate courses, transparency in fees structure, details about boat safety and water training courses, display of clarity information regarding sailing certifications and USCG captain licenses ad collection of online payment methods with various avenues. The various digital media platform utilized by the maritime education and training institutions are SEO (Search Engine Optimization), Content marketing, Social media marketing, Affiliated marketing, Pay-Per-Click (PPC) marketing, E-mail marketing and SMS marketing.

1.5 MARITIME COLLEGS AND UNIVERSITIES IN CHENNAI

The maritime courses offered by colleges and universities in Chennai are: -

1.5.1 Central University - The Indian Maritime University (IMU) (www.imu.edu.in.)

As a Central University, the Indian Maritime University was established by an Act of Parliament (Act 22) on 14th November 2008, and is poised to play a significant role in training maritime personnel. 14th November is celebrated as 'IMU Day' every year. It is headquartered in Chennai, and the new headquarters is located on 300 acres of land between East Coast Road and Old Mahabalipuram Road (Rajiv Gandhi Salai) at Semmancherry. The IMU has its regional campuses at Chennai, Mumbai, Kolkata, Visakhapatnam and Cochin. IMU now provides diploma, degree, postgraduate diploma, and postgraduate degree programmes in Nautical Science, Marine Engineering, Naval Architecture & Ocean Engineering, Ship Building & Repair, Maritime Management, Doctoral Programs, and Post-Sea Courses.

The University's main goal is to facilitate and promote maritime studies, training, research, and extension work with a focus on emerging fields of study such as oceanography, maritime history, maritime laws, maritime security, search and rescue, dangerous cargo transportation, environmental studies, and other related fields, as well as to achieve excellence in these and related fields and other matters connected with or incidental thereto. Through the provision of institutional and research facilities in such

branches of learning that it deems fit, the university contributes to the advancement of advanced knowledge, and also incorporates science and other key and frontier areas of technology and allied disciplines into its educational programs.

A special emphasis is given to the advancement of educational and economic interests and welfare of the people of India by promoting innovations in the teaching-learning process, inter-disciplinary studies, and research. As a catalyst in socio-economic transformation by promoting basic attitudes and values of essence to national development, it also promotes freedom, secularism, equality, and social justice as enshrined in Indian Constitution. By associating with local, regional, and national development issues, the university extends the benefits of knowledge and skills to individuals and society.

1.5.2 Private University

a) AMET University (www.ametuniv.ac.in.)

It is the India's first Maritime Deemed to be University for maritime-related education, training and research. AMET is nestled on the picturesque drive way of the east coast road and overlooks the deep blue sea cradled by the Bay of Bengal. The sole institution from India to join the International Association of Maritime Universities AMET was founded in 1993 with just 14 cadets who were being prepared for a future in the merchant navy through a Higher National Diploma programme in marine engineering. AMET's guiding principles are quality, dedication, knowledge, and excellence. On the 21st of August 2007, AMET became the first Deemed to Be University in India for maritime education, training, research and development activities because of its uncompromising efforts in maritime education and training and its ability to provide a global shipping industry with an unmatched maritime human resource.

Over 3000 students study at AMET through 7 schools and 2 intensive marine and marine-related research and training centers pursuing diploma and doctoral programs. The prestigious and globally renowned DET NORSKE VERITAS, Norway, awarded AMET the prestigious ISO 9001:2015 QMS compliance certificate. AMET offers excellent research, co-curricular, and extracurricular opportunities. AMET has been evaluated and recognised with an A Grade by the National Assessment and Accreditation Council (NAAC), a separate entity of the University Grants Commission, in September 2021. The certification is a sign of the NAAC's quality standards and is good for five years starting on September 13, 2021.

The education at AMET caters to the comprehensive development of all its students so as to make them better educated, more articulate and demanding. AMET was founded with the vision of ensuring a position of prominence among the world's maritime universities and with the mission of nurturing the finest intellectual capital base for the maritime industry - globally. In order to achieve this goal, modern teaching aids are used, well equipped workshops are used, a marine workshop provides hands-on training in marine auxiliaries, a ship on campus, well-furnished dormitories, canteens, indoor and outdoor games, swimming pools, medical facilities, and an overall conducive learning environment are provided.

Many shipping juggernauts, like AP MOLLER MAERSK, GOODWOOD, NYK, SONANGOL, VSHIPS, WALLEMS, SHELL, CHEVRON, STENA, and more continue to pick AMET as their preferred campus interview location after more than 20 years. Graduates of the AMET Business School have also landed lucrative professions in the commercial maritime industry, including ship brokerage and chartering. However, alumni of the AMET programme in naval architecture, petroleum engineering, harbour engineering, marine electrical and electronics engineering have been successful in landing positions with generous salaries and the chance to advance quickly in their careers.

AMET has established a reputation as a top institution for maritime and marine-related occupations thanks to its constant placement record. It has also established a reputation as a reliable consultant for research and development projects, the cost of which can reach several crores of rupees. The honours and recognition that AMET has received for a variety of pursuits of excellence during the past 20 years in maritime education, training, research, and development attest to these accomplishments. Over 400 foreign students attend AMET, representing more than 10 different nations, demonstrating the institution's commitment to promoting cross-cultural understanding, which is the most important characteristic for working in a global setting, and to respecting diversity.

b) Vels University(www.velsuniv.ac.in)

Vels Educational Trust was founded in 1992 with the goal of developing an individual into a whole person with character and talent who is dedicated to national service and growth. Dr. Ishari K Ganesh, a visionary and outstanding educationist, established the trust in loving remembrance of his father, Shri. Isari Velan, a former minister in Dr. MGR's popular government. Vels Educational Trust has always worked

to bring education to the doorsteps of first-generation students and underprivileged members of society. The Vels Group of Institutions was granted university status by the Government of India's Ministry of Human Resource Development. As a result, the original Chairman, Dr. Ishari K. Ganesh, has been appointed President/Chancellor, and he is now in charge of implementing the strategic plan that will define the institute's future growth. He envisions a more globally competitive and internationally respected university.

On the campus of Vels Thalambur lies the School of Maritime Studies. A Director oversees the school, and among its faculty are highly skilled lecturers who were formerly sailors and instructors with years of experience both on board ships and onshore who take great care to prepare the cadets to become future navigating officers and marine engineers. For the purpose of giving cadets the essential instruction, the School contains three advanced workshops, a cutting-edge "Full-mission Navigation Simulator," and three labs. Cadets are brought aboard ships in Chennai harbour as part of the curriculum to familiarise them with naval life. For navigating officers and marine engineers in the merchant navy, "School of Maritime Studies" offers an integrated and comprehensive facility that has been graded A1 by the Ministry of Shipping and is among the best maritime institutions in India.

Candidates who finish their training at this school successfully will be qualified to work as marine engineers or navigating officers on any ship traversing the world's oceans. Students who complete the B.Sc. in Marine Operations will have the knowledge and abilities to succeed at the highest levels in the maritime and offshore sectors. The IRS first granted an ISO 9001:2015 Certification to the School of Maritime Studies in South India.

1.5.3 Colleges Affiliated to State University

a) GKM Institute of Marine Sciences and Technology (www.gkmims.net.in)

The G.K.M. Institute of Marine Sciences and Technology, located in Chennai, is a top-tier training facility for marine sciences and technology founded by Dr. G. Kathamuthu, chairman of the Suganthi Educational Trust, with Dr. Sujatha Balasubramanian serving as chief executive officer, Dr. K. P. Jagannathan serving as director, and Mr. C. Balasubramanian serving as a highly qualified and experienced master mariner and marine industry expert. The institution is situated 5 kilometres off the main route between Chennai and Chengalpet (NH45). The Directorate General of

Shipping, Mumbai has given its approval for the almost 10-acre facility. Both UG and GME programmes are available.

The college is ISO 9001: 2015 accredited by IRQS and has an efficient QMS that covers teaching, learning, and all other supporting operations. The Directorate General of Shipping, Mumbai has approved the "GKM KAMAASHI " - SHIP IN CAMPUS, which offers the cutting-edge facilities for practical hands-on afloat training for the Marine Sciences and Engineering students right on campus. The institution offers top-notch infrastructure to satisfy the needs of the professors and students. A well-equipped computer lab, internet centre, communication skills lab, central library, audio-visual facilities, conference room for group discussions, and digital library are all part of the centralised information centre. For Marine officer Cadet trainees, the College offers a separate hostel facility with a 24-hour security system. The college offers transportation services for the whole city of Chennai and its suburbs.

b) International Marine Academy (IMA)(www.collegechalo.com)

The International Maritime Academy (IMA) was founded in 1999. To administer the marine courses, IMA is a Private Ltd. firm formed under Section 25. It has been authorized by the International Accreditation Organization (IAO), Houston, USA, and accredited by the Directorate General of Shipping (DGS), Ministry of Shipping, Government of India. Additionally, the UK's Royal Institute of Naval Architects (RINA) granted it Provisional Accreditation. The courses are taught by IMA in technical cooperation with Annamalai University. IMA initially accepted 40 students with GP ratings; today, it accepts 80. With 20 students, IMA launched DNS from IGNOU in 2004. Today, it is offering long-term courses. India's top academy for maritime education is called IMA.

In order to provide a realistic approach to the learning process, it developed its Ship-in-Site training facility on the academy campus. In the area of marine training and education, IMA has a very good reputation. The institute offers cutting-edge marine workshops, training tools, and other equipment to its pupils in order to deliver top-notch instruction. Numerous Undergraduate, Postgraduate, Diploma, and PhD programmes are offered by IMA. It is one of the most significant training facilities for seagoing cadets in the country. It is the Top Maritime Education Academy in India. On the actual academy campus, the Institute has built its own Ship-In-Campus training facility. It has a solid reputation in the field of marine education and training and offers all students superior

training. In order to give top-notch training to the whole emerging workforce, it also houses a cutting-edge marine workshop, training tools, and other equipment. The Institute has received the endorsement of the Directorate General of Shipping and is accredited by the International Accreditation Organization. In technical cooperation with Annamalai University, it is also offering courses.

c) Southern Academy of Maritime Studies (www.samsmarine.org.)

The Southern Academy of Maritime Studies (SAMS) was established as a result of the Chairman of the Group's aspiration as a mariner. The Institute has been around for 23 years. SAMS had a modest beginning, offering STCW courses at first, but the Institute expanded quietly but aggressively. Today, SAMS is one of the top marine institutes in the nation, providing a variety of marine degrees. The European Maritime Safety Association (EMSA), a division of the International Maritime Organization, has rated SAMS as a very good maritime college in India. The Directorate General of Shipping, the Ministry of Shipping, and the Government of India have recognised the courses given by the Institute, and it is connected with prestigious universities like Anna University, Alagappa University, Indian Maritime University, etc.

The College has a built-up area of over 2 lakh square feet and is situated on a large 10 acre parcel of land. Its campus offers amenities including a well-equipped workshop and lab, WiFi access, a gym and recreational areas for both indoor and outdoor games, as well as hygienic and nourishing meals to appeal to visitors (North and South). The Institute is situated on a sprawling 10 acres of land, an hour from the heart of the city, with a built up area of 2 lakh sq.ft comprising of excellent infrastructure, Workshops, Labs, Ship in Campus, Auditorium, Gym, Recreation facilities, state of the art Class rooms, living rooms, etc. and highly qualified and dedicated faculties.

The Institute offers a great environment for studying and developing as a professional mariner. The Training Department arranges campus interviews by inviting various firms for student on boarding training. It serves two purposes: one for students to secure their future careers, and another for the industry to secure the best fresh talent available in the region to train and mould for their long-term employee needs. The cell conducts different training and grooming activities for students, such as mock interviews, Group Discussion sessions, resume preparation, and so on. The Ship Board Training unit also aids in the management of industry exchanges and relationships.

1.6 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- 1) To study the socio-economic status of the students perusing maritime education in Chennai.
- 2) To examine the level of effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19.
- 3) To ascertain the students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions in Chennai.
- 4) To study the student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai.
- 5) To ascertain the relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai.
- 6) To identify the impact of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai.
- 7) To suggest various measures to improvise the digital marketing in order to enhance the students' preferences towards maritime educational institutions.

1.7 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The main force advancing humanity today is technology, which has created enormous potential for the global industrial and service sectors. It has changed the lives of people in terms of communication, electronic goods, lifestyle products and many. It not only helps the industrial and service sectors to provide quality of goods and services, it also supports them to market their goods and services through digital media. Apart from the growth of internet, the introduction of smart phones with social application software has made the communication and social interaction of people faster and easier. Instead of communicating in person, anyone can talk to anybody by sitting in one place. Such a tremendous development has made by smart phones using digital media.

In particular social media plays a vital role in providing all updated information to people all over the world with respect to various sectors via internet including education sector. Higher education institutions are enlisting the help of digital marketing companies to develop an efficient strategy for communicating with future students, parents, industry experts, and other stakeholders in order to develop a strong brand image. The students are aware of courses, fees structure and other amenities offered by schools, colleges and universities through digital media. Online application filling, online

exams, correspondence by colleges through e-mail and whatsapp regarding admissions and seats available make easier for the students and parents to admit in colleges without travelling for a long time to visit the colleges each and every time.

Moreover, in the period of Covid-19 pandemic lockdown, digital media played a vital role in bridging a gap between the college and students by providing all facilities by sitting at home. The colleges and universities conducted classes through online and provide effective promotional through digital marketing to admit the students without visiting the colleges and universities in person. But, it is not an easier task for the maritime education that offers practical oriented classes than theoretical one. This study aids in understanding the effectiveness of digital marketing used by engineering colleges offering maritime education to promote their courses which in turn enhances the enrolment ratio in the period of Covid-19. It is not an easier task for the education sector to provide online classes as similar to off line classes.

Furthermore, it is difficult for technical oriented courses offered by engineering colleges to give simulation training through online. Hence, this study make us to understand how effective the online classes handled by maritime courses both theoretical and practical oriented classes and how far it satisfies the students pursuing the same. It also sketches out the students' opinion on digital marketing strategies used by Central University, colleges affiliated to State Universities and Private Universities that impact them to choose specific college or university. In addition, this study provides the clear understanding of the preferable digital media by students to get the promotional information about the college in an updated and fair manner.

1.8 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study is confined to the impact of digital marketing on students' preferences and decision making towards maritime educational institutions during covid-19 pandemic in Chennai. It merely studies about the level of effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai. The study has chosen six colleges and universities offering maritime education in Chennai which includes Indian Maritime University - affiliated to Central University, private universities such as AMET University, Vels Academy of Maritime Education and Training and the colleges

affiliated to state universities namely GKM College of Engineering and Technology, International Maritime Academy and Southern Academy of Maritime Studies. The digital marketing platform chosen by the study to identify its impact on students' preferences and decision making process with respect to maritime education are namely content marketing, search engine optimization, social media marketing, pay-per-click marketing, email marketing, instant message marketing and affiliate and influencer marketing. Moreover, it studies about the socio-economic status of the students in order to find out its association with their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education, effectiveness of online maritime education and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. The findings, suggestions and conclusions are based on the objectives, hypothesis and analysis made under the study.

1.9 PERIOD OF THE STUDY

The study is conducted during the period from 2019 to 2022. The review of relevant literature has been made from the sources like research journals and previous studies etc. The data required for the study has been collected from September 2021 to January 2022.

1.10 LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

- 1) The study is limited to influence of digital marketing on students' preferences and decision making towards maritime educational institutions during covid-19 pandemic in Chennai.
- 2) The study has chosen digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and does not taken into consideration of traditional marketing strategies applied by the institutions.
- 3) The study has chosen select seven digital marketing platforms namely content marketing, search engine optimization, social media marketing, pay-per-click marketing, email marketing, instant message marketing and affiliate and influencer marketing and exclude others.
- 4) The sample size of the study is limited to 400 students perusing maritime education in central university, private university and colleges affiliated to state universities in Chennai.

1.11 CHAPTERIZATION

Chapter-I

It presents the introduction of the study including problem definition, significance, scope and objectives of the study. It sketches out the overview of digital marketing, its evolution, types, and scenario in the era of Covid-19, its future prospects and its relationship with educational institutions. It also looks into the history and development of maritime education and training in India, education methodology applied by maritime educational institutions, its scenario in the era of Covid-19 and the various digital marketing platforms applied by the maritime educational institutions during Covid-19 pandemic lockdown.

Chapter-II

It covers literature review of both Indian and foreign studies with respect to the variables identified from preliminary data collection namely effectiveness of online education, impact of covid-19 pandemic on educational institutions and digital marketing, effect of digital marketing on enhancement of enrolment ratio and students' preferences and decision making towards educational institutions and the effectiveness of digital marketing on other service sectors during covid-19 pandemic situation.

Chapter- III

It presents the step wise operations carried out in this research work. It covers research objectives, pilot study, operationalizing the variables, conceptual framework of the study, sources of data, instrumental design, data analysis procedure, reliability and validity were justified using pilot study and by applying Confirmatory Factor Analysis. It also looks into the sample size, sample area and sampling technique, hypothesis formulation and in-detail explanation of statistical tools used for the study namely t-test, ANOVA, descriptive statistics, chi-square, correspondence analysis, bivariate correlation, multiple linear regression, Friedman test and Structural Equation Modelling.

Chapter-IV

This chapter revolves around data analysis and interpretation of influence of digital marketing on students' preferences and decision making towards maritime educational institutions during covid-19 pandemic in two parts. The first part analyses the association between students' socio-economic status with their opinion on digital marketing strategies, effectiveness of online maritime education and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education. The second part analyses the

significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education; and the significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' decision to pursue maritime education. These analysis and interpretation are critically evaluated and summarized to give findings and suggestions.

Chapter V

This chapter presents the summary of findings, suggestions, conclusion and directions for further research.

CHAPTER II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Technology has radically changed people's lifestyle and behaviour, affecting their decision making across all fields. In fact, in the period of Covid'19, the digital marketing landscape has drastically changed people's attitudes and preferences towards goods and services including education (OECD, 2019). Because of the rigorous lockdown, educational institutions have shifted their offline learning to online learning and emphasized the use of digital media to promote their schools, colleges and universities which impacted the decision making of parents and students towards the choice of their academic area (OECD, 2020).

This study has undertaken to find out the impact of digital marketing and effectiveness of online education on students' preferences and decision making process towards maritime education in Chennai, Tamilnadu. The review of literature is classified into studies made by foreign and Indian authors with respect to the variables identified from preliminary data collection namely effectiveness of online education, impact of covid-19 pandemic on educational institutions and digital marketing, effect of digital marketing on enhancement of enrolment ratio and students' preferences and decision making towards educational institutions and the effectiveness of digital marketing on other service sectors during covid-19 pandemic situation.

2.2 EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE EDUCATION

a) Foreign Studies

Alkabaa, A.S., 2022

Since the Covid-19 outbreak was proclaimed in December 2019, it has progressed across the nations, compelling majority of educational institutions to switch from face-to-face learning to online learning. This research examined students' perspectives and experiences while using Blackboard as an online platform for online learning with respect to top universities in Saudi Arabia and the Middle East. 235 undergraduate students (both male and female) were surveyed using questionnaire methods to collect data from them regarding their experiences and perception towards e-learning. The study's findings addressing how gender and engineering specialties are seen differently on Blackboard are highly noteworthy. Moreover, it is found that gender and engineering

disciplines are significantly different in their perceptions and experiences with respect to online learning.

Baber, H., 2022

The COVID-19 epidemic has shifted much classroom learning to an online setting with which most students are unaccustomed. In a pandemic setting with established social distancing norms, the purpose of this study is to examine the impact of social contact on the efficiency of online learning. In order to analyze the data, the study applied partial least square (PLS) through Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach. The students who were studying online were surveyed using the snowball sampling approach and requested to share the survey link with their networks. The findings of the study indicated that social contact significantly improves the efficacy of online learning. In the context of social distance rules, however, this impact is diminished since individuals place a higher value on lifesaving and ongoing education than they do on socializing online.

Mushtaha, E., et al., 2022

One of the main sectors that the COVID-19 epidemic has impacted is education. The objective of this study is to evaluate how the COVID-19 epidemic has affected students and faculty members learning in higher education, the challenges faced and opportunities available to them by comparing with other colleges. Quantitative research design was used to collect data from 1713 respondents including 1486 students and 227 full-time faculty members at the University of Sharjah. The study findings revealed that flexibility in place and time was the greatest advantage the students and teachers enjoyed during online learning. It also found that assessment and communication methods applied by the colleges positively impact the student's perception towards online learning. The quick adoption of eLearning during the COVID-19 epidemic had detrimental effects on respondents' mental health and socialising, which was the sole disadvantage experienced by the students and faculty members.

Akram, F., et al., 2021

The Covid'19 pandemic has changed the world into online and has made a greater challenge for teaching field to educate the students through online mode. The current study sought to examine the impact of student engagement, instructors' abilities and techniques, training, teaching domain, and teaching perspective on the efficacy of online teaching. The primary data was gathered through emails from Pakistani university professors using a convenience sampling technique and structural equation modelling

was applied to analyze the data. Based on the findings of this study, student participation, teachers' skills, strategies, their training, domain, and perceptions have a significant positive effect on the effectiveness of online teaching. The study concluded that in order to improve the effectiveness of online instruction, universities and colleges must concentrate on the needs of individual teachers..

Asgari, S., et al., 2021

Because of the COVID-19 epidemic, many educational institutions have abruptly switched from traditional face-to-face instruction to an online model. The study observed the effectiveness of online education in engineering colleges at California State University, Long Beach. Six engineering departments' 627 students and 110 staff members were chosen as a sample size to collect data both quantitatively and qualitatively regarding the difficulties they had while completing their online coursework in the spring of 2020. The findings of the study revealed that number of factors that adversely impacted online engineering education, including technological hurdles, logistical hurdles, privacy and security worries, learning and teaching difficulties, and a lack of enough hands-on training. Moreover, majority of the students said that it is difficult for them to have attention and keep engaging during on online teaching.

Bartusevičienė, I., et al., 2021

The recent occurrence of disruptions including pandemics, natural catastrophes, and social unrest has left colleges in an unstable state, which has impacted educational processes. This paper discusses resilient universities in the context of academic continuity. A literature review of resilient organizations and academic continuity as well as a case study of the World Maritime University (WMU) located in Malmö, Sweden were conducted in order to examine student and faculty perceptions and lessons learned in the context of COVID-19. The case study employed focus group method and online questionnaire method to collect data from the students. The results of the study found that a university's ability to foster resilience depends on cultivating anticipating skills, coping skills, and adaptability skills.

Butnaru, G.I., et al., 2021

During a time when online education is the only available option for students, this study examines their perceptions about its effectiveness. There has been some evidence indicating that online instruction can be as effective as traditional instruction, although fewer studies have examined learner satisfaction with online instruction, especially during the transition to online instruction. 784 students from Iași's Virgil Madgearu

Technological Economic High School and Alexandru Ioan Cuza University who were enrolled in online courses made up the population under study. The sample size includes the entire population and everyone has got an opportunity to express their views. The findings show that different students have varied responses to online learning, and that these responses depend on a variety of factors, including the students' comfort level with accessing online resources, their technical capabilities to access online classes, and the way in which the instructors manage the learning activities.

Eka Desi Natalia, V., et al., 2021

The advent of the Covid-19 virus raised concerns in the domains of health, economy, social, politics, and education around the world. Because of this, educational institutions all around the world have carried out online learning by utilizing online technology. This study aims to evaluate the efficacy of online education that has been used in several Asian nations. The study was qualitative in nature which was reviewed the literature of many researchers and the data was gathered from several government regulations. It has been concluded that online learning is capable of speeding up the process of change and reform in education in Asian nations. However, online learning still has a long way to go, so all sectors of the education system need to support it.

Kamysbayeva, A., et al., 2021

Considering COVID-19 and its potential repercussions and expectations, new educational standards are being developed on the basis of interdisciplinary and comprehensive research and evaluation. The research is devoted to the study of modern e-learning challenges in the context of social distance, the analysis of learning experience, problems and opportunities associated with online learning. The study was conducted to analyze the current e-learning issues in the context of social distance, e-learning experience and problems and possibilities linked with online learning. 300 graduate students were surveyed to collect primary data and the participants were allowed to share their e-learning experiences in the period of Covid'19. The research was quantitative in nature. The study's results demonstrate that online learning is an efficient method for developing hard skills, while it is less effective for improving soft skills.

Koob C, et al., 2021

This study explored the factors that influence the professions students' study engagement with respect to health and social professions programs during the COVID-19 pandemic by applying demands-resources-theory. The research design adopted for the study was

cross-sectional in nature that consists of 559 university students of health and social professions in Germany. The findings of the study showed that the demands-resources-theory is appropriate for explaining study participation even in pandemic situation. It is also found that the strong sense of psychological resilience, active self-care and academic self-efficacy of students are considered as the key resources for successful study engagement during major life events. It is concluded that the educational content should be offered in beneficial formats and innovative ways to support students who don't have support networks as a result of pandemic conditions.

Mahyoob, M., 2021

The study applied constructivist and humanistic learning theories to identify the learners' perceptions of the effectiveness of e-learning during COVID-19. In order to assure the attainment of educational quality during unprecedented online learning, the study looked into the key learning activities, namely online learning preference, effectiveness, participation, successes, and given assessment assignments. The study included 333 students pursuing bachelor degree as a sample size and the data was collected through questionnaire method. The study's conclusions highlight the important role that online learning plays in helping students achieve academic success across the majority of learning domains, with the exception of assigned assessment domain that presents challenges for online learning.

Nhatuve, D., 2021

The purpose of this study was to look into the effectiveness of online teaching and learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic at a university in Zimbabwe. Quantitative research design was adopted for the study and the data was collected from 202 students by sending online questionnaire in Google form. According to the study findings, the e-teaching and e-learning strategies implemented to lessen the effects of the COVID-19 Pandemic were ineffective. Majority of the students felt online learning provides frustration for them and it is difficult for them to learn effectively. They stated that the failure and ineffectiveness was due to the difficulties in establishing and maintaining meaningful interactions between lecturers and students as well as ineffective teaching methods. The study came to the conclusion that in order to improve the effectiveness of e-learning the higher education institutions should fund the necessary technology and train teachers in e-learning competences.

Slimi, Z., 2020

This study provides an insight into Oman's higher education system's online teaching and learning experiences in confined circumstances. The main objective of this paper is to study the challenges faced by the students and faculty members during online learning, opportunities available to them to have effective learning. Quantitative research design was applied to collect data from 64 students and faculty members of International Maritime College Oman with respect to their online teaching and learning experiences. The study's findings indicated that, while online learning and teaching is a fresh experience in Oman, it is a demanding experience that has encouraged new learning and teaching techniques namely independent learning skills, problem-solving skills, communication skills and technological communication and IT skills. It is also found that the respondents were faced difficulties related to internet connection, cooperation between teachers and students, autonomy and technological infrastructure of the institutions in Oman.

Zheng, M., et al. 2021

The COVID-19 pandemic forced dental schools to close their campuses and move didactic instruction online. The abrupt transition to online learning, however, has raised several issues that have not been resolved. This study compared how well students thought online courses were viewed by them during the summer quarter of 2020 and investigated whether pedagogical elements were influencing their acceptance of online learning. The research also conducted an empirical evaluation of how online education affected students' course performance throughout the epidemic by applying quasi-experimental design. The sample size of the study includes 482 pre-doctoral students pursuing their studies in U.S dental school. According to the study's findings, the majority of online courses were favourably received by students, and 80% of them expressed a desire to continue taking certain online courses after the epidemic. The regression analysis also revealed that students perceived their online classes were overly effective since they felt engaged with their professors.

Hussain, I., et al., 2020

The most devastating epidemic in recorded history, the new coronavirus (COVID-19) has gravely damaged humans and frozen all spheres of existence. It has a stronger impact on the global education sector in particular due to the disruption of the traditional educational system that results in the closure of all educational institutions worldwide.

The world's educators began considering some effective solutions to this issue, and they ultimately decided that the greatest replacement for traditional classroom instruction at educational institutions was online learning. The current study was carried out to identify the efficacy of the online learning system during the COVID-19 wave. The population of the study includes teachers from one government and one private educational institution in Sargodha which was selected by applying convenient sampling technique. Based on the findings, study is revealed that remote learners can meet their educational needs using online learning, which is an effective and efficient mode of learning.

Obeidat, A., et al., 2020

In response to the unprecedented COVID-19 crisis majority of higher education institutions worldwide were shut down, the danger of viral spread among the general populace, and the distribution of educational information was switched from traditional classroom instruction to online delivery. This study sought to determine how well students at Jordan's Hashemite University perceived the efficiency of the e-learning programme during the COVID-19 epidemic. The sample size of the study is consisted with 399 students. The study's findings demonstrated that students' assessments of their e-learning experiences as a whole were generally favourable. It also found from the study that majority of the difficulties that students described in their e-learning experiences, nevertheless, were technological in nature (e.g., lack of a viable internet network, lack of laptops, etc.). In addition, it is found that most of the students preferred to have Microsoft Teams and smart phones to pursue their e-learning.

b) Indian Studies

Darius, P.S.H., et al., 2021

Through the use of an online survey, the researcher of this study evaluated the efficacy of online teaching and learning techniques for university and college students. The survey was conducted among 450 students from various universities, engineering colleges, medical colleges in South India through questionnaire method in order to collect data regarding the effectiveness of online teaching. The study found that video lectures, online quiz, animations, user-friendly software, interactions by faculty members, digital collaborations, conducive environment and softcopy of subject materials promoted the effectiveness online learning. Moreover, it is found that application of PPT to conduct online classes and comfortable and flexible learning from anywhere at any place are the major advantage for the students to consider online class as an effective one.

Muthuprasad, T., et al., 2021

Due to the COVID-19 epidemic, educational institutions all around the world have switched to online learning platforms to maintain academic activity. In spite of these issues, questions remain about e-learning's preparedness, design and effectiveness, particularly in developing countries such as India, where technical constraints such as device compatibility and bandwidth availability pose a significant challenge. The purpose of this study is to derive insight into the perception, preferences and various aspects of online class of 307 Agricultural Students towards online learning. The results indicated that majority of respondents have expressed their readiness to manage curriculum through online courses during this pandemic period. Furthermore, majority of students prefer smart phones for online learning, and prefer recorded classes with quizzes at the end to maximize their learning effectiveness. Most of the students like to prefer online class considering its convenience and flexibility and at the same time they have negative perception due to connectivity issues in rural areas.

Selvaraj, A., et al., 2021

The Corona virus outbreak disrupted the academic world, stranding millions of registered students and engaged teachers at home. Due to this, the online class was introduced in most countries, including India. The purpose of this study was to evaluate how well Indian teachers and students responded to online classes. In addition, it made an effort to comprehend the experiences and issues faced by the students and the teachers through online classes. The population of the study includes students and teachers from schools and colleges across the country. Four set of questionnaire was framed using Google form for students and faculty members of schools and colleges to get the data from them regarding effectiveness of online class, their comfort level, knowledge transfer and others. The results of the study indicated that online majority of the schools and colleges used Google Meet, and Google classroom for online classes than preferring Zoom and Microsoft teams. It is also found that insufficient study materials, limited data pack, socialization, interruption by family members during class hours, poor internet connectivity, lack of practical sessions and accessibility issues are the challenges faced by both students and faculty members.

Veena. M., et al., 2021

The Covid'19 outbreak forced the educational institution to shift to online teaching which was totally unfamiliar to the students. The study was conducted to understand the students' interest towards online learning and the factors which influence the effectiveness of online teaching and learning by using questionnaire method. Based on the analysis, the study found that the students are uncomfortable and showed lack of interest towards online learning. It is also found that they need good infrastructure, training to the faculty members to handle online class innovatively and orientation programme for the students to adapt to the online classes. The study concluded that the regulatory bodies, universities, and educational institutions need to set a syllabus, provide all necessary infrastructures and design various assessment methods to provide effective online class to the students.

Dhawan, S., 2020

In the aftermath of the sudden outbreak of the Covid'19 pandemic, the education system across the globe was forced to adopt an online mode of instruction. In this study, the SWOCs (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Challenges) of e-learning during a crisis were identified. Descriptive research design was adopted to review the previous studies, reports, journals, search engines, websites in order to understand the significance of online learning and challenges faced by students and faculty members during Covid'19 pandemic situation. Based on the secondary data, the study found that in order to improve the online learning qualities among the students, educational institutions must incorporate adaptability into their processes. The study concluded that disasters and pandemics like Covid-19 may cause a great deal of confusion and strain; as a result, it is crucial to thoroughly and diligently study the technology to balance these concerns and tensions during such a crisis.

2.3 IMPACT OF COVID'19 PANDEMIC ON EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

a) Foreign Studies

Karaca, İ. & Söner, Ö., 2022

The world's supply chain, public health, education, and international trade are just a few of the areas that are being impacted by the Covid'19 pandemic. It also had a substantial impact on the perception of maritime students with respect to their marine profession and the maritime business as a whole. This study investigated how the students' perceive their marine careers after the effect of COVID-19 pandemic. The study used questionnaire method framed with Likert five point scaling technique to collect data from the students with respect to the perception of marine profession. The study's findings indicated that students had a more positive impression of their marine career and a greater grasp that the epidemic that is threatening the maritime sector is not permanent. Moreover, it is suggested by the students through personal interview that the government has to take further steps to frame an effective that matches the needs of the seafarer.

Butnaru GI, 2021

Going to school and shifting education online have been affected as a result of the COVID-19 epidemic. This paper analyzed the students' perception on effectiveness of online classes during Covid'19. The study collected data from 784 students using questionnaire method. The study's findings showed that different students have different responses to online learning, and that these responses depend on a variety of factors, including the students' comfort level, their technical capacity and the way in which the instructors manage the learning activities.

Ergun DEMIREL, 2021

The fundamental component for passing on our culture and civilization to future generations is education but it had a greater negative impact all over the world. Majority of the schools and colleges of various countries have transformed to online mode to conduct their class. But due to the applications of simulator activities and practical trainings for students pursuing marine education, it is difficult and greater challenge for them to conduct their class through online mode. Thus, in order to understand the actual situation, this study sought to assess the opinions and perceptions of the researchers, as well as those of MET professors and students. The data was collected by using questionnaire method. The results of the study indicated that majority of the students and

faculty members find it difficult to learn and teach the practical sessions through online mode. It is also found that application of innovative technology and alternative delivery methods may enhance the effectiveness of online classes.

Menhat M., et al., 2021

The marine industry is essential to boosting the country's economy in Malaysia. This study was undertaken to provide an overview of Covid-19 scenario and its impact on four marine sectors namely tourism, shipping, fisheries and oil and gas with respect to marine industry in Malaysia. The study is based on secondary data and hence it collected data from websites, journals, government reports etc. By comparing with other sectors, the study found that maritime tourism is considered as most affected one and shipping is considered less affected sector in Malaysia. Because of the strong lockdown that prevents individuals from other nations from travelling to other countries, including Malaysia, tourism is severely impacted, and given the increased demand for PPE supplies and test kits during the epidemic, shipping is less affected. Moreover, due to the border closure, revenues from the export of fish and fishery products to other nations have declined and there is a disruption in the supply of imported fish and fishery products. In addition, the study found that the usage of cars, industrial activity, shipping, and transportation has all significantly decreased as a result of MCO, which has a direct influence on the oil and gas industry.

Coman C, et al., 2020

The coronavirus pandemic has caused modifications in higher education institutions' teaching-learning processes and has transformed the offline teaching to online mode. The paper's objective is to determine students' perspectives on their experiences and difficulties faced with online learning during the coronavirus pandemic in order to enhance and improve the online learning system in Romanian universities. The data was collected by using semi-structured questionnaire from 762 students of two largest Romanian universities. The study's findings demonstrated that Romania's higher education institutions were unprepared for online teaching and due to this the students in Romanian universities faced with many problems such as technical issues, lack of technical skills, lack of interaction with teachers and improper adaption to online environment by students and teachers.

Gregorio S. Ochavillo, 2020

Covid'19 has had an impact on various industries in the Philippines and among all; educational sector has been deemed to be the most severely impacted one. Strict

lockdown forces schools to close abruptly including maritime education. Taking into account the current situation of the COVID-19 pandemic, this study intends to assess the abilities of maritime students to deal with the abrupt paradigm shift from face-to-face teaching to online learning, for the first time in maritime education. The study adopted descriptive-normative approach to collect data from the 2nd and 3rd year students pursuing maritime education in Philippines. The data was collected by using questionnaire method in Google Forms. It is found from the results of the analysis that the majority of maritime students were not prepared to cope with the paradigm shift due to the fact that they did not have a personal computer at home, did not have access to internet shops, and did not possess a computer for school work and personal wellbeing. It is also found that the students prefer to have face to face learning and needed softcopy of the subject materials to read comfortably at home.

b) Indian Studies

Jena, P.K., 2020

The Covid-19 pandemic has affected the education sectors all over the world. It has imposed the worldwide lockdown, having a very negative impact on the lives of the students. In order to overcome these problems and eliminate the pandemic danger, the education sector has been working to withstand crises with a new strategy. This research focuses on the steps the Indian government has taking to ensure that education is available throughout the nation. It also analyses the positive and negative impacts of COVID-19 on educational institutions. The study is based on secondary data and was collected from various reports, e-contents and websites and from national and international agencies. The survey revealed that the Ministry of Human Resource Development (MHRD) has set up a number of programmes enabling students to continue their education, including websites and educational channels on Direct to Home TV and radios. Additionally, it has been discovered that students use well-known social media platforms like WhatsApp, Zoom, Google Meet, Telegram, Youtube Live, Facebook Live, etc. during lockdown to access online classrooms. Moreover, the study found few positive impact of covid'19 on educational institutions namely blended learning, enhanced learning management systems, online meetings, collaborative work, digital literacy and demand for Open and Distance Learning (ODL). The negative impact found from the study is that hampered educational activity, reduced employment opportunities; unprepared teachers/students for online education, reduction and delay in payment of schools and colleges, higher obligation for parents to educate their children etc.

Mishra, L., et al., 2020

In India as well as around the world, the entire educational system has collapsed during the lockdown period for Corona virus Disease 2019. This study examines the methods of teaching and learning that Mizoram University uses for its teaching-learning process and subsequent semester exams during Covid'19 b conducting survey through questionnaire method with 260 students 78 faculty members in Mizoram University. It also discusses the need for online teaching and learning in the context of education during the COVID-19 pandemic and how existing educational institution resources can effectively convert traditional education into online education with the aid of virtual classrooms and other essential online tools in this constantly changing educational environment. Based on the analysis, the study found that the Due to their remote location, students had special obstacles with internet and video and were unable to reduce the amount of time needed for online class. It also found that during the lockdown era, there has been a growing understanding of the temporal significance and importance of online teaching and learning style.

2.4 IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON DIGITAL MARKETING

a) Foreign Studies

Antúnez L, et al., 2021

This study explored how the companies utilized the social media especially Facebook in promoting their ultra-processed products during COVID-19 pandemic. A master list of products sold in two Uruguayan online supermarkets was used to look for Facebook profiles for ultra-processed goods. The study's findings showed that 135 Facebook accounts were found in total, and these accounts posted a total of 1749 times on ultra-processed goods, 35% of which mentioned COVID-19. It was also discovered that the majority of the postings included references to preventative measures, and almost one-third of the posts provided suggestions for activities to undertake at home, the majority of which were related to a healthy lifestyle. Moreover, the study found that companies utilized the benefit of Covid-19 in promoting their ultra-processed products by applying digital marketing strategies through Facebook that has enhanced their brand image globally.

Khaled (M. K) Ismail Alshaketheep, et al., 2020

The study investigated the influence of Covid-19 pandemic on digital marketing and the consumer perspective towards it. The study examined whether Covid-19 pandemic provided an excellent opportunity for the organizations to transform their traditional marketing to digital marketing globally. It also analyzed the consumer perception on digital marketing and their decision making on goods and services based on it. The study collected data from 500 consumers in Amman, Jordan. Based on the analysis, the study found that during this Covid-19 pandemic businesses attracted the customers with incentives, anti-crisis bargains, tailored digital communication, and empathy. It is also found that covid-19 affect the digital marketing in a positive way and it has increased the awareness, perception and demand for the goods and services on customers.

b) Indian Studies

Siby K M, 2021

There is a remarkable increase in the digital payment method during the period of Covid-19 epidemic. This study analyzed the consumer perception on digital payment methods during the period of Covid-19 pandemic. The study collected primary data from 107 respondents from Ernakulam district, Kerala through a well-structured questionnaire via Google forms. It examined the role played by demographic characteristics of the respondents such as gender, age, education, profession, and employment on their perception towards digital payment methods. According to the study findings, it is proven that there is no significant difference between the consumers' demographic factors and their perception on digital payment methods in the era of Covid-19 pandemic.

Amit Saha & Debopriya Kar, 2020

As marketing is all about making connections at the proper time and place, online platforms are utilized to captivate, engage, and charm people that build brand awareness and identification while also converting viewers into potential buyers. The frightening effects of COVID-19, however, have caused a significant shift in the situation. It is a challenging moment for everyone as a result of job losses, company losses, cash flow issues, and many other effects of the Corona Virus spreading around the world. This study has explored how consumers perceive digital marketing in this time of adversity

and whether or not it has just served to improve its relevance during this period of social estrangement. The study has adopted stratified random sampling and selected the respondents randomly selected from the total population in each stratum. The sampling size chosen for the study was 200 and the questionnaire were systematically prepared and distributed to collect data from the respondents. The study's findings revealed that most of the respondents spent their major time on social media or watching television and therefore, the study concluded that digital marketing is the easiest way to raise awareness of the public with respect to purchase of goods and services. Brands like Myntra, Fabindia, Tjori, FabAlley, Zivame, and many more are trying their hardest to succeed in digital marketing with their innovative efforts to keep the customers engaged and active on social media. Based on the study's findings, it is widely accepted that Digital Marketing is the most effective marketing technique for food and healthcare products. This follows the current economic situation where most people are experiencing financial difficulty, and food and health are the most important aspects of one's life.

De', R., et al., 2020

Businesses and educational institutions are converting to work-from-home (WFH) policies as a result of increased digitization. This study looked into the use of information systems during the lockdown and the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on the use of digital technology by business organizations during post-pandemic of covid-19. The study's findings showed that the epidemic had a wide range of negative effects, including altering the political landscape of the world, bringing about the fall of empires, and forging new nations. Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic has largely shifted the traditional marketing to digital marketing and it changed the life of customers from offline to online mode. It is also understand that majority of the sectors including education; IT and many applied the work from home (WFH) practices to continue their service to the society. The study concluded that the work from home practices bridges the gap faced by the employees in continuing their career but its effectiveness with respect to trust, performance, communication and collaboration is said to be average.

2.5 EFFECT OF DIGITAL MARKETING ON ENHANCEMENT OF ENROLMENT RATIO AND STUDENTS' PREFERENCES AND DECISION MAKING TOWARDS EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

a) Foreign Studies

Mukosa, F., et al., 2022

Social Media Marketing is the use of internet technologies based on Web 2.0 to create relationships between businesses and customers. In the education sector in Zambia higher education institutions have adopted Social Media as part of their integrated marketing strategies. Research findings indicate that most literature in Zambia on Social Media has focused on the use of Social Media as a teaching aid and not necessarily as a marketing tool. In countries such as the USA and Australia Social Media has increased revenue for educational institutions and enhanced marketing performance for those institutions. The question of how effective Social Media Marketing is for marketing higher education institutions in Zambia is an interesting area of research. This research is a literature review that gathers facts from literature findings of scientific publications and from existing data on Social Media analytical platforms. The findings show that higher education institutions in Zambia need to develop a model for Social Media Marketing for them to enhance their marketing performance.

Nektarios S. MAKRYDAKIS, 2021

In the backdrop of the digital revolution, the digital transformation of marketing in Greek public higher education institutions is crucial. The study sought to examine the implicit and explicit impressions and opinions held by administrators of Greek public universities regarding the link between the use of digital marketing and the recruitment of students. Qualitative research design was adopted and in-depth interview is conducted with the 10 respondents (representatives) of Greek public universities. The study's results, according to the research, showed that administrators think internet marketing has a significant influence on attracting students, particularly young individuals getting ready to graduate from high school.

Ramadhan, A., & Gunarto, M., 2021

COVID-19's global prevalence has prompted all promotional activities to be digitally directed to target various sectors of global society in the wake of its global pandemic, particularly marketing efforts at private higher education (PHE) to attract prospective

students. The data for the study was collected through interviews and interactive communication media with students and internal university officials regarding the application of digital marketing strategies by their university. The study applied "SWOT" analysis approach matrix in order to determine the effectiveness and efficiency of digital marketing strategies applied by the university. especially in the marketing sector by analyzing internal and external influencing factors, subsequent research can make prospective new student registrants as respondents to consider marketing strategies. Specifically, it is found that apart from internal and external influences digital marketing strategies plays a significant role in the preferences and admission of the prospective students to the university.

Castro Benavides, L.M., et al., 2020

The study analyzed the digital transformation in higher education based on the literature review and presents the dimensions and functions associated by universities to integrate digital technology. The study is purely based on secondary data. The findings of the study revealed that university staff members correlated digital technologies with dimensions-functions such as education and infrastructure. Moreover, it s found from the studies that digital marketing is the most recent in terms has been developed. It is also found from the majority of the reviews that digital marketing is not viewed as a valuable tool by public university administrations because there is no culture of digital transformation, no measurable results in attracting students and no understanding of what digital marketing can do.

Cordero-Gutiérrez, R., & Lahuerta-Otero, E., 2020

In order to raise awareness and encourage participation in postgraduate programmes, this study aims to compare the various outcomes and levels of effectiveness of Facebook advertising strategies. Data envelopment analysis technique and multidimensional scaling (MDS) representation were combined to analyze the efficiency of social advertising, offering practitioners and organizations a variety of alternatives. The results of the study found that investments on social media advertising is seen as a cheap and efficient strategy to advertise postgraduate programmes and foster connection with potential students. Additionally, social media advertising increases online and social positioning, boosts visibility, and promotes student recruitment.

Kusumawati, A., 2019

During the past decade, Indonesia has experienced an increase in the number of private and public higher education institutions. As a result, there is now fierce rivalry, and

colleges are using cutting-edge marketing techniques like online marketing to draw in potential students. This study was conducted to explore how students utilize digital media and the role played by digital media with respect to students' preferences towards public university in Indonesia. It also looks into the knowledge of the Higher Education Institutions in using the digital media platform to provide information about their colleges. The study was qualitative in nature. Semi-structured questionnaire and interviews were conducted to collect data from the students. The study findings showed that majority of the students said that they depend and engage on the digital media to seek information regarding the university and the information provided in digital media about the university insist them to prefer the right college.

Aman, K., & Hussin, N., 2018

Digital marketing plays a vital role in the marketing area as it influences the consumer decision to prefer goods and services. This study investigated the effectiveness of social media marketing in higher education institutions. The factors which are taken into account to identify the effectiveness of social media marketing in higher education institutions are minimal cost, time saving and limited resources. The results of the study indicated that social media marketing highly increases the efficiency of higher education institutions and is found to be effective. In addition, it is found that based on the effective information provided by social media marketing, it also increases the students' enrollment and revenue to higher education institutions.

Kusumawati, A., 2018

Digital era has provided the new challenges and opportunities for HEIs. They used the digital marketing to promote their colleges and universities that attracted the students and other stakeholders to make aware of information and allowing them to interact with the institutions directly. This study investigated the significance of digital marketing on universities and students of five Indonesian public universities. The study was exploratory and qualitative in nature. The primary data was collected from prospective and current students by adopting purposive sampling technique and from managers of universities through interview method. The study described several university digital marketing strategies, their efficacy, and the influence they have on students' decision-making while choosing an institution. At a sizable public institution in Indonesia, it investigated, discovered, and understood the issue using a number of theories about digital marketing and the process by which students make decisions on higher educational studies. The results of the study revealed that the awareness of students

regarding digital marketing is at higher level and majority of them use digital media namely search engine, social media and university websites to get information about the HEIs. Moreover, it is found that social media in particularly Facebook has a greater impact on the students' decision on HEIs. They used university official website to gather information related to course offered and admission process. The study also revealed that very few students used offline media such as newspapers, university brochures, radio or television or directly visited the campus to get information of universities.

Peruta, A., & Shields, A., 2018

School marketing strategies often focus on social media marketing - updating and maintaining social media channels with the aim of connecting with prospective students and alumni. This study identified the strategies applied by universities to market their courses. The study applied content analysis to analyze the topics and formats of 5932 Facebook posts from top U.S. colleges and universities. It also provided the strategies used by the university social media managers in order to compose their social media content in a better way to improve engagement, marketing and wider response from the public for the post. The study's findings showed that although certain content themes have a propensity to diminish engagement, others, like sports, dramatically raise it. Another element that boosts engagement is the format, such as incorporating user-generated material.

Fierro, I., et al, 2017

Digital Marketing and its components have been emerging in International Education sector to improve its business practices and to attract and admit the students to their institutions. This study examined how the International Education sector has got positive results after the implementation of digital strategies. The study collected secondary data from various websites, journals and reports. The results of the study concluded that innovative technologies in digital marketing has improved the international education system which results in enhanced interaction of students and their preferences towards the educational institutions worldwide. The major goal of Big Choice Group is to become a global leader in international education, and it has been discovered that CRM is the most user-friendly technology for students to get information about universities.

Martin, C. M., 2015

This study was conducted to examine the effect of social media on collegiate recruitment in Indonesia. The results of the study found that social media marketing and email marketing have the multitasking ability in higher education by communicating with

multiple people at once across multiple platforms. They both have the attribute to communicate easier and in efficient manner with the students. The study also found that the digital marketing has a greater impact on the decision of students towards choice of universities in order to pursue their higher education. The study concluded that digital marketing is found to be the problem solver for educational institutions to provide transparency in information, to filter the negative comment and to reach the students all over the world with minimum cost.

Khan, R.H. (2013)

Communication in society has changed dramatically as a result of social media engagement, a by-product of the web 2.0 environment. Along with influencing consumer preferences for products and services, it also had an influence on students' preferences for higher education institutions. This study investigated the impact of Social Media Marketing attributes on Higher Education institutions in New Zealand. The results of the study revealed that Social Media Marketing attributes had a little impact on the students' preferences for higher education institutions. Furthermore, it has been shown that the higher educational institutions from New Zealand does not mobilize resources for establishing a clear, successful plan for using Social Media Marketing because of their mistrust and lack of commitment.

Constantinides, E., & Marc C. Zinck Stagno, 2012

Higher education institutions now place a strong emphasis on using social media to promote their universities and colleges which insist the students and parents to decision on choice of study in educational institutions. This article examined the role and significance of social media on the preferences of prospective students with respect to the universities and colleges in Netherlands. It also compares students' perception by comparing the digital marketing with traditional marketing. The study divided the respondents into three segments namely Basic users, Social users and Informational users. The results of the study indicated that social media is considered to be the highly influenced media to choose the universities and colleges by prospective students in Netherlands. Moreover, it is also found that apart from information provided in social media curriculum, reputation of a university, quality of life and presence of cultural, social, and sporting facilities also influences their preferences and decision towards universities and colleges.

Oya Y. Rieger, 2009

This study investigated the utilization of Web search engines in various patterns by faculty members and students to support their teaching, learning, and research. The study also examined the satisfaction of faculty members and students with respect to search outcomes and trust in search engines in supporting specific tasks. The data was gathered from faculty members and students by using Web-based survey, interviews, and search log reviews. The results of the study revealed that there is a variation in the use of search engine by the faculty members, graduate and undergraduate students. It also found that there exist a higher satisfaction of faculty members and students with respect to outcomes of their searches and trust in search engines.

Hayes, T.J., et al., 2009

This study analyzed the impact of social media on enhancement of admission in higher educational institutions in USA. It also looked at how social media is used by colleges as a marketing tool and how students rely on information shared by universities on social media to decide whether to apply to universities. Based on the results of the study, social media is considered an excellent two-way communication tool that enables the university to interact with students and prospective students in order to gather valuable information, which in turn enables the university to use it as a targeted promotion tool to influence university selections.

b) Indian Studies**Maity, S., 2022**

This study analyzed the impact of covid-19 on educational institutions and the factors that influenced the digital learning of students at primary education during Covid-19 pandemic situation. The study collected the primary data from 720 students [360 boys (50%) and 360 girls students (50%)] pursuing their education in primary schools from Standard III–VI in West Bengal, India. In order to collect data, the study has chosen Kolkata, Howrah, Paschim Mednipore, and Purulia districts in West Bengal. A study revealed that the school structure, the willingness of teachers and the school to conduct virtual classes, the accessibility and availability of high-speed internet, as well as the economic capability of parents to afford exorbitant internet charges play an important role in virtual learning for primary school students. In addition, the study revealed that girls and students from village government schools experienced the worst effects during the pandemic, as opposed to boys from city schools and private schools. A further conclusion can be drawn from the study which suggests that the structure of the school

system, the availability and accessibility of high-speed internet, the willingness of the school authority and teachers to conduct virtual classes, and parents' economic ability to pay internet charges are significant factors influencing the success of virtual classes for primary school students.

Dr. Gondane, V., & Pawar, M., 2021

The marketing and sales industries saw a significant transition in the present era of digitalization. In the midst of the pandemic, students and working professionals are very much fond on digital media and their usage towards internet is growing day by day. This study examines the impact of digital marketing on education sector with special reference to private institutions at Nagpur, India. The study results revealed that there is a significant difference between the digital marketing strategies applied by the colleges and the number of admissions of students i.e., before adopting digital marketing strategies, the admissions are found to be less and it has been gradually increased after adopting digital marketing strategies. It is also found that majority of the students' preferences towards the college depends on the information provided by the college through digital marketing.

Kumar, V., et al., 2021

Nowadays, digital marketing stands out as the options for choice as we have witnessed a significant shift from off line to internet marketing. By focusing on CTR as a gauge of the campaign's performance, the study evaluated the impact of Google Ad words as employed in digital advertising campaigns promoting business, especially in business schools i.e., this paper identified the effective online advertising strategy used by a Business Schools (B Schools) . According to the findings, it is understand that different types of advertisements have varied click through percentages, with advertisements in the admissions category having a greater CTR than all other categories. It also found that online advertising strategies had a greater impact on the marketing of business schools. The study suggested that online advertising can also be utilized by other educational institutions to promote their admissions and students' preferences on colleges and to improve their Return on Investment (ROI).

Mohit Kumar, et al., 2021

Due to Covid-19 lockdown, Educational sector wholly transformed from offline to online education. This study inspected the impact of digital marketing communication on student's attitude and decision behaviour towards admission in higher educational institutions in Rajasthan. The study applied descriptive research design. The data was

collected from the 672 students pursuing their studies in schools, colleges and universities of Rajasthan by using questionnaire method. The results of the study revealed that there is a significant association between students' attitude and their decision making behaviour with respect to admission. Additionally, the study revealed that within the objective group under consideration, there is a significant degree of mindfulness towards digital media. According to the study's findings, students' of digital media and their attitude as a whole have a significant impact on their decision making behaviour with respect to admission.

Mohit Kumar, et al., 2021

An effective digital marketing campaign utilizes refined tools such as SEO, online journals, audits, viral marketing, show advertisements, web-based media pop-up messages, which can allow global engagement. This study analyzed the growth of digital marketing communication and its impact on student decision making process regarding higher studies in India. The study collected primary data by using both online and offline questionnaire and collected the secondary data from journals, reports, periodicals and magazines. The results of the study revealed that majority of the students were agreed that digital technology plays a crucial role in their decision towards higher education. It is also found that majority of the students strongly agreed that digital media saves their time and cost in searching for information about the colleges and universities. Moreover, it is understood from the study that majority of the students said that their awareness towards higher educational studies and courses is enhanced through digital media. The study concluded that digital marketing communication had a significant and high effect on the students' decision making process for higher studies in India.

Rajkumar, S.G., et al., 2021

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected the Indian education sector and the students' enrolment to it. Due to this heavy competition has been raised between the higher educational institutions and they spend huge amount on advertising, branding and PR activities to attract and admit the students into their colleges. A key component of this research paper is the analysis of the role that digital marketing plays in leveraging the Decision-Making Process for Student Admissions, especially during times of pandemics such as Coronaviruses. According to the study, universities and colleges need to incorporate continuous and engaging user-generated content into their marketing efforts so that prospective students can be reached for admission and enrollment. This can be accomplished through text, images, info graphics, videos, and podcasts.

Biswas, S., 2020

Through the use of DM, an organization is able to develop a lasting relationship with its clients, create value propositions that gain business, provide specialized goods and services, and successfully position its brands by developing "pull" factors. It also provides the HEIs with a source of competitive advantage. This study examined the main effects of DM for the HEIs using an expert opinion-based intuitionist fuzzy and multi-criteria group decision-making framework. Based on the study, it was found that DM can play a critical role in higher education by identifying needs, building relationships and engagement, and communicating transparently. The study concluded that HEIs' competitiveness will be determined by establishing effective and transparent communication channels, understanding latent customer needs, and building long-term relationships. This will be achieved through DM's role in co-designing, co-developing, and co-executing mutually beneficial value propositions between HEIs, students and parents, employers, and other stakeholders.

Dr.Ghosal, I.,et al.,2020

Any country's growth may be shown positively by the Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in higher education. The study analyzed the several perceived factors (Social media marketing, third party portal, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), printed and video portal advertisement and online counselling) influencing the enrolling mechanism used by private institutions through the extraction of weight vectors orthogonally and compared the same with demographic factors. The study adopted descriptive research design and the data was collected from the students pursuing undergraduate and post graduate programmes in private universities. The findings of the study revealed that through digital media the universities can promote the GER and it strengthen the education system at higher level (HES) with resilient and sustainable foundation. It also found that Social media Marketing (SMM) had a significant impact on gender preferences towards private universities.

Prihadini, D., 2020

This study examined the role played by the digital marketing during Covid-19 in promoting private universities and the difficulties faced by them in implementing digital marketing. It also looked into the strategies applied by digital marketing in creating the awareness among the students and enrolment of with respect to private universities. The research design adopted for the study was phenomenological and qualitative in nature.

The data was collection from 20 marketing representatives from private universities in the areas of Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Tangerang, Bekasi (Jabodetabek) through semi-structured interview. The study results revealed that digital marketing is an important factor which promoted the private universities and enhances the student's enrolment to private universities during the Covid-19 pandemic. The study also found that there is a significant difference between universities utilizing digital marketing as a tool in promoting and enhancing their goodwill and those universities which does not concentrate on it. Moreover, it is understood that the students' enrolment on private universities is increased in the era of Covid-19 based on the application of digital marketing strategies in that period.

Krishnamoorthy, A., Srimathi, H., 2019

In Indian Higher Education due to the tremendous growth of Internet, mobile and social media, they have become indispensable components of the marketing mix. An increasingly competitive environment necessitates private institutions to employ professional corporate teams to evolve strategic planning and pivot new forms of outreach and communication. The main aim of this paper is to analyze effect of digital media marketing on higher education in Indian context. The analysis of the study indicated that the higher education marketing strategies must be individualized to share relevant information using multiple channels based on the unique preferences and attitude of the students. Moreover, the educational institutions must be careful in utilizing and handling both traditional and digital marketing to admit prospective students.

Afzal Basha, 2019

Digital marketing is the channel of electronic communication which is used by the businesses to endorse not only the goods and the services towards the marketplace but also by educational institutions to attract prospective students to their universities and colleges. The study analyzed the effectiveness of digital marketing strategies on students' perception and preferences towards educational institutions. The study is quantitative in nature which has collected data from the students pursuing their study in colleges by using questionnaire method. According to the analysis, the study found that majority of the students strongly agreed that the digital marketing had a significant influence on the preferences of students with respect to education institutions.

Dhote, T., et al., 2015

Digitalization has transformed the way information is delivered and perceived by viewers/information seekers, and much of the material given through digital media may not be true and legitimate, raising the possibility of deceiving the target audience. This study examined how digitalization might deceive people and affect their decision-making with respect to education Industry. It has been revealed by the empirical study analysis that respondents have a high degree of awareness about digital media and information provided in digital media greatly influences their college admission decisions. It is also found that convenience; credibility and relevance of the content are the major factors that play a pivotal role in decision making of the respondents regarding preference towards higher educational institutions. In addition, reference group, word of mouth by friends, colleagues and relatives; existing students' suggestions and industrial experts also impact the people' preferences on higher educational institutions.

2.6 EFFECTIVENESS OF DIGITAL MARKETING ON OTHER SERVICE SECTORS IN THE ERA OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC

a) Banking Sector

i) Foreign Studies

Wangechi, W.C., 2014

This study was undertaken to find out the growth of digital marketing and its effect on customer service with respect to Barclays bank of Kenya, Meru Branch in Kenya by applying consumer behaviour theory and two factor theory of customer service. The case study research design was adopted for the study. The target population for the study consists of 15 employees of Barclays bank Meru branch. The data was collected through interview method and analyzed using content analysis method. The analysis found that Barclays bank used different strategies to achieve their customer service. The analysis of the study revealed that majority of the respondents using display advertising, SEO (Search Engine Optimization) and per pay click strategy as a digital marketing strategy for banks. It is also found from the study that majority of the respondents strongly agree that Website design/development in mobile and internet banking and Email marketing is effectively used to serve their customers. The study concluded that the digital marketing strategies applied by the banking industry in Kenya is at average level and hence, it is

suggested for the Barclays bank to use innovative and effective digital marketing strategies to enhance their customer service.

ii) Indian Studies

Sathya Priya. S., 2022

Traditional platforms have given way to contemporary digital platforms as the paradigm for marketing activities. When a bank releases a mobile application for transactions, other businesses simultaneously create new marketing applications for trade. This study was conducted to bridge the gap and provide simpler methods of living by investigating the aspects of digital marketing. The study was based on secondary data (descriptive data) and the data was collected from various websites, journals and books. The results of the study indicated that digital marketing had a significant impact on development of banking sector and small business which has enhancing the goodwill of the banks and small businesses. According to the study's findings, banks and small businesses must design their digital marketing strategies with the necessary knowledge and abilities.

Surabhi Singh, 2016

There have been recent developments in Indian rural banks towards increasing the number of single window operations to avoid harassment from different banking windows. This paper examined the impact of digital marketing adopted by Indian Banks on customer perception and experience towards it. The study has collected both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected from customers of Indian rural banks by using structured scheduled interview method. According to the study's data, Indian rural banking is not significantly impacted by digital marketing and the awareness of digital media by rural customers is said to be low. This may due to the illiteracy and inefficiency of rural customers who are unable to utilize the digital media effectively. The study also found that majority of the respondents said that they were very much comfortable traditional mode of banking operations.

b) Healthcare Sector

i) Foreign Studies

Pasaribu SB, 2022

Digital marketing has experienced explosive development and achieved significant technological strides worldwide during the COVID-19 pandemic. The digital marketing strategies implemented by the hospitals during this pandemic provides greater benefits and positive response from the clients such as it attracted new patients, strengthened

customer/patient loyalty, increased customer/patient trust, increased brand awareness, expanded business, and promote services to patients' relatives and families. The study is purely based on secondary data source. Based on the reviews, the study found that apart from other digital marketing types content marketing had a positive impact on customer engagement, trust, and loyalty.

Ghazi A. Al-Weshah, 2021

This study investigated the role of digital marketing strategies namely e-mail marketing, search engine optimization and social media networks in enhancing international patients' satisfaction in Jordanian healthcare industry. The study applied quantitative research design and by using convenient sampling method it has collected the primary data from 310 patients in different health service organizations (HSO) through questionnaire method. The results of the study indicated that there exists a significant and positive effect of digital marketing strategies on international patients' satisfaction in Jordanian health service industry. Moreover, each digital marketing strategy had a significant effect on international patients' satisfaction in Jordanian health service industry. It is also found that majority of the patients said that apart from other digital marketing types social media networks are the most important strategy which enhances their satisfaction in HSOs.

Khan RZ, Nawaz H., 2021

Digital marketing has significantly increased profits for online businesses, allowing both small and large business owners to thrive in the advertising industry, notably during the year Covid'19. This study examined the modifications and role played by the digital marketing to transform the people from traditional to modern media during the period of Covid-19 pandemic. The study is strictly based on secondary data. Based on the reviews, the study found that digital marketing technology had a tremendous impact on the usage and preferences of customers with respect to all sectors including health sector during the period of Covid'19 and has gained huge profit throughout the globe.

Budd, J., 2020

With the help of technology, public-health officials around the world are responding to COVID-19, preventing the spread of the virus, identifying cases, tracking contacts, evaluating interventions and communicating with the public. The purpose of this study was to capture digital innovations being implemented worldwide in response to the

COVID-19 virus and to identify their shortcomings, as well as barriers to their implementation, such as legal, ethical and privacy issues, as well as challenges with organizational and workforce management. According to the study, the Covid'19 pandemic makes it evident not only for data sharing, but also for rigorous evaluations, ethical frameworks, and community participation in mobile and digital healthcare to evolve in parallel with it.

c) Hotel Sector

i) Foreign Studies

Kenan Mahmutović, 2021

This study evaluated the impact of digital marketing orientation (DMO) towards enhancement of hotel marketing performance. The study collected data from 164 hotels in Croatia, Serbia, Bosnia, Herzegovina and Montenegro by using structured questionnaire method. The results of the study revealed that there exists a positive and significant impact of digital marketing orientation on the enhancement of hotel marketing performance. According to the study, hotel management should develop a business culture emphasizing the strategic importance of digital marketing before investing in digital marketing tools. Ultimately, the study concluded that hotel management must create a business culture emphasizing the strategic importance of digital marketing before investing money in digital marketing tools. In order to optimize digital marketing activities and improve marketing effectiveness and efficiency, an adequate system of digital marketing analytics must be developed.

Lau, A., 2020

This study examined the innovative technologies used by hotel industry in the era of covid-19. The primary data was collected from directors and general managers of nine well-known hotels in China through interview method. In order to examine the new technologies adopted by hotel industry in China, the study applied DeLone and McLean's Information System Success Model. The results of the study revealed that the hotel sector in China used live-stream promotion and live-stream conference in order to improve the information quality provided by hotel industry. It is also found that 5G technology and Wi-Fi 6 are installed by the hotels to enhance the system quality offered to their customers. Moreover, the hotel sector in China introduced and integrated facial recognition, AI, and Robots to their daily operations to enhance service quality.

ii) Indian Studies

Shaik, J.P., 2018

Digital marketing has become increasingly popular in hotels in recent years and the customers feel satisfied in using Social Media Marketing (SMM) and Search Engine Optimization (SEO), YouTube and websites in search of hotels and restaurants with the use of computers and mobiles. Digital marketing aids the customer in getting the information related to hotels and restaurants regarding its services. This study analyzed the role played by the digital marketing on hotel industry with respect to 5 star hotels in Chennai. It focused to identify the type of digital marketing which satisfies the customer with respect to hotel industry. The study adopted both qualitative and quantitative research design and the data was collected from 40 respondents consuming services in 5 star hotels. The study results indicated that search engines play a primary role in enhancing hotels business by offering information about the services in their own websites along with videos and pictures.

d) Tourism Sector

i) Foreign Studies

Shankar, R., 2021

Due to the epidemic, digital marketing has drastically changed over the past few years. People are discovering methods to stay mobile in India and throughout the world by having all of their requirements met just outside their door. This study examined the significance of Tourism and Hospitality in an Economy and the factors that influence the implementation of Digital Marketing in Hospitality and Tourism sector. It also analyses the problems associated with digital marketing and the contribution made by digital marketing in the growth of hospitality and tourism all around the globe. The study is based on secondary data and the data was collected from reports, articles, journals, websites etc. the results of the study revealed that digital marketing plays a crucial role in enhancing the growth of hospital and tourism sector.

Ketter, E, Avraham, E., 2021

This study examined the digital marketing strategies used by NTBs during tourism crisis. The study was qualitative in nature as it analysis the content provided in digital advertisement, advertisement in television and youtube videos. The study used six strategies divided into two phases namely during lock down phase and post-lockdown phase. The strategies used to find out the digital marketing impact on tourism sector during covid-19 are hope and inspiration, the brotherhood of man, and longing and

nostalgia, Welcome back, Covid-19-safe destinations and Restorative experience. The study's findings revealed that the tourism sector should adopt audience-based digital marketing strategies such as hope, inspiration, togetherness, calmness and fate-sharing in order to create a positive response from the customers.

Muhmmad, I. Nofal, 2020

The COVID-19 pandemic has been proven to be a significant issue for the modern world. The study looked at how the usage of digital marketing has affected people's intentions to travel domestically, moderating the impact of price and mediating the impact of perceived usability (PEOU). Quantitative technique of analysis was adopted for the study. The primary data was collected from 377 respondents who wish to have domestic tourism through questionnaire and by adopting convenience sampling technique. The results of the study revealed that digital marketing had a significant and positive relationship with PEOU and intentions of people to domestic tourism. Moreover; PEOU also had a significant relationship with intentions of people to domestic tourism. Additionally, with the mediating factor of PEOU the study found that there is an association between the digital marketing and intention of people to domestic tourism. The results of this study are helpful to the domestic tourism business in determining travellers' demands during the COVID-19 epidemic.

2.7 SUMMARY AND RESEARCH GAP

Based on the foreign and Indian reviews, it has been understood that majority of the students said that the online education conducted by higher educational institutions is said to be moderately effective. Due to insufficient technology, data connection, knowledge, technical issues they are unable to cope up with online education. In particular, students' pursuing technical oriented courses like maritime education felt it more difficult to learn practical sessions through online. It is also found that the majority of the schools and colleges are greatly affected by the Covid'19 pandemic lockdown and the students and faculty members are faced with greater difficulties in teaching and learning the classes through online. On the other hand, it is found from the reviews that Covid'19 pandemic highly impacted and decreased the admissions of students to schools and colleges especially practical and technical oriented courses like maritime education. The reviews of foreign and Indian studies showed that due to Covid'19 pandemic digital marketing plays a vital role in attracting the students towards schools and colleges.

Based on the true and full-fledged information provided by educational institutions, the students prefer and take decision on colleges to pursue their higher studies especially for those who opt for engineering colleges.

The above studies made by foreign and Indian authors does not cover Chennai region and moreover very few studies are looked into the digital marketing strategies and its impact on students' preferences and decision making process with respect to maritime educational institutions. In addition, it is also understood from the reviews that there are very limited Indian studies based on impact of Covid'19 on challenges faced by maritime educational institutions in Chennai city. Hence, this study has been chosen to assess and explain the influence of digital marketing strategies and its impact on students' preferences and decision making process with respect to maritime education in Chennai city. Furthermore, during this pandemic period of Covid'19, this study has been chosen to provide awareness among the students the scenario, scope and growth of maritime educational institutions and the career opportunities available towards it. It also make known to the students the pros and cons of using digital media to take decision on their academic choices with respect to courses and colleges.

CHAPTER – III

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

According to Woody, research entails defining and redefining problems, developing hypotheses, collecting relevant data, analyzing observations, making deductions, and drawing conclusions. In order to ascertain the results of a specific research topic, research methodology is a systematic study that consists of-

- Research design
- Sampling strategy
- Data collection tools
- Data analysis.

As a result, research methodology generates comprehensive information about the methods used to analyse the research problem in a methodical way and offer potential solutions. In this study, it discovers answers regarding influence of digital marketing on students' decision making to prefer and pursue maritime education in maritime institutions of Chennai through the application of scientific procedures.

3.2 RESEARCH QUESTION

- a) Do students' socio-economic variables have an influence on their opinion towards effectiveness of online maritime education, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai?
- b) Does effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 have a relationship with student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai?
- c) Does students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions have an impact on their decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai?

3.3 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES AND METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Table 3.3.1: Research Objectives and its Methodology

Sl. No.	Objectives	Methodology
1.	To study the socio-economic status of the students perusing maritime education in Chennai.	Collecting respondents' socio-economic information from select six universities and colleges offering maritime courses.
2.	To examine the level of effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19.	Analysing the opinion of the respondents regarding the effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 by applying mean and standard deviation and chi-square test is used to find out the association between respondents' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.
3.	To ascertain the students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions in Chennai.	ANOVA and t-test statistical tool is applied to identify the significant differences between respondents' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions in Chennai.
4.	To study the student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai.	Correspondence analysis is used to evaluate the association between respondents' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai.

5.	To ascertain the relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai.	Bivariate correlation analysis is applied to find out the relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai.
6.	To identify the impact of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai.	Multiple regression analysis and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) is applied to measure the impact of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai.
7.	To suggest various measures to improve the digital marketing in order to enhance the students' preferences towards maritime educational institutions.	Based on the findings, the critical issues regarding digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions are highlighted in order to make possible recommendations for the institutions.

3.4 PILOT STUDY

The questionnaire was pre-tested with 60 students from a chosen group of six maritime educational institutions in order to assess its reliability, validity, and appropriateness of the data collection instruments. They were asked to list out their opinion regarding the effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai. Based on the findings of pilot study, the reliability and validity of the instrumental design was worked out. After modifying the questionnaire based on reliability and validity of data collection instrument, the sample size and study design was framed.

3.5 OPERATIONALIZING THE VARIABLES

It refers to defining and measuring the specific variables applied for the study. The present study is concerned with the impact of digital marketing strategies on students' decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai. The students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education is set as a dependent variable. The three variables that may influence the dependent variable is chosen as independent variables namely socio-economic status of the students, effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 and students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions in Chennai. The same has been represented in the conceptual framework of the study.

3.6 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The conceptual framework defines the variables used in the study objectively. It defines clearly to what extent the independent variables namely socio-economic status of the students, effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 and students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions affect the students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai. The tool used for measuring all these variables are clearly explained in hypothesis and statistical tools used for the study.

Figure: 3.6.1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

3.7 RESEARCH DESIGN

The nature of the study adopted by the researcher is descriptive and analytical research design. Descriptive research has chosen to describe the characteristics of students including their socio-economic variables, their opinion regarding the effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education in Chennai. Analytical research design tries to explain why or how certain variables influence the dependent variable. In this study, the data collected from the respondents are analyzed by using effective statistical tools and critical evaluations are made to find out the impact of digital marketing strategies on students' decision making to pursue maritime education in Chennai.

3.8 SOURCES OF DATA

3.8.1 Primary Data

It refers to information obtained for the first time for the specific purpose of the study. It is collected from the students of select maritime educational institutions by using scheduled interview method with respect to their socio-economic variables, their opinion regarding the effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education. While distributing and collecting data from the students, the purpose of the survey was explained clearly in order to get accurate and fair data from them. To have a better understanding, the questionnaire was framed in English. The researcher also guided them in person by explaining each question in an understandable manner with the purpose of free from bias.

3.8.2 Secondary data

Secondary data are already available and easily accessible information that has been gathered and examined by experts, researchers, authors, etc. In this study, secondary data were collected from the websites, journals, articles and dissertation pertaining to the details of effectiveness of online education by central maritime university, private maritime university and colleges affiliated to state universities, digital marketing strategies applied by educational institutions and students' preferences towards maritime education.

3.9 METHODS OF DATA COLLECTION

Following a thorough review of numerous publications and articles, the questions were developed. It was created with consideration for the study's objectives and the statement of the problem. At each stage of designing the final interview schedule, the panel members' opinions were sought, which included marketing experts, statisticians, and research experts. The questionnaire was equipped with one open ended question and the others are closed ended questions. The feedback of the survey was collected for three months.

3.10 INSTRUMENT DESIGN

In order to test hypotheses and analyze the data statistically, a formal standardized tool is used. The scheduled questionnaire is designed by referring to various articles and finalized after getting ideas, suggestions and approval by research supervisor and panel members.

Table 3.10.1: Formal Standardized Tool

Part	Particulars	Scale	No. of Questions	
I	Socio-Economic Variables	Nominal	1	
		Categorical	4	
		Ordinal	2	
		Ratio	1	
		Open Ended	1	
II	Effectiveness of Online Marine Education During Covid-19	Likert	15	
III	Students' Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies of Maritime Educational Institutions	Content Marketing	Likert	6
		Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	Likert	5
		Social Media Marketing (SMM)	Likert	6
		Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	Likert	6
		Email Marketing	Likert	5
		Instant Message Marketing (IMM)	Likert	5
		Affiliate and Influencer Marketing	Likert	6
IV	Student's Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education	Likert	15	
V	Suggestions	Open Ended	1	
Total			79	

3.11 DATA ANALYSIS PROCEDURE

After collecting primary data using scheduled interview method, the filled in questionnaire was edited and has been recorded, updated simultaneously and organized in the Microsoft excel sheet. The data were then presented in tabular form which was analysed and interpreted by using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) and Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS).

3.12 RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY OF DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

3.12.1 Cronbach's Alpha Reliability

An analysis of the internal consistency of the construct was performed using Cronbach's Alpha Reliability. The Cronbach's Alpha ratio is set at 0.60 when reliability is poor, 0.70 when it is acceptable and 0.80 when it is excellent (George & Mallery, 2003; Kline, 2000).

In this study reliability tests were conducted on the variables namely effectiveness of online marine education during Covid-19, students' opinion on digital marketing strategies of maritime educational institutions and student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education.

From the below table, it is learnt that Cronbach's Alpha reliability for effectiveness of online marine education during Covid-19 is (0.968); students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions namely content marketing (0.862), search engine optimization (0.903), social media marketing (0.966), pay-per-click marketing (0.882), email marketing (0.890), instant message marketing (0.902) and affiliate and influencer marketing (0.923) and student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education is (0.941). All of the variables have a high level of dependability, which implies that when measurements are repeated, the variables yield consistent findings.

Table 3.12.1.a: Reliability Test

Sl. No.	Construct	Cronbach's Alpha
1.	Effectiveness of Online Marine Education During Covid-19(F1)	0.968
2.	Students' Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies of Maritime Educational Institutions	
a.	Content Marketing(F2)	0.862
b.	Search Engine Optimization (SEO)(F3)	0.903
c.	Social Media Marketing (SMM)(F4)	0.966
d.	Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)(F5)	0.882
d.	Email Marketing(F6)	0.890
e.	Instant Message Marketing (IMM)(F7)	0.902
f.	Affiliate and Influencer Marketing(F8)	0.923
3.	Student's Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education (F9)	0.941

[Source: Primary data]

Table 3.12.1.b: Split – Half Reliability Test

Serial Number	Variables	Alpha Part I value	Alpha Part II value	Correlation Between forms	Guttman Split-half
1.	F1	0.950	0.942	0.873	0.931
2.	F2	0.721	0.815	0.733	0.846
3.	F3	0.850	0.794	0.811	0.873
4.	F4	0.936	0.931	0.938	0.968
5.	F5	0.833	0.753	0.771	0.869
6.	F6	0.817	0.751	0.829	0.891
7.	F7	0.873	0.804	0.758	0.821
8.	F8	0.872	0.885	0.797	0.887
9.	F9	0.896	0.898	0.827	0.901

[Source: Primary data]

The above table reveals that the alpha value for all the factors or variables in Part I and Part II of the randomly selected respondents is more than 0.7 and the correlation between Part I and Part II is also highly significant. This means that there is a good internal consistency among the data.

3.12.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

It is a diagram of the model that depicts the structures, indicator variables, and interrelationships. Using CFA's quantitative metrics, constructs and theoretical models are evaluated for reliability and validity.

Table 3.12.2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Construct/ Variables	No. of variables	Chi- Square	P Value	GFI	AGFI	CFI	RMR	RMSEA
F1	15	16.829	0.251	0.952	0.936	0.983	0.015	0.006
F2	6	8.905	0.446	0.958	0.902	1.000	0.012	0.001
F3	5	1.939	0.967	0.994	0.981	1.000	0.016	0.001
F4	6	7.211	0.333	0.922	0.919	0.979	0.013	0.007
F5	6	3.062	0.467	1.000	0.998	1.000	0.002	0.001
F6	5	3.488	0.346	0.990	0.963	1.000	0.011	0.003
F7	5	3.619	0.605	0.979	0.936	1.000	0.013	0.001
F8	6	4.397	0.320	0.966	0.920	0.998	0.016	0.009
F9	15	13.538	0.690	0.966	0.931	1.000	0.015	0.002
Suggested value			>0.05 (Hair et al., 1998)	>0.90 (Hu and Bentler , 1999)	>0.90 (Hair et al., 2006)	>0.90 (Hu and Bentle , 1999)	<0.08 (Hair et al., 2006)	< 0.08 (Hair et al.,1998)

[Source: Primary data]

From the above table, it is found that the calculated P value for all the factors is greater than 0.050 which indicates the model is perfectly fit. Here, GFI (Goodness of Fit Index) value and AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index) value is greater than 0.90 which represents that it is a good fit model. The calculated CFI (Comparative Fit Index) value is close to 1 which means that it is a perfectly fit model and also it is found that RMR (Root Mean Square Residuals) and RMSEA (Root Mean Square Error of Approximation) values are less than 0.10, which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

3.12.3 Validity

The ability of a test to fairly judge what it purports to do is referred to as "validity." To assess the reliability of the data collection tool, the content validity and construct validity tests were used.

i) Content Validity

It describes how well an evaluation or measuring instrument captures the various characteristics of a given construct. In order to examine the impacts of digital marketing on students' preferences and decision making process towards maritime education in Chennai city, specialists specialised in this field were requested to provide opinions on how well each question assesses the construction in question. Their responses are then examined, and judgments are made on how to construct each question. The study identified three independent variables based on the evaluation and judgement of the panel members namely students' socio-economic variable; effectiveness of online marine education during Covid-19 and students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions; and one dependent variable namely students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education.

ii) Construct Validity

It refers to how well the various aspects of a given construction can be evaluated or appraised (Brown, J. D., 1996). CFA quantitatively assesses the construct validity through convergent validity and discriminant validity. The study measures the construct validity in a single dimension consisting of seven factors affecting students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions namely content marketing, search engine optimization, social media marketing, pay-per-click marketing, email marketing, instant message marketing and affiliate and influencer marketing.

a) Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is the degree of agreement between two or more measurements of the same construct (Camines and Zeller, 1979). Inspection of variance collected for each factor is used to determine evidence of convergent validity (Fornell and Larcker, 1981). If the variance-extracted value exceeds 0.50, Fornell and Larcker (1981) claim that convergent validity has been demonstrated. The researcher measures Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Construct Reliability (CR) to test the convergent validity of seven factors in the dimensions:-

- **Average Variance Extracted (AVE):** It serves as a concise indicator of the degree to which various elements that make up a construct have converged. To provide sufficient convergent validity AVE should be 0.5 or above [Hulland (1999)].

- **Construct/Composite Reliability (CR):** This measure is preferred to Cronbach's alpha because it provides a better variance estimate, provides matching indicators, and incorporates item loading inside the nomological network (Hair et al., 2006).

Table 3.12.3.a: Analysis of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Construct/Composite Reliability (CR) for Students' Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies of Marine Educational Institutions

Construct	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Construct/Composite Reliability (CR)
F2	0.666	0.922
F3	0.655	0.904
F4	0.624	0.892
F5	0.671	0.924
F6	0.606	0.900
F7	0.647	0.901
F8	0.619	0.906

[Source: Primary data]

The Average Variance Extracted (AVR) for all seven construct under one dimensions is higher than 0.5 indicating adequate Convergent Validity. The Construct Reliability (CR) for the entire construct is above 80% and also it is greater than AVE which indicates that good internal consistency exists between the variables in the construct.

b) Divergent/Discriminant Validity

It shows that a factor defining the variable is not highly correlated with other factors designed to measure the same variable. The study tests whether seven factors affecting students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions namely content marketing, search engine optimization, social media marketing, pay-per-click marketing, email marketing, instant message marketing and affiliate and influencer marketing are identical and is not similar when compared with other factors. In order to assess this, the study compares Average Variance Extracted (AVE) with Squared Inter Construct Correlation (SIC). The AVE estimates should be greater than the corresponding Squared Inter Construct Correlation estimates (SIC) to provide evidence of discriminant validity.

Table 3.12.3.b: Discriminant Validity for Students' Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies of Marine Educational Institutions

Construct	AVE	Squared Inter construct Correlation (SIC) with Other Variables						
		F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
F2	0.666		0.343	0.527	0.545	0.557	0.513	0.490
F3	0.655	0.343		0.469	0.511	0.396	0.401	0.496
F4	0.624	0.527	0.469		0.517	0.560	0.516	0.498
F5	0.671	0.545	0.511	0.517		0.529	0.551	0.507
F6	0.606	0.557	0.396	0.560	0.529		0.524	0.557
F7	0.647	0.513	0.401	0.516	0.551	0.524		0.518
F8	0.619	0.490	0.496	0.498	0.507	0.557	0.518	

[Source: Primary data]

There is a large difference between the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and the Squared Inter Construct Correlation Estimates (SIC) for the seven factors in the above table and the relationship between the factors is low. This means that the seven factors chosen for defining the variable students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions are more in common/related to the variable and identical/unrelated with each other. Therefore, the seven factors constructing CFA model demonstrate discriminant validity.

Figure 3.12.3: Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) for Students' Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies of Marine Educational Institutions

3.13 STUDY AREA, POPULATION AND SAMPLE SIZE DETERMINATION

3.13.1 Study Area

The study deals with the impact of digital marketing on students' preferences and decision making towards maritime educational institutions during covid-19 pandemic in Chennai. Following the Covid'19 epidemic, universities and colleges offering maritime education have a significant problem in providing simulation-based practical training and courses through online coordination. The necessity for online delivery of simulation-based supplementary courses in Tamilnadu maritime institutions remains unfulfilled (GMDSS, ECDIS, and ROC & ARPA, etc.).As well, virtually administered written and oral competency exams lack guidance for students who are unable to attend a practical session. The efficiency of online teaching methodologies has an impact on the probability that prospective students would seek maritime education during that academic year. Owing this, the study has chosen Chennai area to identify the effectiveness of online education offered by maritime colleges and the students' preferences to pursue maritime education in that academic year.

In the COVID 19 pandemic time, digital marketing had the opportunity to play a crucial role by providing all the information about the products and services through various digital media. Not only does it have an impact on products and services, but it also has a significant impact on educational institutions, as they display their advertisements and online teaching strategies to entice students to enrol in their programmes. Hence, the study has been chosen to identify the impact of digital marketing on choice of students to pursue maritime education in Chennai city. There are six colleges and universities offering maritime education in Chennai. The total strength of the students joined the course in the academic year 2018-2020 and now pursuing their final year in maritime colleges of Chennai is considered as respondents for the study and are given below: -

Table 3.13.1: Study Area

Sl. No.	Name of Institute	Institution & Affiliation	Strength
1.	Indian Maritime University, Chennai	Central University (IMU)	80
2.	AMET University, Chennai.	Private University	200
3.	Vels Academy of Maritime Education And Training, Chennai.	Private University	80
4.	G.K.M. Institute of Marine Sciences and Technology, Chennai.	Affiliated to Anna University	36
5.	International Maritime Academy, Chennai.	Affiliated to Annamalai University	160
6.	Southern Academy of Maritime Studies, Chennai.	Affiliated to Allagappa University	40
Total			596

[Source: Primary data]

3.13.2 Population of the Study

The population refers to the individuals involved in the study who were targeted to receive opinions on a particular topic. Since the study is confined to the students' perusing final year in marine engineering courses in Chennai, the population is found to be known. The total number of students perusing maritime education in Central University, colleges affiliated to State Universities and Private Universities in the academic year 2020 – 2021 is 596.

3.13.3 Sampling Procedure and Sample Size Determination

In every research, there is no scope of including the entire population and only the sample could be selected by applying the appropriate and standard statistical formula. Since the population is known and finite, the study applied the following formula to determine the sample size of the study.

$$\text{Sample size (n)} = N * X / (X + N - 1),$$

Where,

$$X = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * p * (1-p) / MOE^2$$

$Z_{\alpha/2}$ = Critical value of the Normal Distribution at $\alpha/2$

MOE = Margin of Error

p = Sample Proportion

N = Population Size

For this study, the confidence level is 99.9%, critical value is 3.291, 'p' is assumed to be 50% (0.5), MOE is 5% (0.05). By applying the same in the formula we get,

$$X = Z_{\alpha/2}^2 * p*(1-p) / MOE^2$$

$$= \frac{(3.291)^2 * (0.5)(1-0.5)}{(0.05)^2} = \frac{0.9604}{0.0025} = 1083.068$$

Therefore,

$$\text{Sample size (n)} = N * X / (X + N - 1),$$

$$n = \frac{596 * 1083.068}{1083.068 + 596 - 1} = \frac{645508.588}{1678.068}$$

n = 384.67 which is approximately rounded off to 400

Thus, the most optimum sample size needed for the study is 400.

3.14 SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The population for the study consists of 596 students pursuing their final year in maritime colleges and universities in Chennai which is known and definite. Hence, proportionate stratified random sampling technique is adopted to choose 400 final year students from the population. It means division of population into smaller sub-groups called stratum (six colleges and universities). A sample of 400 students is drawn from each stratum using random sampling on 67% proportionate basis.

Table 3.14.1: Distribution of Respondents based on Sampling Technique

Sl. No.	Stratification of Population	Strength	Proportionate Sampling (67% of the Elements)
1.	Indian Maritime University, Chennai	80	54
2.	AMET University, Chennai.	200	134
3.	Vels Academy of Maritime Education and Training, Chennai.	80	54
4.	G.K.M. Institute of Marine Sciences and Technology, Chennai.	36	24
5.	International Maritime Academy, Chennai.	160	107
6.	Southern Academy of Maritime Studies, Chennai.	40	27
Total			400

[Source: Primary data]

3.15 FORMULATION OF HYPOTHESES

For testing purpose, the research question, research objectives and conceptual framework of the study were converted into hypotheses. It mainly tests the significant relationship between independent variables (socio-economic status of the students, effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 and students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions) and dependent variable (students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education).

H₁₁: There is a significant difference between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

H₁₂: There is a significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

H₁₃: There is a significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

H₁₄: There is a significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.

H₁₅: There is a significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' decision to pursue maritime education.

H₁₆: There is a significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education and the digital marketing platform preferred by them to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions.

H₁₇: There exists a perfectly fit model between students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions (IV) and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education (DV).

3.16 STATISTICAL TOOLS USED

The statistical tools used for the analysis are briefly explained below: -

- i) To test the goodness of data Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) is executed using Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS).
- ii) To study the students' socio-economic variables, frequencies are used.
- iii) To study the most significant statement in each factor of students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education, Descriptive Statistics is used.
- iv) To study the significant difference between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions, t-test and One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) is used.
- v) To find out the significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education, Chi-square test is used.
- vi) To study the association between students' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education, Correspondence Analysis is used.
- vii) To ascertain the significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, Bivariate Correlation is used.
- viii) To analyze the significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, Multiple Regression is used.
- ix) To identify the significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education and the digital marketing platform preferred by them to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions, Friedman test is used.
- x) To find out the fitness of data and to estimate the relationships between independent (students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education

during Covid-19 and digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions) and dependent (students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) is executed using Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS).

The statistical tools used in this study are explained below in a detailed manner:

i) Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

Statistically, a confirmatory factor analysis determines whether the measured variables represent the number of constructs accurately. Thus, in order to test the consistency of items in a factor, CFA is used and is executed using Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS). A model fit measurement can be obtained by removing the low factor loading items and comparing to how well it captures the covariance between all the items in the model. In this study, CFA is applied for three variables namely effectiveness of online marine education during Covid-19, students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education.

ii) Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

It is a statistical technique for building and testing statistical models. It includes the aspects such as confirmatory factor analysis, path analysis and regression analysis which aids in proving whether the model is fit for the theory. For this study, SEM will be applied for three variables namely effectiveness of online marine education during Covid-19, students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education.

Table 3.16.1: Model Fit Indices for Assessing Goodness of Fit

Variables	Suggested value
Chi-square value	-
P value	> 0.05 (Hair et al., 1998)
Goodness of Fit (GFI)	> 0.90 (Hu & Bentler, 1999)
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	> 0.90 (Hair et al., 2006)
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	> 0.90 (Hu & Bentler, 1999)
Root Mean Square Residual (RMR)	< 0.08 (Hair et al.,2006)
Root Mean Squared Error of Approximation (RMSEA)	< 0.08 (Hair et al.,1998)

iii) Percentage Analysis

It provides a means of describing any number of variables with statistics and graphs. In this study, it is applied for socio-economic status of the respondents to differentiate the nominal and categorical variables through graphical presentation and tables.

iv) Descriptives statistics

It finds out the significance of factors framed under each variable and to have better comparison within it. For this study, it is applied to compute mean and standard deviation of variables namely effectiveness of online marine education during Covid-19, students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and student's preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education.

v) Independent Sample t-test

It is used for comparing the means of two grouped dichotomous variable with quantitative Likert scaled dependent variable. In this study, t-test is applied to compare the significant difference between gender and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

vi) One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

It is a technique used for comparing the means of two or more grouped variable with quantitative Likert scaled dependent variable. In this study, one-way ANOVA is used for comparing the significant difference between students' nominal scaled socio-economic variables i.e., variable having more than two groups (age, college/university, parents' occupational status, monthly income of family and student's awareness of maritime education) and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

vii) Chi-square test

This goodness-of-fit test compares the observed and expected frequencies in each category to test whether all categories contain the same proportion of values or each category contains a user-specified proportion of values. In this study, it is applied to test the association between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

viii) Correspondence Analysis

It is a descriptive/exploratory technique designed to analyse simple two-way and multi-way tables containing some measure of correspondence between the rows and columns. This is applied to find out the association between students' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education.

ix) Bivariate Correlation:

It computes the pair wise relationship between set of variables and displays the results in a matrix. It is helpful to determine the strength and direction of the link between two scaled variables. For this study, it is applied to test the significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.

x) Multiple Regression

It estimates the co-efficient of the linear equation, involving one or more independent variables that best predict the value of the dependent variable. In this study, it has been applied to test the significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' decision to pursue maritime education.

xi) Friedman test

It is usually utilized in multiple testing efforts to discover variations in treatments. It requires classifying each row (or block) and then taking into account column value of rankings. In this study, Friedman test is used for ranking the students' preferences on factors that insist them to pursue maritime education and the digital marketing platform preferred by them to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions.

3.17 SUMMARY

This chapter discussed the methodology adopted for the study in a systematic way to frame an instrumental design, fix the sample size and sampling technique, collect the data and to assess the reliability and validity of data collected from the respondents. It presents the operationalizing of variables namely independent and dependent variables used to analyze the influence of digital marketing strategies on students' decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai. It portrays the conceptual framework of the study to clearly define the independent variables used to measure the dependent

variables of the study. The nature of the study adopted by the researcher is descriptive and analytical research design. Both primary and secondary data were used to collect data related to the study. The instrumental design consists of 79 questions designed with categorical, ratio, ordinal and Likert scale questions. The reliability and validity of data was tested by applying AMOS software. The instrument designed for the study is fit to process with further steps i.e., the collected data had well-equipped reliability and validity. The sample size of 400 students pursuing final year maritime education in the academic year 2020 - 2021 were determined for the study by using appropriate formula and the sampling technique adopted was stratified proportional random sampling technique. Based on the objectives and theoretical framework, seven hypotheses were framed for the study. The statistical tools like AMOS, bivariate correlation, multiple regression, percentage analysis, descriptive statistics, ANOVA, independent sample t-test, chi-square test, correspondence analysis, Friedman test and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) were used to test the influence of digital marketing strategies on students' decision making process to pursue maritime education; significance and association between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online marine education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in Chennai.

CHAPTER - IV

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

INTRODUCTION

In India, where a diversity of demographics exists, the traditional classroom serves as a great place for students from different socioeconomic backgrounds to come together to learn and develop their skills and talent, which are essential for the success of democracy. In response to Covid-19 lockdown, the government has declared lockdown and closed educational institutions, which have suspended regular classes, postponed exams, and halted learning. This situation requires all educational institutions including colleges and universities offering maritime education to adopt an online method of teaching, adopt several new techniques and digital technologies for teaching, such as recorded video lectures, audio lectures, lectures delivered on digital platforms, etc (Educationasia.in 2020). Such live lectures and webinars are extremely useful for creating a real classroom environment, since they provide slides, content, the use of the whiteboard, attendance marking, discussion among students and teachers, student to student interaction, and assignment and assessment by sending question papers via email or WhatsApp (Pravat Kumar Jena, 2020).

Moreover, parents weren't able to visit the colleges to gain knowledge about colleges, fees, and other facilities, which negatively impacted admissions into higher education institutions particularly maritime educational institutions. The colleges and universities offering maritime education market their colleges and courses by using both traditional and digital marketing methods to reach parents and students. The question is, however, how effective the online education offered by maritime educational institutions is, and how far its digital marketing strategies have influenced students to enroll in maritime educational institutions for their higher education. In this chapter, an analysis has been made to examine the level of effectiveness of online education, students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process towards maritime education in Chennai.

The primary data are collected from 400 students pursuing final year in maritime education in select seven colleges and universities affiliated to central university, private

university and state university. The data are arranged in simple tabular form and were segregated for analysis as per the objectives and hypotheses of the study. They were analyzed with the help of statistical tools namely percentage analysis, independent sample t-test, ANOVA test, chi-square test, decision tree analysis, Bivariate correlation, Multiple regression, Friedman test and Structural Equation Modeling by using SPSS according to the following sequential order.

- 4.1 Socio-economic status of the students (Frequencies).
- 4.2 Factor wise level of students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education (Descriptive statistics).
- 4.3 Significant difference between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions (Independent Sample t-test and One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)).
- 4.4 Significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education (Chi-square test).
- 4.5 Significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education (Correspondence analysis).
- 4.6 Significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education (Bivariate correlation).
- 4.7 Significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' decision to pursue maritime education (Multiple regression).
- 4.8 Significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education and the digital marketing platform preferred by them to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions (Friedman test).
- 4.9 Structural Equation Modeling to estimate the relationship between students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 and digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions (IV) and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education (DV).

4.1 SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF THE STUDENTS (FREQUENCIES)

In order to study the socio-economic status of respondents, percentage analysis is applied. The socio-economic variables considered for the study are respondents' gender, age, parents' occupational status, monthly income of their family and their awareness about maritime educational institutions. The details are shown in the following table 4.1.1.

Table 4.1.1: Socio-Economic Status of the Respondents

Socio-Economic Status	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	228	57
Female	172	43
Total	400	100
Age		
21 years	160	40
22 years	132	33
23 years	68	17
24 years	40	10
Total	400	100
University		
Central University	54	14
Private University	188	47
State University	158	39
Total	400	100
Parents' Occupational Status		
Private Employee	96	24
Government Employee	116	29
Business	92	23
Professionals	56	14
Agriculturist	40	10
Total	400	100

Monthly Income of their Family (In Rupees)		
Up to Rs. 30,000	92	23
Rs. 30,001 – Rs. 50,000	84	21
Rs. 50,001 – Rs. 70,000	104	26
Rs. 70,001 – Rs. 90,000	64	16
Rs. 90,001 and above	56	14
Total	400	100
Awareness of Maritime Educational Institutions		
Friends & Family Members	48	12
Advertisement in Newspapers	80	20
Advertisement in TV Channels	68	17
Digital Marketing	168	42
Experts of Education Fair	36	9
Total	400	100

[Source: Primary data]

Gender

From the above table, it can be understood that 57% of the respondents are male and the remaining 43% of them are female. Hence, it is understood that majority of the respondents are male (57%).

Age of the Respondents

From the above table, it can be observed that 40% of the respondents are in the age of 21 years old, 33% of them are 22 years of age, 17% of them are 23 years of age and 10% of them are 24 years of age. Therefore, it is clear that majority (40%) of the respondents are in the age of 21 years.

University of the Respondents

From the above table, it can be learnt that 47% of the respondents are pursuing their final year maritime course in private university, 39% of them are pursuing in colleges affiliated to state university and 14% of them are pursuing in central university. Hence, it is understood that majority (47%) of the respondents are pursuing their final year maritime course in private university.

Parents' Occupation of the Respondents

From the above table, it can be studied that 29% of the respondents' parents are government employees, 24% of the respondents' parents are working in private companies, 23% of the respondents' parents are doing business, 14% of the respondents' parents are professionals and 10% of the respondents' parents are agriculturist. As a result, it is evident that majority (32%) of the respondents' parents are government employees.

Monthly Income of the Respondents' Family

From the above table, it can be learnt that 26% of the respondents' family is earning monthly income between Rs.50,001 and Rs.70,000, 23% of the respondents' family is earning monthly income up to Rs. 30000, 21% of the respondents' family is earning monthly income between Rs.30,001 and Rs.50,000, 16% of the respondents' family is earning monthly income between Rs.70,001 and Rs.90,000 and 14% of the respondents' family is earning monthly income of Rs.90,001 and above. Consequently, it is understandable that majority (26%) of the respondents' family is earning monthly income between Rs.50,001 and Rs.70,000.

Awareness of Maritime Educational Institutions by the Respondents

From the above table, it can be inferred that 42% of the respondents are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing, 20% of them are aware through advertisement in newspapers, 17% of them are aware through advertisement in television channels, 12% of them are aware through their friends and family members and 9% of them are aware based on the experts' advice given in educational fair. As a result, it is clear that majority (42%) of the respondents are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing.

4.2 FACTOR WISE LEVEL OF RESPONDENTS' OPINION ON EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE MARITIME EDUCATION DURING COVID-19, DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES APPLIED BY MARITIME EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND THEIR PREFERENCES AND DECISION MAKING PROCESS TO PURSUE MARITIME EDUCATION (DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS)

In order to study the factor wise level of opinion of respondents' on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education, descriptive analysis is used. From the value of mean and standard deviation, the differences in their level of effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education can be measured and interpreted. It also aids in identifying the most significant statement in each variable.

4.2.1 Respondents' Opinion towards Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education during Covid-19

The respondents' level of opinion towards the effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 is acknowledged through descriptive analysis. Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the highest factor which supports the effectiveness of maritime education is identified.

Table 4.2.1: Respondents' Opinion towards Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education during Covid-19 (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	Use of Power point presentation.	3.74	1.190	1.416
2.	Clarity in explaining the subject.	3.53	1.246	1.553
3.	Good communication skills of faculty members.	3.75	1.262	1.591
4.	Explanation of content through videos and practical examples.	3.71	1.277	1.630
5.	Provision of understandable study materials.	3.72	1.291	1.666
6.	Effective doubt clearing classes.	3.71	1.269	1.610

7.	Using excel and other innovative technology for mathematics.	3.66	1.322	1.749
8.	Provision of MCQ through Google forms and other applications.	3.66	1.315	1.729
9.	Provision of user friendly virtual classroom software.	3.52	1.238	1.533
10.	Continuous assessment based on online tests, assignments etc.	3.50	1.347	1.815
11.	Timely completion of lessons.	3.68	1.312	1.722
12.	Continuous and uninterrupted sessions.	3.56	1.316	1.731
13.	Transparency and precise maintenance of attendance.	3.53	1.262	1.593
14.	Strict monitoring of students during class hours and tests.	3.43	1.261	1.589

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are above 3.00 but below 4.00; which means all the respondents' opinion towards effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 is considered as good. As a result, it is apparently known that the online education taken by maritime educational institutions are moderately effective and the students have learned and developed their knowledge to some extent and they also had interactions with the faculty members as like educating through offline.

Based on the mean value, the statement "Good communication skills of faculty members (3.75)" is considered to be the significant factor by the students that supported the effectiveness of online maritime education, followed by "Use of Power point presentation (3.74)", "Provision of understandable study materials (3.72)", "Explanation of content through videos and practical examples and Effective doubt clearing classes (3.71)", "Timely completion of lessons (3.68)", "Using excel and other innovative technology for mathematics and Provision of MCQ through Google forms and other applications (3.66)", "Continuous and uninterrupted sessions (3.56)", "Clarity in explaining the subject and Transparency and precise maintenance of attendance (3.53)", "Provision of user friendly virtual classroom software (3.52)", "Continuous assessment based on online tests, assignments etc (3.50)", "Updation of progress report to parents (3.49)" and "Strict monitoring of students during class hours and tests (3.43). The online education offered by the educational institutions during Covid-19 is said to be moderately effective has been proven by the studies namely Baber, H., 2022; Mushtaha, E., et al., 2022;

Akram, F., et al., 2021; Asgari, S., et al., 2021; Bartusevičienė, I., et al., 2021; Darius, P.S.H., et al., 2021; Muthuprasad, T., et al., 2021; Selvaraj, A., et al., 2021 and many more.

4.2.2 Respondents’ Opinion towards Content Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions

The respondents’ level of opinion towards the content marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is predictable through descriptive analysis. Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the high level opinion of respondents towards content marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is identified.

Table 4.2.2: Respondents’ Opinion towards Content Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	It provides clear and precise information about the college/university.	3.85	1.308	1.712
2.	The language used for content is easily understandable.	3.96	1.226	1.502
3.	The presentation of content attracts and creates curiosity to know about the college/university.	3.65	1.262	1.591
4.	The content provided enhances the value and goodwill of the college/university.	3.66	1.389	1.929
5.	It covers the entire and needed information about the college in a simplified manner.	3.84	1.303	1.699
6.	The channel used for content marketing is easily accessible by a wide range of people.	3.80	1.218	1.484

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are between 3.50 and 4.00; which means all the respondents’ opinion towards the content marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is considered as excellent. As a result, it is apparently known that the maritime educational institutions provide enhanced information and details regarding courses, fees structure etc through content marketing.

Based on the mean value, the statement “The language used for content is easily understandable (3.96)” is considered to be the significant factor that attracted the students to view the content marketing provided by maritime educational institutions, followed by “It provides clear and precise information about the college (3.85)”, “It covers the entire and needed information about the college in a simplified manner

(3.84)”, “The channel used for content marketing is easily accessible by a wide range of people (3.80)”, “The content provided enhances the value and goodwill of the college (3.66)” and “The presentation of content attracts and creates curiosity to know about the college (3.65)”. Content marketing serves as a significant digital marketing for the educational institutions that insist the students to prefer colleges and universities and this has been proven by the following research studies namely Rajkumar, S.G., et al., 2021; Julie M. Pharr, 2019; Jacqueline Marie Getty, 2015.

4.2.3 Respondents’ Opinion towards Search Engine Optimization (SEO) of Maritime Educational Institutions

The respondents’ level of opinion towards the Search Engine Optimization (SEO) applied by maritime educational institutions is identified through descriptive analysis. Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the high level opinion of respondents towards Search Engine Optimization (SEO) applied by maritime educational institutions is identified.

Table 4.2.3: Respondents’ Opinion towards Search Engine Optimization (SEO) of Maritime Educational Institutions (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	It grabs the attention of people.	3.56	1.183	1.414
2.	It generates qualified traffic to the college/university website.	3.53	1.256	1.577
3.	It increases the awareness about the college/university.	3.52	1.245	1.549
4.	It enhances the choice and preferences towards college/university.	3.59	1.194	1.425
5.	It creates high value among the people about the college/university.	3.57	1.233	1.519

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are above 3.00 but below 3.60; which means all the respondents’ have moderate opinion towards the search engine optimization of maritime educational institutions. It is therefore understood that maritime educational institutions’ search engine optimization does not support the students to search for colleges and universities offering maritime courses.

Based on the mean value, the statement “It enhances the choice and preferences towards college (3.59)” is considered to be the significant statement that insist the students to use search engine optimization to view the colleges or universities offering maritime education, followed by “It creates high value among the people about the college (3.57)”, “It grabs the attention of people (3.56)”, “It generates qualified traffic to the college website (3.53)” and “It increases the awareness about the college (3.52)”. It is also evident from the following previous studies that search engine optimization is the significant factor which influence the students to prefer educational institutions namely Bin, W., et al., 2018; Bhandari, R. S., & Bansal, S., 2019; Bhandari, R. S., & Bansal, A., 2018.

4.2.4 Respondents’ Opinion towards Social Media Marketing (SMM) of Maritime Educational Institutions

The respondents’ level of opinion towards the Social Media Marketing (SMM) of maritime educational institutions is known through descriptive analysis. Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the high level opinion of students with respect to social media marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is identified.

Table 4.2.4: Respondents’ Opinion towards Social Media Marketing (SMM) of Maritime Educational Institutions (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	The platform chosen for SMM is highly effective.	4.08	0.830	1.414
2.	The design and graphics used for PPC is highly good-looking.	4.09	0.799	1.577
3.	The blogs and messages posted in SM about the college are eye-catching.	4.02	0.872	1.549
4.	It covers all levels of the audience to read and view the information about the college/university.	4.11	0.619	1.425
5.	It gives relevant and complete information about the college/university.	4.10	0.778	0.605
6.	The promotional messages are fair enough to create trust among the audience towards the college/university.	4.04	0.857	0.734

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are above 4.00; which means all the respondents' have excellent opinion on social media marketing applied by maritime educational institutions. Hence, it is clearly learnt that the maritime educational institutions offer clarity and eye catching information about their colleges or universities by keeping in mind of all range of students through social media marketing.

Based on the mean value, the statement "It covers all levels of the audience to read and view the information about the college/university (4.11)" is considered to be the significant statement that forces the students to view the social media marketing presented by maritime educational institutions, followed by "It gives relevant and complete information about the college/university (4.10)", "The design and graphics used for PPC is highly good-looking (4.09)", "The platform chosen for SMM is highly effective (4.08)", "The promotional messages are fair enough to create trust among the audience towards the college/university (4.04)" and "The blogs and messages posted in SM about the college are eye-catching (4.02)". Thus, social media marketing has a positive impact on students' preferences and decision making to pursue various courses in colleges or university and the same has been proven by the following research studies namely C.H., et al., 2022; Dr.Ghosal, I., et al., 2020;Rishab Singh, 2019; Chen E, DiVall M., 2018.

4.2.5 Respondents' Opinion towards Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) of Maritime Educational Institutions

The respondents' level of opinion towards Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) applied by maritime educational institutions is acknowledged through descriptive analysis. Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the high level opinion of students regarding Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) is identified.

Table 4.2.5: Respondents' Opinion towards Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) of Maritime Educational Institutions (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	The advertisement format used for PPC is appreciable.	2.98	1.150	1.323
2.	The advertisement network applied for PPC is accessible by a wide range of audience.	2.98	1.115	1.243
3.	The college made the finest decision possible while selecting the PCC platform.	2.73	.990	0.980

4.	It insists the audience to click and get into the advertisement.	3.12	1.053	1.108
5.	The keywords used for advertisement create curiosity among the audience to know more about the college/university.	3.25	1.073	1.150
6.	The landing page content is a natural extension of the advertisement copy shown in the network page.	3.32	1.158	1.341

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are between 2.75 and 3.35; which means all the respondents' have reasonable opinion towards the Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) offered by maritime educational institutions. Hence, it is apparent that the maritime educational institutions' Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) is not that much effective and is not supported them to enhance their viewers.

Based on the mean value, the statement "The landing page content is a natural extension of the advertisement copy shown in the network page (3.32)" is considered to be the significant statement that make the Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) as an effective one, followed by "The keywords used for advertisement create curiosity among the audience to know more about the college/university (3.25)", "It insists the audience to click and get into the advertisement (3.12)", "The advertisement format used for PPC is appreciable and The advertisement network applied for PPC is accessible by a wide range of audience (2.98)" and "The college made the finest decision possible while selecting the PCC platform (2.73)". Consequently, PPC serves as a moderately effective factor for educational institutions to attract and admit students to the college or university and the same has been evident by the following research studies namely Sam Yadegar, 2021; Messah, O.B., & Mutali. J. Namulia Immaculate, 2020.

4.2.6 Respondents' Opinion towards E-mail Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions

The respondents' level of opinion towards e-mail marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is identified through descriptive analysis. Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the high level opinion of students towards e-mail marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is identified.

Table 4.2.6: Respondents' Opinion towards E-mail Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	The content about the college given in email is provided in a simple language.	3.45	1.054	1.110
2.	The compelling subject lines of email marketing forces the audience to open the message.	3.33	1.002	1.004
3.	The regular e-mail postage leaves an impression on the audience about the college/university.	3.16	.957	.917
4.	It gives updated information about the college and its available seats for courses.	3.48	1.016	1.032
5.	The email design is simple, narrow and impactful.	3.20	1.078	1.163

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are above 3.00 but below 3.50; which means all the respondents' have good but not tremendous opinion towards the e-mail marketing applied by maritime educational institutions. It is therefore inferred that the e-mail marketing supports in a moderate way for maritime colleges so as to make the students to enroll in maritime courses.

Based on the mean value, the statement "It gives updated information about the college and its available seats for courses (3.48)" is considered to be the significant statement that forces the students to admit in maritime colleges or university, followed by "The content about the college given in email is provided in a simple language (3.45)", "The compelling subject lines of email marketing forces the audience to open the message (3.33)", "The email design is simple, narrow and impactful (3.20)" and "The regular e-mail postage leaves an impression on the audience about the college/university (3.16)". Thus, e-mail marketing serves as a key factor for the colleges or university to promote their courses and it has been proven by the previous studies namely Anton Savchenko, 2022; Elle Gellrich, 2022; Andriani KUSUMAWATI, 2019.

4.2.7 Respondents' Opinion towards Instant Message Marketing (IMM) of Maritime Educational Institutions

The respondents' level of opinion towards Instant Message Marketing (IMM) applied by maritime educational institutions is known through descriptive analysis. Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the high level opinion of students

towards Instant Message Marketing (IMM) applied by maritime educational institutions is identified.

Table 4.2.7: Respondents’ Opinion towards Instant Message Marketing (IMM) of Maritime Educational Institutions (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	Reliable content is posted in IMM.	2.93	1.135	1.288
2.	The design of the message targets the right audience.	2.95	1.118	1.251
3.	The content used is highly appealing.	2.92	1.305	1.704
4.	It contains all of the necessary information in a single paragraph.	2.90	1.179	1.391
5.	The time slot selected for message posting boosts college preferences.	2.80	1.313	1.724

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are below 3.00; which means all the respondents’ have below the average opinion towards Instant Message Marketing (IMM) applied by maritime educational institutions. Thus, it is obvious that the maritime educational institutions is not providing in a better way the information about their maritime courses, fees structure and other facilities through Instant Message Marketing (IMM).

Based on the mean value, the statement “The design of the message targets the right audience(2.95)” is considered to be the significant statement which insist the students to read messages send by maritime colleges and university, followed by “Reliable content is posted in IMM (2.93)”, “The content used is highly appealing (2.92)”, “It contains all of the necessary information in a single paragraph (2.90)” and “The time slot selected for message posting boosts college preferences (2.80)”. Accordingly, Instant Message Marketing (IMM) support the educational institutions in a normal way that insist the students to think about their preferences to educational institutions and the same has been proven by the following research studies namely Le Roux DB & Parry DA., 2022; Tang, Y., Hew, K.F., 2022; Pokhrel, S.,2018.

4.2.8 Respondents’ Opinion towards Affiliate and Influencer Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions

The respondents’ level of opinion towards Affiliate and Influencer Marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is identified through descriptive analysis.

Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the high level opinion of students' towards Affiliate and Influencer Marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is identified.

Table 4.2.8: Respondents' Opinion towards Affiliate and Influencer Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	It drives traffic to the college link.	2.92	0.957	0.916
2.	It gives comprehensible information about the college.	2.61	0.990	0.980
3.	It enhances the quality of college by offering valid content in a precise manner.	2.70	0.923	0.852
4.	The presentation and communication of information about the college reaches all levels of audience.	2.68	0.871	0.759
5.	Outstanding performance by an influencer who promotes the college.	2.82	0.995	0.990
6.	Targeted audience is covered by the platform and niche selected for affiliate marketing.	2.65	0.985	0.970

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are below 3.00; which means all the respondents' have dreadful opinion Affiliate and Influencer Marketing applied by maritime educational institutions. It is therefore inferred that the maritime educational institutions does not concentrate on the Affiliate and Influencer Marketing in promoting their colleges or university.

Based on the mean value, the statement "It drives traffic to the college link (2.92)" is considered to be the significant statement that attracts the students to watch the advertisement made through affiliated or influencer marketing by maritime educational institutions, followed by "Outstanding performance by an influencer who promotes the college (3.82)", "It enhances the quality of college by offering valid content in a precise manner (3.70)", "The presentation and communication of information about the college reaches all levels of audience (3.68)", "Targeted audience is covered by the platform and niche selected for affiliate marketing(3.65)" and "It gives comprehensible information about the college (3.61)". Therefore, affiliated or influencer marketing used by

educational institutions is fairly effective and the same has been proven by the following research studies namely Neha Kulwal, 2021; Nick Malekos, 2019.

4.2.9 Respondents' Opinion towards Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education

The respondents' level of opinion towards preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education is identified through descriptive analysis. Based on the value of mean and standard deviation, the high level of preferences and decision making process of students to pursue maritime education is identified.

Table 4.2.9: Respondents' Opinion towards Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education (Descriptives)

Sl. No.	Statements	Mean	SD	Coefficient of Variance
1.	I have chosen this course to travel all over the world by sea.	3.68	1.058	1.120
2.	I pursue this course to learn about the world's unique facts and qualities.	3.68	1.058	1.120
3.	I am curious to know and expand my knowledge in maritime education.	3.63	1.066	1.136
4.	My decision to pursue this course is due to wider job opportunities all over the globe.	3.63	1.075	1.156
5.	I joined this course to get a dignified job.	3.55	1.118	1.251
6.	My choice towards the course is to earn a high salary.	3.66	1.013	1.027
7.	I like to do challenging tasks by working offshore.	3.74	1.102	1.215
8.	My choice of career is to be adventurous and interesting.	3.62	1.086	1.179
9.	To gain practical and technical knowledge rather than studying theoretically.	3.48	1.163	1.353
10.	My ambition to pursue this course is to become a captain of the ship.	3.64	1.092	1.193
11.	The fee structure to pursue this course is reasonable and affordable.	3.69	1.047	1.097

12	Effective and attractive infrastructure and facilities offered by college insist me to prefer maritime education.	3.64	1.083	1.173
13	The explanation given by faculty members creates confidence and trust to prefer this course.	3.69	1.018	1.036
14	The placement details and assurance given by college forces me to make a decision regarding this course.	3.58	1.098	1.207
15	I like to do a job by interacting with nature.	3.69	0.936	0.876

[Source: Primary Data]

It is known from the above table that the mean value for all the statements are above 3.00; which means all the respondents' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education is said to be good. It is therefore clearly learnt that the students have fair preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Based on the mean value, the statement "I like to do challenging tasks by working offshore (3.74)" is considered to be the significant statement that forces the students to prefer and decide upon maritime education, followed by "The fee structure to pursue this course is reasonable and affordable (3.69)", "The explanation given by faculty members creates confidence and trust to prefer this course (3.69)", "I like to do a job by interacting with nature (3.69)", "I have chosen this course to travel all over the world by sea (3.68)", "I pursue this course to learn about the world's unique facts and qualities (3.68)", "My choice towards the course is to earn a high salary (3.66)", "My ambition to pursue this course is to become a captain of the ship (3.64)", "Effective and attractive infrastructure and facilities offered by college insist me to prefer maritime education (3.64)", "I am curious to know and expand my knowledge in maritime education (3.63)", "My decision to pursue this course is due to wider job opportunities all over the globe (3.63)", "My choice of career is to be adventurous and interesting (3.62)", "The placement details and assurance given by college forces me to make a decision regarding this course (3.58)" and "I joined this course to get a dignified job (3.55)".

4.3 SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE BETWEEN STUDENTS' SOCIO-ECONOMIC VARIABLES AND THEIR OPINION ON DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES APPLIED BY MARITIME EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS (INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST AND ANOVA)

In order to study the significant differences between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions, Independent Sample T-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test is applied.

HYPOTHESIS (H₁₁): There is a significant difference between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

4.3.1 Significant Difference between Respondents' Gender and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between respondents' gender and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between respondents' gender and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Table 4.3.1: Respondents' Gender and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions (Independent Sample –T-test)

Factors	Gender		t value	P value
	Male	Female		
Content Marketing	24.14 (2.52)	21.72 (4.12)	7.258	0.001**
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	19.4 (2.96)	17.42 (3.32)	6.266	0.001**
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	25.58 (2.97)	21.09 (7.40)	8.328	0.001**
Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	19.65 (2.56)	17.42 (3.21)	7.726	0.001**
Email Marketing	18.00 (1.73)	15.75 (3.27)	8.857	0.001**

Instant Message Marketing	16.44 (2.71)	13.47 (4.55)	8.099	0.001**
Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing	17.88 (2.56)	15.25 (3.43)	8.811	0.001**

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ** Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values within the bracket denote standard deviation.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents' gender and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. The mean level of male is better than female with respect to seven digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions i.e., for male it is superior [Content Marketing (24.14), Search Engine Optimization (SEO) (19.4), Social Media Marketing (SMM) (25.58), Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) (19.65), Email Marketing (18.00), Instant Message Marketing (16.44) and Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing (17.88)] when compared to female [Content Marketing (21.72), Search Engine Optimization (SEO) (17.42), Social Media Marketing (SMM) (21.09), Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) (17.42), Email Marketing (15.75), Instant Message Marketing (13.47) and Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing (15.25)]. It is evident from the following articles that there is a direct relationship between respondents' gender and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by educational institutions and companies namely Manju, P., & Dr. Kavitha, M., 2021; Tama-Rutigliano, K., 2018; Perju-Mitrana, A., & Budaciaa, A.E., 2015; Li et al., 2015; Bae, S., Lee, T., 2011; Kang, 2011; Mehta et al., 2010; Phang 2010.

4.3.2 Significant Difference between Respondents' Age and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between respondents' age and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between respondents' age and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Table 4.3.2: Respondents' Age and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions (ANOVA Test)

Factors	Age (in years)				F value	P Value
	21 years	22 years	23 years	24 years		
Content Marketing	22.58 ^a (4.29)	23.42 ^a (3.38)	22.06 ^a (2.69)	22.50 ^a (3.55)	12.439	0.064
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	18.60 ^a (3.08)	18.64 ^a (2.84)	17.47 ^a (2.98)	18.23 ^a (3.80)	12.014	0.111
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	24.58 ^b (3.49)	25.24 ^b (3.10)	22.41 ^a (3.54)	22.50 ^a (3.45)	15.280	0.000 ^{**}
Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	18.88 ^b (2.98)	19.30 ^b (2.50)	17.12 ^a (3.04)	17.80 ^a (2.02)	15.987	0.001 ^{**}
Email Marketing	17.06 ^b (2.25)	17.76 ^b (1.77)	15.75 ^a (3.77)	16.60 ^a (1.77)	12.689	0.000 ^{**}
Instant Message Marketing	15.70 ^a (3.01)	16.33 ^a (2.55)	13.40 ^a (5.33)	14.29 ^a (2.63)	14.355	0.088
Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing	16.88 ^b (2.76)	17.09 ^b (2.56)	15.63 ^a (4.12)	16.20 ^a (2.39)	15.422	0.001 ^{**}

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ^{**} Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values within the bracket denote standard deviation.
3. Different alphabet between age of respondents denote significant at 5 per cent level using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT).
4. For respondents' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions under seven factors 'a' signifies below 'neutrally agreed' and 'b' signifies above 'neutrally agreed'.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that except content marketing, search engine marketing and instant message marketing there is a significant difference between respondents' age and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, the respondents in all the age group have neutral opinion on content marketing [21 years (22.58^a), 22 years (23.42^a), 23 years (22.06^a) and 24 years (22.50^a)], search engine optimization [21 years (18.60^a), 22 years (18.64^a), 23 years (17.47^a) and 24 years (18.23^a)] and instant message marketing [21 years (15.70^a), 22 years (16.33^a), 23 years (13.40^a) and 24 years (14.29^a)] applied by maritime educational institutions. The respondents in the age of 21 years and 22 years are having higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions than the respondents in the age of 23 years [social media marketing (22.41^a), pay-per-click marketing (17.12^a), email marketing (15.75^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (15.63^a)] and 24 years [social media marketing (22.50^a), pay-per-click marketing (17.80^a), email marketing (16.60^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (16.20^a)].

Hence, it is concluded that except content marketing, search engine marketing and instant message marketing there is a direct relationship between respondents' age and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions i.e., the respondents in the age group of 21 years and 22 years have higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and the respondents in the age group of 24 years have lower level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. The same has been proven from the following studies that there is a significant difference between respondents' age and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by educational institutions and companies namely Manju, P., & Dr. Kavitha, M., 2021; Li et al., 2015; Kang, 2011; Mehta et al., 2010; Phang 2010.

4.3.3 Significant Difference between Respondents' University and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between respondents' university and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between respondents' university and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Table 4.3.3: Respondents' University and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions (ANOVA test)

Factors	University			F value	P Value
	CU	PU	SU		
Content Marketing	13.15 ^a (1.61)	24.49 ^c (2.84)	22.28 ^b (3.16)	9.311	0.001 ^{**}
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	14.24 ^a (2.35)	19.57 ^c (2.82)	18.09 ^b (2.98)	11.962	0.001 ^{**}
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	9.52 ^a (1.71)	26.29 ^c (2.69)	23.75 ^b (3.96)	10.723	0.001 ^{**}
Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	13.44 ^a (1.72)	19.82 ^c (2.48)	18.35 ^b (2.44)	9.723	0.001 ^{**}
Email Marketing	11.28 ^a (2.12)	17.93 ^c (1.73)	17.14 ^b (2.16)	8.883	0.001 ^{**}
Instant Message Marketing	7.19 ^a (2.17)	17.21 ^c (2.72)	15.59 ^b (3.21)	9.948	0.001 ^{**}
Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing	10.83 ^a (1.77)	18.02 ^c (2.19)	16.33 ^b (2.81)	8.408	0.001 ^{**}

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ^{**} Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values within the bracket denote standard deviation.
3. CU- Central University, PU–Private University, SU – State University.
4. Different alphabet between university of respondents denote significant at 5 per cent level using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT).
5. For respondents' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions under seven factors 'a' signifies below 'neutrally agreed', 'b' signifies 'neutrally agreed', 'c' signifies above 'neutrally agreed'.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents' university and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, the respondents pursuing their maritime education in private university have higher level of opinion on digital marketing

strategies applied by maritime educational institutions [content marketing (24.49^c), search engine optimization (19.57^c), social media marketing (26.29^c), pay-per-click marketing (19.82^c), email marketing (17.93^c), instant message marketing (17.21^c) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (18.02^c)] than the respondents pursuing in central university [content marketing (13.15^a), search engine optimization (14.24^a), social media marketing (9.52^a), pay-per-click marketing (13.44^a), email marketing (11.28^a), instant message marketing (7.19^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (10.83^a)].

In addition, the respondents pursuing their maritime education in private university have fair level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions namely content marketing (22.28^b), search engine optimization (18.09^b), social media marketing (23.75^b), pay-per-click marketing (18.35^b), email marketing (17.14^b), instant message marketing (15.59^b) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (16.33^b).

Hence, it is concluded that there is a direct relationship between respondents' university and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions i.e., the respondents pursuing their maritime education in private university have higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions; respondents pursuing their maritime education in private university have medium level of opinion on ; and the respondents pursuing their maritime education in central university have lower level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. It is also proven by the following previous studies that there is a direct relationship between respondents' university and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by educational institutions and companies namely Manju, P., & Dr. Kavitha, M., 2021; Li et al., 2015; Kang, 2011; Mehta et al., 2010; Phang 2010.

4.3.4 Significant Difference between Respondent Parents' Occupational Status and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Table 4.3.4: Respondent Parents’ Occupational Status and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions (ANOVA Test)

Factors	University					F value	P Value
	PE	GE	B	P	A		
Content Marketing	23.40 ^b (3.48)	20.38 ^a (3.79)	24.70 ^c (3.41)	24.57 ^c (2.21)	22.40 ^b (2.97)	27.851	0.001 ^{**}
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	17.67 ^b (2.51)	15.00 ^a (3.54)	20.09 ^c (2.50)	19.86 ^c (3.23)	17.33 ^b (3.45)	21.597	0.001 ^{**}
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	24.29 ^b (3.29)	16.83 ^a (7.68)	27.48 ^c (1.70)	25.07 ^c (2.89)	24.86 ^b (3.84)	33.654	0.001 ^{**}
Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	17.79 ^b (2.72)	15.93 ^a (3.15)	20.57 ^c (2.31)	19.64 ^c (2.46)	17.14 ^b (1.66)	31.855	0.001 ^{**}
Email Marketing	16.33 ^b (2.40)	14.59 ^a (3.72)	18.22 ^c (1.87)	18.14 ^c (1.26)	16.45 ^b (1.52)	29.962	0.001 ^{**}
Instant Message Marketing	15.20 ^b (3.16)	11.90 ^a (5.10)	17.30 ^c (3.19)	17.29 ^c (2.17)	15.48 ^b (2.55)	32.124	0.001 ^{**}
Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing	17.33 ^b (2.95)	14.10 ^a (3.92)	18.96 ^c (1.66)	18.71 ^c (2.79)	16.69 ^b (2.61)	25.775	0.001 ^{**}

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ^{**} Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values within the bracket denote standard deviation.
3. PE- Private Employee, GE–Government Employee, B – Business, P – Professionals and A - Agriculturist.
4. Different alphabet between occupational status of respondent patents denote significant at 5 per cent level using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT).
5. For respondents’ opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions under seven factors ‘a’ signifies below ‘neutrally agreed’, ‘b’ signifies ‘neutrally agreed’ and ‘c’ signifies above ‘neutrally agreed’.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of business [content marketing (24.70^c), search engine optimization (20.09^c), social media marketing (27.48^c), pay-per-click marketing (20.57^c), email marketing (18.22^c), instant message marketing (17.30^c) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (18.96^c)] and professionals have higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions [content marketing (24.57^c), search engine optimization (19.86^c), social media marketing (25.07^c), pay-per-click marketing (19.64^c), email marketing (18.14^c), instant message marketing (17.29^c) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (18.71^c)] than the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of government employee [content marketing (20.38^a), search engine optimization (15.00^a), social media marketing (16.83^a), pay-per-click marketing (15.93^a), email marketing (14.59^a), instant message marketing (11.90^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (14.10^a)].

Moreover, the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of private employee [content marketing (23.40^b), search engine optimization (17.67^b), social media marketing (24.29^b), pay-per-click marketing (17.79^b), email marketing (16.33^b), instant message marketing (15.20^b) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (17.33^b)] and agriculturist [content marketing (22.40^b), search engine optimization (17.33^b), social media marketing (24.86^b), pay-per-click marketing (17.14^b), email marketing (16.45^b), instant message marketing (15.48^b) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (16.69^b)] have moderate level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Hence, it is noticeable that there is a direct relationship between respondent's respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions i.e., the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of business and professionals have their opinion towards the digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions at higher level; the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of private employee and agriculturist are having moderate level of opinion and the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of government employee have lower level of opinion towards the digital marketing strategies applied by

maritime educational institutions. It is proven from the following previous studies that there is a direct relationship between respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by educational institutions and companies namely Pappas et al., 2017.

4.3.5 Significant Difference Between Respondent Parents' Monthly Income and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Table 4.3.5: Respondent Parents' Monthly Income and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions (ANOVA Test)

Factors	Parents' Monthly Income (in Rupees)					F value	P Value
	Up to Rs.30,000	Rs.30,001 - Rs.50,000	Rs.50,001 - Rs.70,000	Rs.70,001 - Rs.90,000	Rs.90,001 and above		
Content Marketing	22.57 ^a (3.15)	23.57 ^a (3.51)	22.69 ^a (4.03)	22.69 ^a (4.26)	22.07 ^a (3.53)	41.570	0.181
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	18.96 ^a (2.27)	17.62 ^a (3.64)	17.65 ^a (3.93)	18.44 ^a (2.98)	19.07 ^a (3.04)	43.649	0.116
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	24.30 ^a (5.74)	23.33 ^a (4.37)	20.96 ^a (7.33)	22.50 ^a (6.25)	24.86 ^a (6.77)	45.279	0.099
Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	18.74 ^a (3.00)	18.81 ^a (2.70)	17.88 ^a (3.28)	18.63 ^a (3.26)	17.79 ^a (3.50)	41.950	0.204
Email Marketing	16.52 ^a (3.23)	17.48 ^a (2.42)	16.46 ^a (3.18)	16.06 ^a (2.75)	17.14 ^a (2.64)	42.850	0.134
Instant Message Marketing	15.09 ^a (4.01)	15.33 ^a (3.69)	14.62 ^a (4.22)	13.44 ^a (4.35)	15.07 ^a (4.44)	42.313	0.156
Affiliate Marketing	16.48 ^a (3.52)	16.52 ^a (2.53)	16.85 ^a (3.88)	15.88 ^a (3.34)	15.71 ^a (2.99)	41.488	0.122

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. The values within the bracket denote standard deviation.
2. Different alphabet between monthly income of respondent parents denote significant at 5 per cent level using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT).
3. For respondents' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions under seven factors 'a' signifies 'neutrally agreed'.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is accepted at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, the monthly income of respondent parents' at all ranges have moderate level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions i.e., the respondent parents' earn monthly income of up to Rs.30,000 [content marketing (22.57^a), search engine optimization (18.96^a), social media marketing (24.30^a), pay-per-click marketing (18.74^a), email marketing (16.52^a), instant message marketing (15.09^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (16.48^a); between Rs.30,001 and Rs.50,000 [content marketing (23.57^a), search engine optimization (17.62^a), social media marketing (23.33^a), pay-per-click marketing (18.81^a), email marketing (17.48^a), instant message marketing (15.33^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (16.52^a); between Rs.50,001 and Rs.70,000 [content marketing (22.69^a), search engine optimization (17.65^a), social media marketing (20.96^a), pay-per-click marketing (17.88^a), email marketing (16.46^a), instant message marketing (14.62^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (16.85^a); between Rs.70,001 and Rs.90,000 [content marketing (22.69^a), search engine optimization (18.44^a), social media marketing (22.50^a), pay-per-click marketing (18.63^a), email marketing (16.06^a), instant message marketing (13.44^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (15.88^a)] and monthly income of Rs.90,001 and above [content marketing (22.07^a), search engine optimization (19.07^a), social media marketing (24.86^a), pay-per-click marketing (17.79^a), email marketing (17.14^a), instant message marketing (15.07^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (15.71^a)] have moderate level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Hence, it is concluded that there is no relationship between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. There is no evident from the previous studies that there is no

relationship between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by educational institutions and companies.

4.3.6 Significant Difference between Respondents' Awareness about Maritime Educational Institutions and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between respondents' awareness about maritime educational institutions and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Alternative Hypothesis: There is a significant difference between respondents' awareness about maritime educational institutions and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Table 4.3.6: Respondents' Awareness about Maritime Educational Institutions and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions (ANOVA Test)

Factors	Awareness					F value	P Value
	FFM	AN	ATC	DM	EEF		
Content Marketing	20.50 ^b (3.68)	22.88 ^c (3.96)	20.85 ^b (3.59)	23.94 ^c (3.53)	18.33 ^a (2.53)	3.211	0.001 ^{**}
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	18.43 ^b (3.23)	18.47 ^c (3.13)	19.00 ^b (2.86)	20.11 ^c (2.59)	16.50 ^a (3.47)	10.060	0.001 ^{**}
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	21.83 ^b (7.87)	22.53 ^c (3.32)	21.90 ^b (5.37)	24.56 ^c (3.83)	19.90 ^a (8.51)	8.188	0.001 ^{**}
Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	17.58 ^b (3.07)	19.33 ^c (2.19)	17.65 ^b (2.44)	20.93 ^c (2.90)	15.50 ^a (4.19)	3.841	0.001 ^{**}
Email Marketing	16.75 ^b (4.11)	18.82 ^c (2.08)	16.67 ^b (2.19)	20.90 ^c (2.27)	14.95 ^a (3.46)	11.984	0.001 ^{**}
Instant Message Marketing	15.33 ^b (5.16)	17.67 ^c (2.95)	15.94 ^b (2.75)	18.38 ^c (4.09)	12.85 ^a (4.25)	9.100	0.001 ^{**}
Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing	16.08 ^b (4.75)	18.00 ^c (3.28)	16.18 ^b (2.59)	19.88 ^c (3.73)	14.55 ^a (3.51)	8.944	0.001 ^{**}

[Source: Primary data

Note

1. ^{**} Denotes significant at 1% level.

2. The values within the bracket denote standard deviation.
3. FFM - Friends & Family Members, AN - Advertisement in Newspapers, ATC - Advertisement in TV Channels, DM - Digital Marketing and EEF - Experts of Education Fair.
4. Different alphabet between awareness of respondents on maritime educational institutions denote significant at 5 per cent level using Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT).
5. For respondents' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions under seven factors 'a' signifies below 'neutrally agreed'; 'b' signifies 'neutrally agreed' and 'c' signifies above 'neutrally agreed'

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant difference between respondents' awareness about maritime educational institutions and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, those respondents who are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing [content marketing (23.94^c), search engine optimization (20.11^c), social media marketing (24.56^c), pay-per-click marketing (20.93^c), email marketing (20.90^c), instant message marketing (18.38^c) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (19.88^c)] and advertisement through newspapers [content marketing (22.88^c), search engine optimization (18.47^c), social media marketing (22.53^c), pay-per-click marketing (19.33^c), email marketing (18.82^c), instant message marketing (17.67^c) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (18.00^c)] have higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions than the respondents who are aware of the same through experts of educational fair [content marketing (18.33^a), search engine optimization (16.50^a), social media marketing (19.90^a), pay-per-click marketing (15.50^a), email marketing (14.95^a), instant message marketing (12.85^a) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (14.55^a)].

Moreover, those respondents who are aware of maritime educational institutions through advertisement in television channels [content marketing (20.85^b), search engine optimization (19.00^b), social media marketing (21.90^b), pay-per-click marketing

(17.65^b), email marketing (16.67^b), instant message marketing (15.94^b) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (16.18^b) and from their friends and family members have moderate level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions [content marketing (20.50^b), search engine optimization (18.43^b), social media marketing (21.83^b), pay-per-click marketing (17.58^b), email marketing (16.75^b), instant message marketing (15.33^b) and affiliate marketing/influencer marketing (16.08^b)].

Hence, it is noticeable that there is a direct relationship between respondent's awareness about maritime educational institutions and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions i.e., respondents who are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing and advertisement through newspapers have higher level of opinion towards digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions than the respondents who are aware of the same from experts of education fair. The respondents who are aware of maritime educational institutions through advertisement in television channels and from their friends and relatives have medium level of opinion towards digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. It is proven from the following previous studies that there is a direct relationship between respondents' awareness and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by educational institutions and companies namely Shanmuga Priya , M., & Dr. Anitha , P., 2021; Dr. Soundarapandiyam, K., & Dr. Nimalathan, B., 2020; Pappas et al., 2017; Li et al., 2015.

4.4 SIGNIFICANT ASSOCIATION BETWEEN STUDENTS' SOCIO-ECONOMIC VARIABLES AND THEIR OPINION ON EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE MARITIME EDUCATION(CHI-SQUARE TEST)

In order to study the significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education, chi-square test is applied.

HYPOTHESIS (H₁₂): There is a significant association between respondents' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

4.4.1 Significant Association between Respondents' Gender and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between respondents' gender and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between respondents' gender and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Table 4.4.1: Respondents' Gender and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education (Chi-square test)

Gender	Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education			Total	Chi-square value	P value
	Low	Medium	High			
Male	48 (21.1)	100 (43.9)	80 (35.1)	228	83.057	0.001**
Female	52 (30.2)	100 (58.1)	20 (11.6)	172		
Total	100	200	100	400		

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ** Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values shown in () refer to row percentage.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between respondents' gender and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Based on the row percentage, male respondents (35.1%) are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the female respondents (11.6%). It is also noted that majority of the respondents have moderate level of opinion [male (43.9%) and female (58.1%)] on effectiveness of online maritime education. The research studies which support the result that there is a significant association between respondents' gender and their opinion on effectiveness of online education are Alavudeen SS, 2021; Yu, Z., 2021; Ghaleb A. 2021; Naresha , B., 2016; Md. Islam, A.,2011.

4.4.2 Significant Association between Respondents' Age and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between respondents' age and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between respondents' age and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Table 4.4.2: Respondents' Age and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education (Chi-square test)

Age (in years)	Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education			Total	Chi-square value	P value
	Low	Medium	High			
21 years	29 (18.1)	82 (51.3)	49 (30.6)	160	16.228	0.001**
22 years	32 (24.2)	64 (48.5)	36 (27.3)	132		
23 years	24 (35.3)	34 (50.0)	10 (14.7)	68		
24 years	15 (37.5)	20 (50.0)	5 (12.5)	40		
Total	100	200	100	400		

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ** Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values shown in () refer to row percentage.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between respondents' age and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. Based

on the row percentage, respondents in the age group of 21 years (30.6%) are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondents in the age group of 24 years (12.5%). It is also noted that majority of the respondents have moderate level of opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education [21 years (51.3%), 22 years (48.5%), 23 years (50%) and 24 years (50%)]. The research studies which support the result that there is a significant association between respondents' age and their opinion on effectiveness of online education are Alavudeen SS, 2021; Yu, Z., 2021; Durga Bhusal, 2020; Ghaleb A. 2021; Naresha, B., 2016; Md. Islam, A., 2011.

4.4.3 Significant Association between Respondents' University and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between respondents' university and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between respondents' university and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Table 4.4.3: Respondents' University and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education (Chi-square test)

Educational Status	Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education			Total	Chi-square value	P value
	Low	Medium	High			
Central University	35 (64.8)	14 (25.9)	5 (9.3)	54	42.755	0.003**
Private University	31 (16.5)	95 (50.5)	62 (33.0)	188		
State University	34 (21.5)	91 (57.6)	33 (20.9)	158		
Total	104	184	112	400		

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ** Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values shown in () refer to row percentage.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between

respondents' university and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. Based on the row percentage, respondents pursuing their maritime education in private university (33%) are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondents who are pursuing their maritime education in central university (9.3%). It is also noted that majority of the respondents have moderate level of opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education [central university (25.9%), private university (50.5%) and state university (57.6%)]. The research studies which have proven that there is a significant association between respondents' university and their opinion on effectiveness of online education are Alavudeen SS, 2021; Ghaleb A. 2021; Yu, Z., 2021; Naresha, B., 2016; Md. Islam, A., 2011.

4.4.4 Significant Association between Respondent Parents' Occupational Status and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between respondents' occupational status and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between respondents' occupational status and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Table 4.4.4: Respondent Parents' Occupational Status and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education (Chi-square test)

Occupational Status	Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education			Total	Chi-square Value	P value
	Low	Medium	High			
Private Employee	16 (16.7)	65 (67.7)	15 (15.6)	96	54.217	0.001**
Government Employee	38 (32.8)	58 (50.0)	20 (17.2)	116		
Business	18 (19.6)	41 (44.6)	33 (35.9)	92		
Professionals	8 (14.3)	26 (46.4)	22 (39.3)	56		
Agriculturist	20 (50.0)	10 (25.0)	10 (25.0)	40		
Total	100	200	100	400		

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ** Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values shown in () refer to row percentage.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. Based on the row percentage, respondent parents' occupation under the category of professionals (39.3%) is superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondent parents' who are private employee (15.6%). It is also noted that majority of the respondents have moderate level of opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education [private employee (67.7%), government employee (50%), business people (44.6%), professionals (46.4%) and agriculturist (25%)]. The research studies which proven the result that there is a significant association between respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on effectiveness of online education are Alavudeen SS, 2021; Yu, Z., 2021; Ghaleb A. 2021; Naresha , B., 2016; Md. Islam, A., 2011.

4.4.5 Significant Association between Respondent Parents' Monthly Income and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Table 4.4.5: Respondent Parents' Monthly Income and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education (Chi-square test)

Monthly Income	Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education			Total	Chi-square value	P value
	Low	Medium	High			
Up to Rs. 30,000	20 (21.7)	64 (69.6)	8 (8.7)	92	61.405	0.003**
Rs. 30,001 – Rs. 50,000	20 (23.8)	52 (61.9)	12 (14.3)	84		

Rs. 50,001 – Rs. 70,000	32 (30.8)	44 (42.3)	28 (26.9)	104		
Rs. 70,001 – Rs. 90,000	12 (18.8)	16 (25.0)	36 (56.3)	64		
Rs. 90,001 and Above	16 (28.6)	24 (42.9)	16 (28.6)	56		
Total	100	200	100	400		

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ** Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values shown in () refer to row percentage.

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. Based on the row percentage, respondent parents' who are earning monthly income between Rs. 70,001 and Rs. 90,000 (56.3%) are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondent parents' earning monthly income of up to 30,000 (8.7%). It is also noted that majority of the respondents have moderate level of opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education [parents' monthly income of up to Rs. 30,000 (69.6%), Rs.30,001 – Rs. 50,000 (61.9%), Rs. 50,001 – Rs. 70,000 (42.3%), Rs. 70,001 – Rs. 90,000 (25%) and Rs. 90,001 and above (42.9%).The research studies which evident the result that there is a significant association between monthly income of respondent parents and their opinion on effectiveness of online education are Alavudeen SS, 2021; Yu, Z., 2021; Ghaleb A. 2021; Naresha , B., 2016; Md. Islam, A.,2011.

4.4.6 Significant Association between Respondents' Awareness and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between respondents' awareness and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between respondents' awareness and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.

Table 4.4.6: Respondents' Awareness and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education (Chi-square test)

Awareness	Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education			Total	Chi-square Value	P value
	Low	Medium	High			
Friends & Family Members	14 (29.2)	22 (45.8)	12 (25.0)	48	14.517	0.019*
Advertisement in Newspapers	20 (25.0)	40 (50.0)	20 (25.0)	80		
Advertisement in TV Channels	22 (32.4)	28 (41.2)	18 (26.5)	68		
Digital Marketing	29 (17.3)	94 (56.0)	45 (26.8)	168		
Experts of Education Fair	15 (41.7)	16 (44.4)	5 (13.9)	36		
Total	100	200	100	400		

[Source: Primary data]

Note

1. ** Denotes significant at 1% level.
2. The values shown in () refer to row percentage.

Since P value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected at 5 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between respondents' awareness and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. Based on the row percentage, the respondents who are aware of maritime educational institution based on digital marketing (26.8%) are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondents who are aware of the same from experts of educational fair by the colleges or university (13.9%). It is also noted that majority of the respondents have moderate level of opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education [friends and family members (45.8%), advertisement in newspapers (50%), advertisement in TV channels (41.2%), digital marketing (56%) and experts of education fair (44.4%)]. The research studies which support the result that there is a significant association between respondents' awareness and their opinion on effectiveness of online education are Dr.P. Subramanian, B & Shanmugam, A.P., 2021; Panneer selvam. S.K., 2016; Yacoba, A., et al., 2011.

4.5 SIGNIFICANT ASSOCIATION BETWEEN STUDENTS' SOCIO-ECONOMIC VARIABLES AND THEIR PREFERENCES AND DECISION MAKING TO PURSUE MARITIME EDUCATION(CORRESPONDENCE ANALYSIS)

In order to study the significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education, Correspondence analysis is used.

HYPOTHESIS (H₁₃): There is a significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

4.5.1 Association between Respondents' age and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between respondents' age and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between respondents' age and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Table 4.5.1: Respondents' Age and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education (Correspondence Analysis)

Dimension	Inertia	Proportion of Inertia		Chi-square value	P value
		Accounted for	Cumulative		
1	0.613	0.830	0.830	295.389	0.001**
2	0.125	0.170	1.000		
Total	0.738	1.000	1.000		

[Source: Primary data]

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level.

Since the p value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between respondents' age and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education i.e., the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is based on their age. In this model, the total inertia (total variance explained) is 73.8% which indicates that 73.8% of the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education can be significantly explained by their age. The remaining

26.2% is not explained which means that the rest 26.2% of the variation in students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is related to other variables which are not depicted in this model. Therefore, the total inertia of this model is considered as good.

Figure 4.5.1: Respondents' Age and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

The figure 4.5.1 illustrates the association between respondents' age and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The students who are in the age of 21 years have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education, followed by the students in the age of 22 years have medium level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education and the students in the age group between 23 and 24 years have low level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The studies which has proven the association between the age and students' decision to pursue higher education are Punpreet Kaur & Dr. Amanpreet 2022; Bajar, J., Gopun, C., 2021; Rodrigues, A. P., 2017; Tamtekin Aydın, O., & Bayır, F., 2016.

4.5.2 Association between Respondents' University and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between respondents' university and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between respondents' university and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Table 4.5.2: Respondents' University and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education (Correspondence Analysis)

Dimension	Inertia	Proportion of Inertia		Chi-square value	P value
		Accounted for	Cumulative		
1	0.559	0.729	0.729	306.556	0.001**
2	0.208	0.271	1.000		
Total	0.766	1.000	1.000		

[Source: Primary data]

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level.

Since the p value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between respondents' university and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education i.e., the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is based on their university. In this model, the total inertia (total variance explained) is 76.6% which indicates that 76.6% of the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education can be significantly explained by their university. The remaining 23.4% is not explained which means that the rest 23.4% of the variation in students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is related to other variables which are not depicted in this model. Therefore, the total inertia of this model is considered as good.

The figure 4.5.2 illustrates the association between respondents' university and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The students who pursue their maritime education in central university have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education, followed by the students pursuing their maritime education in private university have medium level of preferences and decision

making to pursue maritime education and the students pursuing their maritime education in state university have low level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The studies which has proven the association between the university and students' decision to pursue higher education are Punpreet Kaur & Dr. Amanpreet 2022; Bajar, J., Gopun, C., 2021;Rodrigues, A. P., 2017; Tamtekin Aydın, O., & Bayır, F., 2016.

Figure 4.5.2: Respondents' University and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

4.5.3 Association between Occupational Status of Respondent Parents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between occupational status of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between occupational status of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Table 4.5.3: Occupational Status of Respondent Parents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education (Correspondence Analysis)

Dimension	Inertia	Proportion of Inertia		Chi-square value	P value
		Accounted for	Cumulative		
1	0.507	0.660	0.660	119.713	0.001**
2	0.261	0.340	1.000		
Total	0.767	1.000	1.000		

[Source: Primary data]

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level.

Since the p value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between occupational status of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education i.e., the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is based on their parents' occupational status. In this model, the total inertia (total variance explained) is 76.7% which indicates that 76.7% of the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education can be significantly explained by their parents' occupational status. The remaining 23.3% is not explained which means that the rest 23.3% of the variation in students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is related to other variables which are not depicted in this model. Therefore, the total inertia of this model is considered as good.

The figure 4.5.3 illustrates the association between occupational status of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The students' parent who are government employee have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education, followed by the students' parent who are professionals and doing business have medium level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education and the students' parent who are private employee and agriculturist have low level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.. The studies which have proven the association between parents' occupation and students' decision to pursue higher education are Punpreet Kaur & Dr. Amanpreet 2022; Bajar, J., Gopun, C., 2021; Rodrigues, A. P., 2017; Tamtekin Aydın, O., & Bayır, F., 2016.

Figure 4.5.3: Occupational Status of Respondent Parents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

4.5.4 Association between Monthly Income of Respondent Parents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between monthly income of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between monthly income of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Table 4.5.4: Monthly Income of Respondent Parents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education (Correspondence Analysis)

Dimension	Inertia	Proportion of Inertia		Chi-square value	P value
		Accounted for	Cumulative		
1	0.636	0.906	0.906	109.581	0.001**
2	0.066	0.094	1.000		
Total	0.702	1.000	1.000		

[Source: Primary data] Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level.

Since the p value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between monthly income of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education i.e., the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is based on their parents' monthly income. In this model, the total inertia (total variance explained) is 70.2% which indicates that 70.2% of the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education can be significantly explained by their parents' monthly income. The remaining 29.8% is not explained which means that the rest 29.8% of the variation in students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is related to other variables which are not depicted in this model. Therefore, the total inertia of this model is considered as good.

Figure 4.5.4: Monthly Income of Respondent Parents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

The figure 4.5.4 illustrates the association between monthly income of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The students' parent who are earning above Rs.90,000 have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education, followed by the students'

parent who are earning monthly income between Rs. 50,000 and Rs. 90,000 have medium level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education and the students' parents who are earning monthly income below Rs. 50,000 have low level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The studies which have proven the association between parents' monthly income and students' decision to pursue higher education are Punpreet Kaur & Dr. Amanpreet 2022; Bajar, J., Gopun, C., 2021; Rodrigues, A. P., 2017; Tamtekin Aydın, O., & Bayır, F., 2016.

4.5.5 Association between Awareness of Respondents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant association between awareness of respondents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant association between awareness of respondents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

Table 4.5.5: Awareness of Respondents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education (Correspondence Analysis)

Dimension	Inertia	Proportion of Inertia		Chi-square value	P value
		Accounted for	Cumulative		
1	0.473	0.591	0.591	124.767	0.001**
2	0.327	0.409	1.000		
Total	0.800	1.000	1.000		

[Source: Primary data]

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level.

Since the p value is less than 0.01, null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant association between awareness of respondents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education i.e., the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is based on their awareness regarding maritime educational institutions. In this model, the total inertia (total variance explained) is 80% which indicates that 80% of the students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education can be significantly explained by their awareness regarding maritime educational institutions. The remaining 20% is not explained which means that the rest 20% of the variation in students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education is related to

other variables which are not depicted in this model. Therefore, the total inertia of this model is considered as excellent.

Figure 4.5.5: Awareness of Respondents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

The figure 4.5.5 illustrates the association between awareness of respondents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The students who are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing and advertisement in news papers have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education, followed by the students aware of the same through advertisement and television channels have medium level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education and the students aware of the same through friends and family members and by the experts of educational fair have low level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. The studies which have proven the association between awareness and students’ decision to pursue higher education are Kusumawati, A., 2019; Constantinides, E., & Marc C. Zinck Stagno, 2012.

4.6 SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE MARITIME EDUCATION AND STUDENT'S PREFERENCES AND DECISION TO PURSUE MARITIME EDUCATION (BIVARIATE CORRELATION)

In order to study the significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, bivariate correlation is applied.

HYPOTHESIS (H₁₄): There is a significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.

Table 4.6: Relationship between Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education and Student's Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education (Bivariate Correlation)

Factors	Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education	Student's Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education
Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education	1	0.993**
Student's Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education	0.993**	1

[Source: Primary Data]

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since the P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence it is concluded that there is a strong and positive relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education. This implies if the level of effectiveness of online

maritime education increases; the student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education also increases.

There are no previous studies that have been proven the relationship between effectiveness of online education and students' preferences towards educational institutions. But, the studies that support the relationship between effectiveness of online education and student engagement are Darius, P.S.H., et al., 2021; Muthuprasad, T., et al., 2021; Gopal, R., 2021; Selvaraj, A., et al., 2021; Veena. M., et al., 2021; Obeidat, A., et al., 2020.

4.7 SIGNIFICANT INFLUENCE OF DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES ON STUDENTS' PREFERENCES AND DECISION TO PURSUE MARITIME EDUCATION (MULTIPLE REGRESSION)

In order to study the significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, multiple regression is applied.

HYPOTHESIS (H₁₅): There is a significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.

Table 4.7.1.a Predictor Variables of Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple R value	R Square value	Adjusted R² value	F value	Standard Error	P value
0.993	0.986	0.985	4825.399	1.622	0.001**

[Source: Primary Data]

From the table 4.7.1.a, it is revealed that the students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education can be predicted at $R^2 = 0.986$. The value of R^2 denotes that 98.6% of the observed variability in students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education can be significantly explained by their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions namely Content Marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Social Media Marketing (SMM), Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC), Email Marketing, Instant Message Marketing and Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing. The remaining 1.4% is not explained which means that the rest 1.4% of the variation of students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime

education is related to other variables which are not depicted in this model. Since the P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, the linear combination of students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions is significantly related to their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education ($F = 4825.399$ and $P = <0.001$).

Table 4.7.1.b: Co-efficient between Digital Marketing Strategies and Students' Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education

Variables	USC	SE	SC	t value	P value
(Constant)	0.339	0.152	-	2.232	0.006**
Content Marketing	0.410	0.065	0.249	6.346	0.001**
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	0.373	0.065	0.182	5.746	0.001**
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	0.721	0.077	0.371	9.365	0.001**
Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	0.266	0.071	0.110	3.734	0.001**
Email Marketing	0.385	0.080	0.153	4.833	0.001**
Instant Message Marketing	0.326	0.063	0.166	5.217	0.006**
Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing	0.298	0.065	0.215	4.587	0.002**

[Source: Primary Data]

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

USC = Unstandardised Co-efficient, SE = Standard Error

SC = Standardised Co-efficient

Dependent variable (Y) = Students' Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education.

Independent/predictor variable = Content Marketing (X_1), Search Engine Optimization (SEO) (X_2), Social Media Marketing (SMM) (X_3), Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) (X_4), Email Marketing (X_5), Instant Message Marketing (X_6) and Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing (X_7)

From the table 4.7.1.b, the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) equation for predicting students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education is: -

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \text{Students' Preferences and Decision} \\ \text{to Pursue Maritime Education (Y)} \end{array} \right\} = 0.410X_1 + 0.373X_2 + 0.721X_3 + 0.266X_4 \\ + 0.385X_5 + 0.326X_6 + 0.298X_7 + e$$

The co-efficient of X_1 is 0.410 which represents the direct relationship between content marketing and students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, holding other variable as constant. The estimated positive sign indicates that for each additional unit of students' opinion on content marketing strategy, there is a 0.410 unit increase in their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education and it is significant at 1% level. Rajkumar, S.G., et al., 2021; Julie M. Pharr, 2019; Jacqueline Marie Getty, 2015 are the studies which has proven that there is a significant relationship between content marketing and students' preferences on educational institutions.

The co-efficient of X_2 is 0.373 which represents the direct relationship between search engine optimization and students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, holding other variable as constant. The estimated positive sign indicates that for each additional unit of students' opinion on search engine optimization strategy, there is a 0.373 unit increase in their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education and it is significant at 1% level. This has been proven by the previous studies namely Bin, W., et al., 2018; Bhandari, R S., & Bansal, S., 2019; Bhandari, R. S.,, 2018.

The co-efficient of X_3 is 0.721 which represents the direct relationship between social media marketing and students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, holding other variable as constant. The estimated positive sign indicates that for each additional unit of students' opinion on social media marketing strategy, there is a 0.721 unit increase in their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education and it is significant at 1% level. This has been evident from the previous studies namely C.H., et al., 2022; Dr.Ghosal, I., et al., 2020; Rishab Singh, 2019; Chen E, DiVall M., 2018.

The co-efficient of X_4 is 0.266 which represents the direct relationship between pay-per-click marketing and students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, holding other variable as constant. The estimated positive sign indicates that for each additional unit of students' opinion on pay-per-click marketing strategy, there is a 0.266 unit increase in their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education and it is significant at 1% level. Sam Yadegar, 2021; Messah, O.B., & Mutali. J. Namulia Immaculate, 2020 has proven that there is a relationship between pay-per-click marketing and educational institutions.

The co-efficient of X_5 is 0.385 which represents the direct relationship between email marketing and students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education,

holding other variable as constant. The estimated positive sign indicates that for each additional unit of students' opinion on email marketing strategy, there is a 0.385 unit increase in their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education and it is significant at 1% level. Anton Savchenko, 2022; Elle Gellrich, 2022; Andriani KUSUMAWATI, 2019 has evident that there is a relationship between email marketing and effective promotion of educational institutions.

The co-efficient of X_6 is 0.326 which represents the direct relationship between instant message marketing and students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, holding other variable as constant. The estimated positive sign indicates that for each additional unit of students' opinion on instant message marketing strategy, there is a 0.326 unit increase in their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education and it is significant at 1% level. The studies which has proven that there is a relationship between instant message marketing and effectiveness and students' preferences on educational institutions are Le Roux DB & Parry DA., 2022; Tang, Y., Hew, K.F., 2022; Pokhrel, S.,2018.

The co-efficient of X_7 is 0.298 which represents the direct relationship between affiliate marketing/influencer marketing and students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education, holding other variable as constant. The estimated positive sign indicates that for each additional unit of students' opinion on affiliate marketing/influencer marketing strategy, there is a 0.298 unit increase in their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education and it is significant at 1% level. Neha Kulwal, 2021; Nick Malekos, 2019 are the articles that has proven there is a relationship between affiliate marketing and promotion of educational institutions.

Thus, the analysis has proven that there is a significant impact of digital marketing strategies and students' preferences towards educational institutions and the same has been proven by the previous studies namely Dr. Gondane, V., & Pawar, M., 2021; Kumar, V., et al., 2021; Mohit Kumar, et al., 2021; Rajkumar, S.G., et al., 2021; Biswas, S., 2020; Dr.Ghosal, I., et al., 2020; Prihadini, D., 2020; Krishnamoorthy, A., Srimathi, H., 2019; Afzal Basha, 2019; Dhote, T., et al., 2015.

4.8 SIGNIFICANT DIFFERENCE IN THE MEAN RANK OF FACTORS THAT INSIST THE STUDENTS TO PURSUE MARITIME EDUCATION AND THE DIGITAL MARKETING PLATFORM PREFERRED BY THEM TO SEARCH FOR INFORMATION REGARDING MARITIME EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS (FRIEDMAN TEST)

In order to find the significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education and the digital marketing platform preferred by them to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions, Friedman test is applied.

Null Hypothesis (H₁₆): There is no significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education and the digital marketing platform preferred by them to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions.

4.8.1 Significant Differences in the Mean Rank of Factors that insist the Students to Pursue Maritime Education

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education.

Table 4.8.1: Factors that Insist the Students to Pursue Maritime Education (Friedman test)

Factors	Mean Rank	Chi-square value	P value
To gain marine knowledge	6.33	636.741	0.001**
To place in a dignified job	2.80		
To get high salaried job	3.87		
To become a captain of the ship	4.19		
To do a challenging job in marine	5.24		
Higher demand over the globe	1.49		
Interest to do offshore jobs	7.74		
Affordable fees structure	8.22		

[Source: Primary Data] Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant difference among the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education. On the basis of mean rank, the major significant factor that insist the students to pursue maritime education is “Higher demand over the globe (1.49)” followed by “To place in a dignified job (2.80)”, “To get high salaried job (3.87)”, “To become a captain of the ship(4.19)”, “To do a challenging job in marine (5.24)”, “To gain marine knowledge(6.33)”, “Interest to do offshore jobs (7.74)” and “Affordable fees structure(8.22)”. The studies that has proven the above factors that influences the students to prefer maritime education are Edirisinghe, L., & Shen, L., 2018; Ku, Kang-Ning et al., 2017; Edirisinghe, et al, 2016; Carlos L., et al., 2015; Kalvaitiene, G., et al., 2011.

4.8.2 Significant Differences in the Mean Rank of Digital Marketing Platform Preferred by the Students to Search for Information Regarding Maritime Educational Institutions

Null Hypothesis: There is no significant difference in the mean rank of digital marketing platform preferred by the students to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions.

Alternate Hypothesis: There is a significant difference in the mean rank of digital marketing platform preferred by the students to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions.

Table 4.8.2: Digital Marketing Platform Preferred by the Students to Search for Information Regarding Maritime Educational Institutions (Friedman test)

Digital Marketing Platform	Mean Rank	Chi-square value	P value
Content Marketing	2.38	648.691	0.001**
Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	5.82		
Social Media Marketing (SMM)	1.88		
Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	7.63		
Email Marketing	3.94		
Instant Message Marketing	4.78		
Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing	6.02		

[Source: Primary Data] Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

Since P value is less than 0.01, the null hypothesis is rejected at 1 per cent level of significance. Hence, it is concluded that there is a significant difference among the mean ranks of digital marketing platform preferred by the students to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions. On the basis of mean rank, the most significant digital marketing platform preferred by the students to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions is Social Media Marketing (SMM)(1.88) followed by Content Marketing (2.63), Email Marketing (3.94), Instant Message Marketing (4.78), Search Engine Optimization (SEO) (5.82), Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing(6.02) and Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) (7.63). The proven studies that describes the digital marketing platform preferred by students to search for information regarding educational institutions are Mukosa, F., et al., 2022; Maity, S., 2022; Dr. Gondane, V., & Pawar, M., 2021; Kumar, V., et al., 2021; Mohit Kumar, et al., 2021; Rajkumar, S.G., et al., 2021; Nektarios S. Makrydakis, 2021; Ramadhan, A., & Gunarto, M., 2021; Castro Benavides, L.M., et al., 2020; Cordero-Gutiérrez, R., & Lahuerta-Otero, E., 2020.

4.9 STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING TO ESTIMATE THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STUDENTS' OPINION ON EFFECTIVENESS OF ONLINE MARITIME EDUCATION DURING COVID-19 AND DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES APPLIED BY MARITIME EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS (IV) AND THEIR PREFERENCES AND DECISION MAKING PROCESS TO PURSUE MARITIME EDUCATION (DV)

In order to find the fitness of data and to estimate relationship between the variables namely students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education is executed by using Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS).

HYPOTHESIS (H₁₇): There does not exists a perfectly fit model between students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions(IV) and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education(DV).

The variables used in the Structural Equation Modeling are:

I. Observed, Endogenous Variables

1. Students' Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education
2. Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions
3. Students' Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education

II. Unobserved, exogenous variables

e1: Error term for Students' Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education

e2: Error term for Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions

e3: Error term for Students' Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education

Hence, Number of Variables in this model is:

Number of variables in this model : 06

Number of observed variables : 03

Number of unobserved variables : 03

Number of exogenous variables : 03

Number of endogenous variables : 03

Overall Test of the Model

The overall model fit can be estimated through three sets of goodness-of-fit measures namely,

- a) Absolute fit measures
- b) Incremental fit measures and
- c) Parsimonious fit measures (Hair et al., 1998).
- d) Maximum likelihood estimates

a) Absolute fit measures

It is calculated by four measures namely likelihood ratio Chi-square test, Root Mean Square Residual (RMR), Goodness-of-fit Index (GFI) and Adjusted Goodness-of-fit Index (AGFI).

Minimum was achieved

Chi-square = 32.455

Degrees of freedom = 3

Probability level = 0.068

The calculated value of Chi-square test is 32.455, which gives a P-value of 0.068 (greater than 0.05, Hair et al., 1998) and this model is an adequately fit model.

Table 4.9.1
Model Fit Summary – CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Default model	5	32.455	1	0.068	32.455
Saturated model	6	0.000	0	-	-
Independence model	3	231.240	3	0.000	77.080

[Source: Primary Data]

It is the minimum value of the discrepancy between the predicted and actual matrices. Chi-square statistics compares the default model and the independence model with the saturated model. From the above table, it is found that the default model has been associated at 32.455 percent with saturated model and on other side the independence model has been associated at 231.240 percent with saturated model.

Table 4.9.2
Root Mean Square Residual, Goodness-of-Fit and Adjusted Goodness-of-fit Index

Model	RMR	GFI	AGFI	PGFI
Default model	0.067	0.983	0.998	0.164
Saturated model	0.000	1.000	-	-
Independence model	6.318	0.744	0.487	0.372

[Source: Primary Data]

i) Root Mean Square Residual (RMR): It is the square root of the average squared amount by which the sample variances and covariances differ from their estimates obtained under the assumption that the model is correct. The RMR (Root Mean Square Residuals) should be less than 0.08 for a good model (Hair et al., 2006). From the above table, it is observed that the default model of RMR is 0.067 which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

ii) Goodness-of-Fit (GFI): It is similar to the Baseline Comparisons giving a statistic between 0 and 1. If the GFI is greater than 0.90, it indicates that it is a perfect fit model (Hu and Bentler, 1999), and is used with maximum likelihood estimation for missing data. From the above table, it is noted that the default model of GFI is 0.983 which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

iii) Adjusted Goodness-of-fit Index (AGFI): It takes into account the degrees of freedom available for testing the model. If the AGFI is greater than 0.90, it indicates that

it is a perfectly fit model (Hair et al., 2006). From the above table, it is inferred that the default model of AGFI is 0.998 which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

iv) Incremental Fit Measures/ Baseline Comparisons

It compares the model with a base line or null model. Null model is a single model with no measurement error. The measures namely Normed Fit Index (NFI), Relative Fit Index (RFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) and Comparative Fit Index (CFI) are used to calculate the model fit.

Table 4.9.3
Baseline Comparisons

Model	NFI Delta1	RFI rho1	IFI Delta2	TLI rho2	CFI
Default model	0.955	0.964	0.959	0.976	0.999
Saturated model	1.000	-	1.000	-	1.000
Independence model	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

[Source: Primary Data]

i) Normed Fit Index (NFI): It shows how far the default model is between the (terribly fitting) independence model and the (perfectly fitting) saturated model. From the above table, it is observed that the default model has a discrepancy of 0.955 between the (terribly fitting) independence model and the (perfectly fitting) saturated model (Bentler and Bonett, 1980). It is very closer to the fit of the saturated model than the fit of the independence model which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

ii) Relative Fit Index (RFI): It is the NFI standardized based on the degrees of freedom of the models, with values close to one again indicating a very good fit (Bollen, 1986). From the above table, it is found that the default model of RFI is 0.964 which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

iii) Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI) and Comparative Fit Index (CFI): It is also known as the Bentler-Bonett Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI). The typical range for TLI lies between zero and one, but it is not limited to that range. TLI values close to 1 indicate a very good fit. From the above table, it is known that the default model of TLI is 0.976 which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model. It is also found that the default model of Incremental Fit Index (IFI) is 0.959 and Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is 0.999 are equal to one which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

iv) Parsimony-Adjusted Measures

It is calculated by Parsimony Ratio (PRATIO), Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI) and Parsimonious Comparative Fit Index (PCFI).

Table 4.9.4
Parsimony-Adjusted Measures

Model	PRATIO	PNFI	PCFI
Default model	0.333	0.318	0.320
Saturated model	0.000	0.000	0.000
Independence model	1.000	0.000	0.000

[Source: Primary Data]

The parsimony ratio expresses the number of constraints in the model being evaluated as a fraction of the number of constraints in the independence (James, Mulaik and Brett, 1982; Mulaik, et al., 1989). It is used in the calculation of Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI) and Parsimonious Comparative Fit Index (PCFI). Parsimonious Normed Fit Index (PNFI) is the result of applying the parsimony adjustment to the NFI. Parsimonious Comparative Fit Index (PCFI) is a degree of freedom adjusted modification of the CFI. These three measures are likely to be lower than the NFI and CFI, because they take the model's complexity into account. From the above table, it is observed that the default model of PRATIO is 0.333, PNFI is 0.318 and PCFI is 0.320, which is lesser than NFI (0.955) which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

Table 4.9.5
Non-Centrality Parameter (NCP)

Model	NCP	LO 90	HI 90
Default model	9.455	2.523	23.797
Saturated model	0.000	0.000	0.000
Independence model	228.240	182.026	281.864

[Source: Primary Data]

It is an estimate of the Non-Centrality Parameter. The columns labelled "LO 90" and "HI 90" gives a 90) confidence interval for this statistics. From the above table, it is noted that with approximately 90 percent confidence, the population NCP for the Default model is between 2.523 and 23.797.

Table 4.9.6
Model Fit Summary – FMIN

Model	FMIN	F0	LO 90	HI 90
Default model	0.011	0.005	0.000	0.026
Saturated model	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
Independence model	0.253	0.241	0.175	0.322

[Source: Primary Data]

F_0 is the non-centrality parameter (NCP) divided by its degrees of freedom. This is similar to the CMIN/DF statistics. The results also give the lower (LO 90) and upper limits (HI 90) of a 90) confidence interval for this statistics. From the above table, it is observed that with approximately 90 percent confidence, the population F_0 for the Default model is between 0.000 and 0.026.

Table 4.9.7
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)

Model	RMSEA	LO 90	HI 90	PCLOSE
Default model	0.044	0.080	0.244	0.013
Independence model	0.437	0.390	0.485	0.000

[Source: Primary Data]

It is a corrected statistics that gives a penalty for model complexity, calculated as the square root of F_0 (F_0 tends to favor more complex models) divided by Degrees of Freedom. RMSEA values of 0.08 or less are good fit (Hair et al., 1998). From the above table, it is found that the default model of RMSEA is 0.044 which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model.

Table 4.9.8
Expected Cross Validation Index (EVC I)

Model	ECVI	LO 90	HI 90	MECVI
Default model	0.051	0.034	0.087	0.052
Saturated model	0.030	0.030	0.030	0.030
Independence model	0.595	0.479	0.729	0.595

[Source: Primary Data]

It is similar to Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The columns labelled “LO 90” and “HI 90” gives the 90) confidence interval for this statistics. From the above table, it is noted that with approximately 90 percent confidence, the population EVC I for the Default model is between 0.034 and 0.087.

Table 4.9.9
Model Fit Summary – HOELTER

Model	HOELTER .05	HOELTER .01
Default model	147	254
Independence model	14	20

[Source: Primary Data]

Hoelter’s (1983) “Critical N” is the largest sample size for which one would accept the hypothesis that a model is correct (in other words, the sample size above which the chi-square goodness of fit test would go from non-significant to significant). The result can be interpreted as “the model would be rejected at the [0.05/0.01] level with a sample size of greater than X.” From the above table, it is observed that Hoelter suggested that 147 is the largest sample size for which one could accept at the 0.05 level the hypothesis that the Default model is correct. In other words, if the sample size were any bigger than 147 one would reject the Default model at the 0.05 level. He also suggested that 254 is the largest sample size for which one could accept at the 0.01 level the hypothesis that the Default model is correct. In other words, if the sample size were bigger than 254 one would reject the Default model at the 0.01 level.

Maximum Likelihood Estimates

In order to obtain non-standardised and standardised regression weights, a variance estimate for the residual errors and the squared multiple correlation of the variables are calculated. The results are: -

Table 4.9.10
Variables in Structural Equation Model Analysis

Variables	USC	SE	SC	t value	P value
Students’ Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education ← Students’ Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education	0.615	0.065	0.772	9.529	0.001**
Students’ Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education ← Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions	0.928	0.072	0.802	12.836	0.001**

[Source: Primary Data]

Note: ** Denotes significant at 1% level

i) Unstandardized Co-efficient

From the above table, it is found that the unstandardized co-efficient for students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education is 0.615 which signifies a direct effect on their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education, holding other variables as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that the students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education would increase by 0.615 for every unit increase in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education and this co-efficient value is significant at 1% level.

From the above table, it is found that the unstandardized co-efficient for students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions is 0.928 which signifies a direct effect on their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education, holding other variables as constant. The estimated positive sign implies that the students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education would increase by 0.928 for every unit increase in their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and this co-efficient value is significant at 1% level.

ii) Standardized Co-efficient

Based on the standardized co-efficient, students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education have a positive impact on their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education(0.772). It means that when the students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education goes up by 1 unit; their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education goes up by 0.772 units.

Based on the standardized co-efficient, students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions have a positive impact on their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education (0.802). It means that when the students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions goes up by 1 unit; their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education goes up by 0.802 units.

This fit model has been proven by the research studies namely Mukosa, F., et al., 2022; Nektarios S. Makrydakis, 2021; Ramadhan, A., & Gunarto, M., 2021; Castro Benavides, L.M., et al., 2020; Cordero-Gutiérrez, R., & Lahuerta-Otero, E., 2020; Kusumawati, A., 2019; Aman, K., & Hussin, N., 2018; Kusumawati, A., 2018.

Figure 4.9.1

Structural Equation Modeling for Relationship between Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education, Digital Marketing Strategies and Students' Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education

4.10 SUMMARY

From the various analyses, the findings of the hypotheses formulated are given below: -

Table 4.10.1: Results of Hypotheses

Sl. No.	Hypotheses	Result
Significant Difference between Students' Socio-Economic Variables and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions		
H ₁₁	There is a significant difference between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.	
Independent Sample T-test		
1.	There is a significant difference between respondents' gender and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions	Accepted at 1 per cent level
Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test		
1.	There is a significant difference between respondents' age and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.	Except Content Marketing, Search Engine Marketing and Instant Message Marketing, the others are Accepted at 1 per cent level
2.	There is a significant difference between respondents' university and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
3.	There is a significant difference between respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
4.	There is a significant difference between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on digital	Rejected at 5 per cent level

	marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.	
5.	There is a significant difference between respondents' awareness about maritime educational institutions and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
Significant Association between Students' Socio-Economic Variables and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education		
H ₁₂	There is a significant association between respondents' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.	
Chi-square test		
1.	There is a significant association between respondents' gender and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
2.	There is a significant association between respondents' age and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
3.	There is a significant association between respondents' university and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
4.	There is a significant association between respondents' occupational status and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
5.	There is a significant association between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
6.	There is a significant association between respondents' awareness and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education.	Accepted at 5 per cent level
Significant Association between Students' Socio-Economic Variables and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education		
H ₁₃	There is a significant association between students' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.	

Correspondence Analysis		
1.	There is a significant association between respondents' age and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
2.	There is a significant association between respondents' university and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
3.	There is a significant association between occupational status of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education	Accepted at 1 per cent level
4.	There is a significant association between monthly income of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education	Accepted at 1 per cent level
5.	There is a significant association between awareness of respondents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education	Accepted at 1 per cent level
Significant Relationship Between Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education and Student's Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education		
H ₁₄	There is a significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.	
Bivariate Correlation		
1.	There is a significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
Significant Influence of Digital Marketing Strategies on Students' Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education		
H ₁₅	There is a significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.	
Multiple Regression		
1.	There is a significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level

Significant Difference in the Mean Rank of Factors that insist the Students to Pursue Maritime Education and the Digital Marketing Platform Preferred by them to Search for Information Regarding Maritime Educational Institutions		
H ₁₆	There is no significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education and the digital marketing platform preferred by them to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions.	
Friedman test		
1.	There is a significant difference in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
2.	There is a significant difference in the mean rank of digital marketing platform preferred by the students to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions.	Accepted at 1 per cent level
Estimating the Relationship Between Students' Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education during Covid-19 and Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions (IV) and their Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education(DV)		
H ₁₇	There does not exist a perfectly fit model between students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions(IV) and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education(DV)	
Structural Equation Modeling		
1.	There exists a perfectly fit model between students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education	Accepted at 1 per cent level

CHAPTER – V

FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

5.1 FINDINGS

The findings of the study are based on the analysis of primary data. Based on the analysis, it is learnt that there is a significant difference between students' socio-economic variables and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and significant association between respondents' socio-economic variables and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. It is also found that there is a there is an association between students' socio-economic variables and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

It is identified from Friedman test that the major significant factor that insists the students to pursue maritime education is “Higher demand over the globe (1.49)”; and most significant digital marketing platform preferred by the students to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions is Social Media Marketing (SMM).

It is evident from the correlation analysis that there is a significant relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education. Based on the regression analysis, it is proven that there is a significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.

Finally, it is proven from the Structural Equation Modeling that there is a relationship between students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education. Collectively, the findings of the study are given on the basis of objectives and hypotheses in the following order: -

5.1.1 Socio-economic status of the Respondents (Frequencies)

Based on frequencies, it can be inferred that majority of the respondents are male (57%), majority (40%) of the respondents are 21 years of age, majority (29%) of the respondents' parents are government employees, majority (26%) of the respondents' family is earning monthly income between Rs.50,001 and Rs.70,000 and majority (42%) of the respondents are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing.

5.1.2 Factor Wise Level of Respondents' Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education during Covid-19, Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions and their Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education (Descriptive Statistics)

- a) **Respondents' Opinion towards Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education during Covid-19:** It is found that all the respondents' opinion towards effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19 is considered as good. Based on the mean value, the statement "Good communication skills of faculty members (3.75)" is considered to be the significant factor by the students that supported the effectiveness of online maritime education.
- b) **Respondents' Opinion towards Content Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is apparently known that all the respondents' opinion towards the content marketing applied by maritime educational institutions is considered as excellent. Based on the mean value, the statement "The language used for content is easily understandable (3.96)" is considered to be the significant factor that attracted the students to view the content marketing provided by maritime educational institutions.
- c) **Respondents' Opinion towards Price and Payment Method Offered by E-commerce Companies:** It is understood that e-commerce companies offer enhanced price and payment methods for the goods and services sold by them. Based on the mean value, the statement "The price offered by e-commerce companies is comparatively less than offline retailers (3.17)" is considered to be the significant statement under price and payment method factor which attracts the consumer to prefer e-commerce companies
- d) **Respondents' Opinion towards Search Engine Optimization (SEO) of Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is clearly learnt that the maritime educational institutions' search engine optimization does not support the students to search for colleges and universities offering maritime courses. Based on the mean value, the statement "It enhances the choice and preferences towards college (3.59)" is considered to be the significant statement that insists the students to use search engine optimization to view the colleges or universities offering maritime education.
- e) **Respondents' Opinion towards Social Media Marketing (SMM) of Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is apparent that the maritime educational institutions offer clarity and eye catching information about their colleges or universities by

keeping in mind of all range of students through social media marketing. Based on the mean value, the statement “It covers all levels of the audience to read and view the information about the college/university (4.11)” is considered to be the significant statement that forces the students to view the social media marketing presented by maritime educational institutions.

- f) Respondents’ Opinion towards Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) of Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is inferred that the maritime educational institutions’ Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) is not that much effective and is not supported them to enhance their viewers. Based on the mean value, the statement “The landing page content is a natural extension of the advertisement copy shown in the network page (3.32)” is considered to be the significant statement that makes the Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) as an effective one.
- g) Respondents’ Opinion towards E-mail Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is obvious that the e-mail marketing supports in a moderate way for maritime colleges or university so as to make the students to enroll in maritime courses. Based on the mean value, the statement “It gives updated information about the college and its available seats for courses (3.48)” is considered to be the significant statement that forces the students to admit in maritime colleges or university.
- h) Respondents’ Opinion towards Instant Message Marketing (IMM) of Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is inferred that the educational institutions is not providing in a better way the information about their maritime courses, fees structure and other facilities through Instant Message Marketing (IMM). Based on the mean value, the statement “The design of the message targets the right audience (2.95)” is considered to be the significant statement which insists the students to read messages send by maritime colleges and university.
- i) Respondents’ Behavior towards Affiliate and Influencer Marketing of Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is understood that the maritime educational institutions does not concentrate on the Affiliate and Influencer Marketing in promoting their colleges or university. Based on the mean value, the statement “It drives traffic to the college link (2.92)” is considered to be the significant statement that attracts the students to watch the advertisement made through affiliated or influencer marketing by maritime educational institutions.

j) Respondents' Behavior towards Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education: It is understood that the students have fair preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. Based on the mean value, the statement "I like to do challenging tasks by working off-shore (3.74)" is considered to be the significant statement that forces the students to prefer and decide upon maritime education.

5.1.3 Significant Difference between Students' Socio-Economic Variables and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions [Independent Sample T-test and One way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)]

a) Respondents' Gender and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions: It is found that there is a significant difference between respondents' gender and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, it is identified that the male respondents have better opinion than female respondents with respect to seven digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

b) Respondents' Age and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions: It is found that except content marketing, search engine marketing and instant message marketing there is a direct relationship between respondents' age and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions i.e., the respondents in the age group of 21 years and 22 years have higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and the respondents in the age group of 24 years have lower level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

c) Respondents' University and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions: It is found that there is a significant difference between respondents' university and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, it is identified that the respondents pursuing their maritime education in private university have higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions than the respondents pursuing in central university. The respondents pursuing their maritime education in private

university have fair level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

- d) Respondent Parents' Occupational Status and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is found that there is a significant difference between respondent parents' occupational status and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, it is identified that the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of business sand professionals have higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions than the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of government employee. The occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of private employee and agriculturist are having moderate level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.
- e) Respondent Parents' Monthly Income and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is found that there is no significant difference between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, it is identified that the monthly income of respondent parents' at all ranges has moderate level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.
- f) Respondents' Awareness about Maritime Educational Institutions and their Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is found that there is a significant difference between respondents' awareness about maritime educational institutions and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. Based on Duncan Multiple Range test, it is identified that the respondents who are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing and advertisement through newspapers have higher level of opinion towards digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions than the respondents who are aware of the same from experts of education fair. The respondents who are aware of maritime educational institutions through advertisement in television channels and from their friends and relatives have medium level of opinion towards digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions.

5.1.4 Significant Association between Students' Socio-Economic Variables and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education(Chi-Square Test)

- a) **Respondents' Gender and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between respondents' gender and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. Moreover, it is identified that male respondents are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the female respondents.
- b) **Respondents' Age and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between respondents' age and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. In addition, it is understood that the respondents in the age group of 21 years are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondents in the age group of 24 years.
- c) **Respondents' University and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between respondents' university and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. Furthermore, it is evident that the respondents pursuing their maritime education in private university are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondents who are pursuing their maritime education in central university.
- d) **Respondent Parents' Occupational Status and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between respondent parents' occupational status and their n their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. Moreover, it is learnt that the respondent parents' occupation under the category of professionals are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondent parents' who are private employee.
- e) **Respondent Parents' Monthly Income and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. In addition, it is proven that the respondent parents' who are earning monthly income between Rs. 70,001 and Rs. 90,000 are superior in their

opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondent parents' earning monthly income of up to 30,000.

- f) Respondents' Awareness and their Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between respondents' awareness and their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education. It is found that the respondents who are aware of maritime educational institution based on digital marketing are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondents who are aware of the same from experts of educational fair by the colleges or university.

5.1.5 Association between Students' Socio-Economic Variables and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education(Correspondence Analysis)

- a) Respondents' age and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between respondents' age and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. It is also identified that the students who are in the age of 21 years have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.
- b) Respondents' University and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between respondents' university and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. It is also clearly learnt that the students who pursue their maritime education in central university have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.
- c) Occupational Status of Respondent Parents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between occupational status of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. It is also understood that the students' parents who are government employee have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.
- d) Monthly Income of Respondent Parents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between monthly income of respondent parents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. It is also evident that the students'

parent who are earning above Rs.90,000 have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

- e) **Awareness of Respondents and their Preferences and Decision Making to Pursue Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant association between awareness of respondents and their preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education. It is also revealed that the students who are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing and advertisement in news papers have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education.

5.1.6 Significant Relationship between Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education and Student's Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education(Bivariate Correlation)

It is identified from the correlation analysis that there is a strong and positive relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education. This implies if the level of effectiveness of online maritime education increases; the student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education also increases

5.1.7 Significant Influence of Digital Marketing Strategies on Students' Preferences and Decision to Pursue Maritime Education (Multiple Regression)

It is revealed from regression analysis that 98.6% of the observed variability in students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education can be significantly explained by their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions namely Content Marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Social Media Marketing (SMM), Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC), Email Marketing, Instant Message Marketing and Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing. The linear combination of students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions is significantly related to their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education ($F = 4825.399$ and $P = <0.001$).In addition, it is found that there exists a direct relationship between digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education.

5.1.8 Significant Difference in the Mean Rank of Factors that insist the Students to Pursue Maritime Education and the Digital Marketing Platform Preferred by them to Search for Information Regarding Maritime Educational Institutions (Friedman Test)

- a) **Factors that insist the Students to Pursue Maritime Education:** It is found that there is a significant in the mean rank of factors that insist the students to pursue maritime education. On the basis of mean rank, the major significant factor that insist the students to pursue maritime education is “Higher demand over the globe (1.49)” followed by “To place in a dignified job (2.80)”, “To get high salaried job (3.87)”, “To become a captain of the ship (4.19)”, “To do a challenging job in marine (5.24)”, “To gain marine knowledge (6.33)”, “Interest to do offshore jobs (7.74)” and “Affordable fees structure (8.22)”.
- b) **Digital Marketing Platform Preferred by the Students to Search for Information Regarding Maritime Educational Institutions:** It is found that there a significant difference among the mean ranks of digital marketing platform preferred by the students to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions. On the basis of mean rank, the most significant digital marketing platform preferred by the students to search for information regarding maritime educational institutions is Social Media Marketing (SMM) (1.88) followed by Content Marketing (2.63), Email Marketing (3.94), Instant Message Marketing (4.78), Search Engine Optimization (SEO) (5.82), Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing (6.02) and Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC) (7.63).

5.1.9 Structural Equation Modeling to Estimate the Relationship between Students’ Opinion on Effectiveness of Online Maritime Education during Covid-19 and Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions (IV) and their Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education (DV)

It is found out that the chi-square value for all the factors is 32.455 and the calculated P value is 0.068(greater than 0.05, Hair et al., 1998) which indicates the model is perfectly fit. Here GFI (Goodness of Fit Index = 0.983) value and AGFI (Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index = 0.998) value is greater than 0.9 which represents that it is a good fit model. The calculated CFI (Comparative Fit Index = 0.999) value is close to 1 which means that it is a perfectly fit model and also it is found that RMR (Root Mean Square Residuals = 0.067) and RMSEA (Root Mean

Square Error of Approximation = 0.044) values are less than 0.080 which indicates that it is a perfectly fit model. This fit model has been proven by the research studies namely Mukosa, F., et al., 2022; Nektarios S. Makrydakis, 2021; Ramadhan, A., & Gunarto, M., 2021; Castro Benavides, L.M., et al., 2020; Cordero-Gutiérrez, R., & Lahuerta-Otero, E., 2020; Kusumawati, A., 2019; Aman, K., & Hussin, N., 2018; Kusumawati, A., 2018.

5.2 SUGGESTIONS

5.2.1 Suggestions to Enhance Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions based on their Socio-Economic Status

- a) **Gender:** Based on the Independent Sample T-test and Chi-square test, it is found that there is a direct relationship between respondents' gender and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and effectiveness of online maritime education (Manju, P., & Dr. Kavitha, M., 2021; Alavudeen SS, 2021; Yu, Z., 2021; Ghaleb A. 2021;) i.e., male respondents have better opinion than female respondents with respect to seven digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. This may be due to the fact that male students are excessively dependent on their mobile devices and prefer to use the internet to research topics rather than asking their friends and family for advice. (Sachin Dave, 2015). It is also identified from the personal interview that women are more inclined to use digital media for texting or emails to build relationships and have deeper conversations and men use it for entertainment purpose and to search for other information (Chen, B., et al., 2016; www.firstpost.com, 2016). Hence, it is suggested for the colleges using digital marketing platform to provide information and advertisement in a manner to attract women students and make aware of them regarding maritime courses and scope all over the world.
- b) **Age:** It is clearly evident from the analysis of ANOVA, chi-square and correspondence analysis that there is a direct relationship between respondents' age and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions, effectiveness of online maritime education and their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education (Punpreet Kaur & Dr. Amanpreet 2022; Bajar, J., Gopun, C., 2021; Manju, P., & Dr. Kavitha, M., 2021; Alavudeen SS, 2021; Yu, Z., 2021;) i.e., the students in the age group of 21 years and 22 years have high level

of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions, effectiveness of online maritime education and their preferences and decision towards maritime educational institutions than the students in the age group of 23 years and 24 years. This may be due to the comparatively less usage of digital media by elder students than students in the age group of 21 years and 22 years (McDonough CC, 2016; Shivan Meymo & Kenn Nyström, 2017). Additionally, it is known from the personal interview that the students in the age group of 23 and 24 said that their break period provides them enough time to analyze the value and scope of the college and university by visiting in person and interacting with the senior students and their age mates. Due to Covid-19 pandemic lockdown, the students in the age group of 21 and 22 years do not have a chance to do the same. Therefore, it is advised that the maritime educational institutions' to give equal importance to both traditional and digital marketing platforms in providing the traditional value of the college, its significance and scope through television, radio, newspapers, social media, etc.

- c) **University:** From the ANOVA, chi-square and decision tree analysis, it is significantly proven that there is a direct relationship between respondents' university and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions, effectiveness of online maritime education and their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education (Punpreet Kaur & Dr. Amanpreet 2022; Bajar, J., Gopun, C., 2021; Yu, Z., 2021; Manju, P., & Dr. Kavitha, M., 2021). i.e., the respondents pursuing their maritime education in private university have a higher level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and effectiveness of online education than the students pursuing the same in central university. But, based on the personal interview it is understood that majority of the students prefer to do their maritime education in central university because of its assured career opportunities and very less tuition fees (Sakunth Kumar, 2019; leverageedu.com, 2019). Therefore, it is recommended for the private colleges and universities to make aware of the students and parents regarding their affordable tuition fees and available career opportunities in the digital marketing platform.
- d) **Occupational Status:** Based on the ANOVA, chi-square and correspondence analysis, it is inferred that there is a direct relationship between respondent parents'

occupational status and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions, effectiveness of online maritime education and their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education (Alavudeen SS, 2021; Yu, Z., 2021; Ghaleb A. 2021; Pappas et al., 2017; Naresha , B., 2016; Rodrigues, A. P., 2017; Tamtekin Aydın, O., & Bayır, F., 2016) i.e., the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of business and profession have high level of opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and effectiveness of online maritime education than the occupational status of the respondents' parent under the category of government employee. On the other hand, the occupational statuses of the respondents' parent under the category of government employee have high level of preferences towards maritime education than the private employee and agriculturist. This is because government employee may have the eligibility and quota to get admission of their son/daughter in central university which may not possible for the private employee and others. They get their children enrolled in central university without taking much risk and they does not depend on private university and colleges' digital marketing to search for information offering maritime courses. Furthermore, businesspeople and professionals may have the financial means to enroll their son/daughter in private universities and colleges and pay significant tuition to receive a quality education. Hence, it is suggested for the private universities and colleges to offer true and correct information about the maritime courses portraying that are worthier than central university by targeting the students' parents in the position of agriculturist, private employee, business people and professionals.

- e) **Monthly Income of respondent parents:** The analysis of ANOVA test clearly depicted that there is no relationship between respondent parents' monthly income and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions. This is due to the fact that everyone in today's society uses digital marketing for a variety of objectives irrespective of their income level. Based on the chi-square test, it is proven that the students' parent who are earning monthly income between Rs. 70,001 and Rs. 90,000 are superior in their opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education than the respondent parents' earning monthly income of up to 30,000 (Naresha , B., 2016; Md. Islam, A.,2011). This may due to the facilities and ambience provided by the students' parents to their son/daughter during Covid-

19 lockdown which may not be possible for the low income level people. It is obviously known from the correspondence analysis that the students' parent who are earning above Rs.90,000 have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education than the students' parents who are earning monthly income below Rs. 50,000 (Gopun, C., 2021; Rodrigues, A. P., 2017; Tamtekin Aydın, O., & Bayır, F., 2016). This may be because of their solid financial standing and preference to enroll their kids in private institutions and universities. Consequently, it is suggested for private colleges and universities to tailor the tuition fees closer to central university fees provide ample facilities and make the parents aware of education loan and other financial support provided them for the students from poor financial background.

- f) **Students' awareness regarding maritime educational institutions:** From the analysis of ANOVA, chi-square and correspondence analysis, it is well-known that there is a direct relationship between respondents' awareness of maritime educational institutions and their opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime colleges and universities, effectiveness of online maritime education and their preferences and decision to pursue maritime education (Kusumawati, A., 2019; Constantinides, E., & Marc C. ZinckStagno, 2012) i.e., the students who are aware of maritime educational institutions through digital marketing and advertisement in news papers have high level of preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education than the students aware of the same through friends and family members and by the experts of educational fair. In order to increase parents' knowledge of their colleges and universities, it is advocated that educational institutions employ digital marketing platforms to provide essential information to parents in a clear and practical way that prevents the parents from making a second option to search for the same in newspapers, magazines, etc.

5.2.2 Suggestions for Enhancement of Digital Marketing Strategies Applied by Maritime Educational Institutions

It is clearly inferred from the Bivariate Correlation that there is a strong and positive relationship between effectiveness of online maritime education and student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education. Based on the regression analysis, it is proven that that there is a significant influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision to pursue maritime education. Finally, it is proven

from the Structural Equation Modeling that there is a relationship between the variables namely students' opinion on effectiveness of online maritime education during Covid-19, digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institutions and their preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education. Therefore, it is well-known that if the level of effectiveness of online maritime education increases; the student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education also increases (Darius, P.S.H., et al., 2021; Muthuprasad, T., et al., 2021; Gopal, R., 2021; Selvaraj, A., et al., 2021; Veena. M., et al., 2021; Obeidat, A., et al., 2020). In addition, it is also proven that if the digital marketing strategies applied by maritime educational institution increases; the student's preferences and decision to pursue maritime education also increases (Mukosa, F., et al., 2022; Maity, S., 2022; Dr. Gondane, V., & Pawar, M., 2021; Kumar, V., et al., 2021; Mohit Kumar, et al., 2021; Rajkumar, S.G., et al., 2021; Nektarios S. Makrydakis, 2021; Ramadhan, A., & Gunarto, M., 2021; Castro Benavides, L.M., et al., 2020; Cordero-Gutiérrez, R., & Lahuerta-Otero, E., 2020). Hence, it is suggested for the educational institutions to concentrate more on their digital marketing strategies to provide updated information to the people all over the world in order to find the right choice of education institution by the students and parents. They should concentrate their marketing efforts on the mobile market as it is predicted that 9.3 million individuals will have mobile subscriptions by the end of 2019, with students accounting for the majority of this group between the ages of 18 and 25 (Kusumawati, A., 2019). Mobile marketing is essential for the educational sector since more than two-thirds of these students indicate they prefer to get updates and reminders through mobile message. Hence, it is advised for the educational institutions to provide instant messages regarding available seats, courses, fees structure through instant messages and emails on a daily basis and other detailed information in their web pages and through social media channels in an attractive manner. In order to enhance enrollment rates, they should execute strategies that increase traffic, student engagement, brand awareness and loyalty, and message communication at different phases of the funnel. The demands of every student are different, thus educational institutions must take this into account when developing their digital marketing strategies. As a result, multiple channels for contact and discussion may need to be established up in order to best serve each potential student's needs.

5.3 CONCLUSION

The study of the relationship between digital marketing strategies and students' preferences and decision making process to pursue higher education becomes very significant. Due to Covid-19 pandemic lockdown, it is difficult for the students and parents to get the true and fair information about the colleges and universities offering maritime education. On the other hand, due to lack of personal touch by educational institutions, it is difficult for them to understand the students' behavior regarding their career choices, their ambition and skills in pursuing maritime courses. Moreover, covid-19 pandemic lockdown separated the students and colleges and it is not possible for the students to get the information about the colleges and universities by visiting in person. Thus, people from all over the world depend on digital media platform namely social media, search engine optimization, email, instant messaging, affiliate marketing and more to get information and facilities offered by colleges and universities. The digital marketing techniques of educational institution create and share the required level of information with the students.

The majority of internet users only look at the first three pages of search engine results when looking for the information they need, thus maritime educational institutions need to keep this in mind. In order to appear their websites consistently in the top three pages of search engine results, these institutions must employ the appropriate keywords, key phrases and make use of optimization techniques. Additionally, maritime educational institutions must ensure that the information they provide for potential students is compelling and pertinent. It is also advisable for the educational institution to share their college or university information through social media in the form of pictures as well as videos that insist even the illiterate to view and understand the value and goodwill of their college and university. The content they create via content marketing can directly influence the prospective students. In addition, direct communication via online technology can also be used with digital marketing to maintain a dialogue with the target audience

The study concluded that there is a significant impact of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision making to pursue maritime education in Chennai. The study found that, in comparison to traditional marketing, digital marketing makes it possible for educational institutions to connect with potential students and parents, leading to higher conversion rates. This is because of its low cost, immediate

feedback, easily accessible tools, and wider market globally. It provides the avenues for the prospective students to search for information through online, provide alarm through their effective advertisement for the students who frequently use the mobile phones and internet to get information, possible comparison of various colleges, user-friendly applications attracted many students to prefer and decide on their higher education. The study made potential suggestions to maritime educational institutions to enhance their awareness among students and parents, enrollment ratio and goodwill of their colleges and universities.

5.4 SCOPE FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

- a) The study is restricted to influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education in the era of covid-19 pandemic in Chennai city. Therefore, in future there is a scope to extend this research to scenario of maritime enrollment ratio before and after covid-19 pandemic lockdown.
- b) In order to study the students' opinion on digital marketing strategies applied by maritime universities namely central university, private university and colleges under state university, the study has chosen seven digital marketing platform namely Content Marketing, Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Social Media Marketing (SMM), Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC), Email Marketing, Instant Message Marketing and Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing. While extending this research, other digital marketing platform namely marketing analytics, video marketing, audio marketing and virtual reality marketing can also be included.
- c) In order to study the influence of digital marketing strategies on students' preferences and decision making process to pursue maritime education, the study has selected central university, state university and private university offering maritime courses in Chennai. Hence, in future there is a scope to extend the study by including other district, states, entire Tamilnadu and India.
- d) It is also recommended to have a further study by comparing other engineering courses with maritime course with respect to their scope, advantages and career opportunities.

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COVID -19 AND ITS IMPACT ON DIGITAL MARKETING; A STUDY ON CADET`S DECISION MAKING PROCESS IN MARITIME EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Questionnaire

A. Socio-Economic Status of the Students

- a. Name of the Respondent (Optional)*: _____
- b. Gender : a) Male () b) Female ()
- c. Age : a) 21 years () b) 22 years ()
c) 23 years () d) 24 years ()
- : a) Central University ()
b) Private University ()
c) State University ()
- d. Parents' Occupation : a) Private Employee ()
b) Government Employee ()
c) Business () d) Professional ()
e) Agriculturist ()
- e. Monthly income : a) Up to Rs.30, 000 ()
b) Rs.30, 001- Rs.50, 000 ()
c) Rs.50, 001- Rs. 70,000 ()
d) Rs.70, 001- Rs.90,000 ()
e) Rs.91, 000 and above ()

1.7 How do you aware of Maritime Educational Institutions?

- a) Friends & Family Members () b) Advertisement in Newspapers ()
c) Advertisement in TV Channels () d) Digital Marketing ()
e) Experts of Education Fair ()

1.8 What factors insist you to pursue Maritime Education?

Sl. No.	Factors	Rank
1.	To gain marine knowledge	
2.	To place in a dignified job	
3.	To get high salaried job	

4.	To become a captain of the ship	
5.	To do a challenging job in marine	
6.	Higher demand over the globe	
7.	Interest to do offshore jobs	
8.	Affordable fees structure	

1.9 What is your preferred Digital Marketing Platform to search for information regarding Maritime Educational Institutions?

Sl. No.	Digital Marketing Platforms	Rank
1.	Content Marketing	
2.	Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	
3.	Social Media Marketing (SMM)	
4.	Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)	
5.	Email Marketing	
6.	Instant Message Marketing	
7.	Affiliate Marketing/Influencer Marketing	

B. Effectiveness of Online Marine Education during Covid-19

Sl. No.	Statements	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1.	Use of PowerPoint presentation.					
2.	Clarity in explaining the subject.					
3.	Good communication skills of faculty members.					
4.	Explanation of content through videos and practical examples.					
5.	Provision of understandable study materials.					
6.	Effective doubt clearing classes.					
7.	Using excel and other innovative technology for mathematics.					
8.	Provision of MCQ through Google forms and other applications.					

9.	Provision of user friendly virtual classroom software.					
10.	Continuous assessment based on online tests, assignments etc.					
11.	Timely completion of lessons.					
12.	Continuous and uninterrupted sessions.					
13.	Transparency and precise maintenance of attendance.					
14.	Strict monitoring of students during class hours and tests.					
15.	Updation of progress report to parents.					

C. Students' Opinion on Digital Marketing Strategies of Maritime Educational Institutions

Sl. No.	Statements	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
I.	Content Marketing					
1.	It provides clear and precise information about the college/university.					
2.	The language used for content is easily understandable.					
3.	The presentation of content attracts and creates curiosity to know about the college/university.					
4.	The content provided enhances the value and goodwill of the college/university.					
5.	It covers the entire and needed information about the college/university in a simplified manner.					
6.	The channel used for content marketing is easily accessible by a wide range of people.					
II.	Search Engine Optimization (SEO)					
1.	It grabs the attention of people.					
2.	It generates qualified traffic to the college/university website.					
3.	It increases the awareness about the college/university.					
4.	It enhances the choice and preferences towards college/university.					

5.	It creates high value among the people about the college/university.					
III.	Social Media Marketing (SMM)					
1.	The platform chosen for SMM is highly effective.					
2.	The design and graphics used for PPC is highly good-looking.					
3.	The blogs and messages posted in SM about the college/university are eye-catching.					
4.	It covers all levels of the audience to read and view the information about the college/university.					
5.	It gives relevant and complete information about the college/university.					
6.	The promotional messages are fair enough to create trust among the audience towards the college/university.					
IV.	Pay-Per-Click Marketing (PPC)					
1.	The advertisement format used for PPC is appreciable.					
2.	The advertisement network applied for PPC is accessible by a wide range of audience.					
3.	The college/university made the finest decision possible while selecting the PCC platform.					
4.	It insists the audience to click and get into the advertisement.					
5.	The keywords used for advertisement create curiosity among the audience to know more about the college/university.					
6.	The landing page content is a natural extension of the ad copy shown in the network page.					
V.	Email Marketing					
1.	The content about the college/university given in email is provided in a simple language.					
2.	The compelling subject lines of email marketing forces the audience to open the message.					
3.	The regular e-mail postage leaves an impression on the audience about the college/university.					

4.	It gives updated information about the college/university and its available seats for courses.					
5.	The email design is simple, narrow and impactful.					
VI.	Instant Message Marketing (IMM)					
1.	Reliable content is posted in IMM.					
2.	The design of the message targets the right audience.					
3.	The content used is highly appealing.					
4.	It contains all of the necessary information in a single paragraph.					
5.	The time slot selected for message posting boosts college/university preferences.					
VII.	Affiliate and Influencer Marketing					
1.	It drives traffic to the college/university link.					
2.	It gives comprehensible information about the college/university.					
3.	It enhances the quality of college/university by offering valid content in a precise manner.					
4.	The presentation and communication of information about the college/university reaches all levels of audience.					
5.	Outstanding performance by an influencer who promotes the college/university.					
6.	Targeted audience is covered by the platform and niche selected for affiliate marketing.					

D. Student's Preferences and Decision Making Process to Pursue Maritime Education

Sl. No.	Statements	Strongly agree (5)	Agree (4)	Neutral (3)	Disagree (2)	Strongly Disagree (1)
1.	I have chosen this course to travel all over the world by sea.					
2.	I pursue this course to learn about the world's unique facts and qualities.					

3.	I am curious to know and expand my knowledge in maritime education.					
4.	My decision to pursue this course is due to wider job opportunities all over the globe.					
5.	I joined this course to get a dignified job.					
6.	My choice towards the course is to earn a high salary.					
7.	I like to do challenging tasks by working offshore.					
8.	My choice of career is to be adventurous and interesting.					
9.	To gain practical and technical knowledge rather than studying theoretically.					
10.	My ambition to pursue this course is to become a captain of the ship.					
11.	The fee structure to pursue this course is reasonable and affordable.					
12.	Effective and attractive infrastructure and facilities offered by college/university insist me to prefer maritime education.					
13.	The explanation given by faculty members creates confidence and trust to prefer this course.					
14.	The placement details and assurance given by college/university forces me to make a decision regarding this course.					
15.	I like to do a job by interacting with nature.					

E. Give your valuable suggestions to improve the digital marketing strategies of maritime educational institutions

*****Thank you for spending your valuable time in filling the questionnaire. Your data is kept confidential*****

Direct to Consumer using Livestream as an Innovative Marketing Medium during COVID-19

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Subject Area: Business Management.

Type of the Paper: Conceptual Research Analysis.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E|](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6085277>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJAEML](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Rajasekar, D., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Direct to Consumer using Livestream as an Innovative Marketing Medium during COVID-19. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 6(1), 77-86.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6085277>

International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI : <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJAEML.2581.7000.0121>

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *Owing to COVID, when many of the physical retail areas were closed and customers were inside, brands were always considering inventive ways to associate with the customers. The accessibility of customers to sellers remained. The live stream was an awesome way to access customers and multiply engagement.*

Design/Methodology/Application: *Establishing a conceptual notion based on model development using the emphasis group - learning method and model analysis using the ABCD listing methodology.*

Findings/Result: *The analyst has recognized that engagement must not be restricted to buyers alone. Livestream is an amazing stage to lock in accomplices as well as internal employees within the company. Livestreaming is long-term of retail and e-commerce. The coronavirus pandemic devastated almost all sectors of the business.*

Research limitations/implications: *Businesses across the country and across the world experienced their supplies, business relations adversely hampered. The demand for most of the products and services reduced to a great extent. The business interruption insurance policy can come to the rescue but unfortunately, if a particular business is not listed on, the policy is not covered. It becomes inevitable to review and reiterate the policies. In many places, in almost all sectors, all spheres, all levels, from the rich to the poor, the losses and damages caused by coronavirus havoc are irreparable. No agency or organization ponders over their compensation of them.*

Originality/New knowledge/Interpretation/Value: *The objective of this paper is to exhibit the most recent patterns and upgrades in live streaming. Moreover, the feasibility of utilizing Livestream as an integrated marketing communication channel is explained.*

Paper Type: *Conceptual research*

Keywords: Marketing and Communication Channel, Direct to consumers, live stream, Covid-19, ABCD Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION :

Ecommerce live streaming digitally gives the consumers the closest shopping experience that a consumer finds in a physical store. Just like how meetings have gotten virtual via Zoom, Livestream is the newest and most interactive way for brands to interact with stakeholders. With the speedy growth of digital channels and social media and consumers spending more and more time on social media, brands are eagerly looking at new ways to engage with their customers. Livestreaming is a very useful channel to interact with the customers as we can get the maximum attention and full engagement from the customer. The audience can also post their comments live on the Livestream; this further strengthens the communication with the audience and makes it into a dialogue. Advantages of online gushing incorporate the capacity to reach a huge group of onlookers, way better presentation, wealthy substance, numerous stages, and way better interaction with the target showcase. Livestreaming is progressing to be a \$70.5 billion industry by 2021.

Many shoppers prefer Livestream to other digital interactions with brands/ influencers as they feel that there is a more open and transparent interaction possible during a live stream. They get to experience what the brand speakers are talking about and get to see the usage of the product in real-time and understand the benefits. Chen, 2019 [1] put forward that Livestream shopping must give shoppers a

more helpful, intuitive, and engaging shopping involvement, which in turn can progress client fulfillment and shopping purposefully.

However, live streaming is not all about communicating with consumers. It could be used to communicate with partners (downstream, upstream, or B2B customers). Furthermore, it can be used to communicate internally within the organization. This can help reduce the hierarchies in the organization and the geographic restrictions COVID has placed on business travel. Internal livestreams make the workers feel that the administration is in proximity to them, and it creates and makes a feeling of exchange. Moreover, it can be used for Monthly town hall meetings, product launches, and training programs that include external stakeholders as well. Livestreams allow the audience to see more into the organization.

Using a measure of content interactivity and a locus of control communication indicator, a primary study was done to gladden-dissect arbitrary samples of two teleshopping programs (The Fashion Channel and Quality Value Convenience Network) Auter and Moore, 1993 [2]. When it comes to shopping in promenades, there are usually a large number of visitors who spend time simply window shopping or going down the islands to enjoy their shopping experience. In our research, we discovered that similar guests prefer to shop online for any products or services. The study focuses on the other half of active shoppers and tries to figure out what motivates them to purchase online (Sajid Marickar and Rajasekar, 2014 [3]). E-retailers should make their websites more secure and ensure that their products are delivered on time and have a Positive impact of online shopping stations on online shopping Consumer surveys show that incorporating station characteristics makes a significant contribution in online shopping. Additionally, personal morals have a favorable impact on shopping (Javadi et al., 2012 [4]). Relaxed payment, slow shipment, undesirable products, spam or infection, unpleasant emails, and technology issues are all major deterrents to online shopping. Businesses should be wary of comparable main issues that lead to online buying discontent (Katawetawaraks et.al 2011 [5]).

Consumer characteristics and their effects on online shopping intention and behavior have been investigated from a range of angles, and the results of related research have substantially improved online merchandising practice. As a relatively new subject of exploration, there are still several unanswered questions. In this section, we'll look at several exploratory topics and trends that deserve more investigation. In addition, we discuss several explorations design challenges that are relevant to future empirical studies (Zhou et.al 2007 [6]).

While real-world shopping relationships are largely based on face-to-face interactions between customers and salespeople, electronic commerce relationships are largely based on the retailer's Web site. The association between colorful aspects of online shopping and consumer buying taste was investigated in this study (Park, 2011 [7]).

2. LIVE STREAMING PLATFORMS :

Livestreaming stages incorporate Facebook live, YouTube, Periscope, Meerkat, Blab, Streaming Media and Ustream, Twitch, You now, etc.

2.1 Periscope:

Periscope functions as a video-streaming app that permits you to share your information and connect with watchers in real-time. It's moreover one of the viral social systems out nowadays, with a gathering of people of more than 10 million enrolled clients. Rugg and Burroughs (2014) [8] expressed that Periscope is the product of this complicated duality. It could be a stage for citizens to bypass state and corporate control while at the same time enmeshing clients within the exceptional generation forms of the advanced media businesses. Periscope which is possessed by Twitter, encompasses an add-up to 10 million clients and has almost 2 million every day dynamic clients.

- 10 million people have enlisted for Periscope accounts
- Periscope presently has 2 million day by day dynamic users
- Periscope clients observe more than 40 a long time of video each day

2.2 Facebook Live:

In today's promoting world, consumers are on Facebook. From the greatest brand to the nearby ice cream shop, everybody is utilizing the gigantically well-known stage in their social media promoting technique to pick up unused clients and increment brand presentation and customer relations. Video livestreaming is the most recent instrument. Facebook has obtained in it's as of now noteworthy cluster

of showcasing strategies. Facebook has a total number of 1.13 billion dynamic clients daily. Facebook Live remains the most used social media channel for livestream in the Middle East.

2.3 YouTube

From the time when YouTube made its big appearance in 2005, it has revolutionized video gushing as an entire, with web recordings presently more open to a more extensive gathering of people. YouTube as of now has millions of clients with recordings being observed more than billions of times. Furthermore, YouTube has come to numerous groups of onlookers and indeed made a few of its clients into prevalent web stars. It is not astonishing that YouTube is additionally utilized as a compelling computerized showcasing stage, because of its awesome effect on web clients and web-guests.

2.4 Meerkat:

Meerkat is an easy-to-use app, and it could end up being a fantastic storytelling tool for brands. The app has good potential and could communicate from a storytelling perspective. Furthermore, it could be a GREAT publishing tool—for media outlets and brands.

2.5 BLAB:

BLAB is another shape of social media within the showcasing tool kit full of alternatives. It too can be a shape of usable substance that can highlight different viewpoints almost you and your company. Video can break through a greater part of messaging and display the foremost true see of you and your commerce to your audience, whereas it locks your prospects and clients within the handle. BLAB makes this happen with ease.

2.6 Twitch:

Amazon`s Twitch may be a spilling stage that generally shows video diversion live streaming and eSports competitions. Besides gaming, Twitch broadcasts music and imaginative and real-life substance. It`s video recreations, nevertheless, that account for the vast and lion`s share of sees and hours clients pass on Twitch.

- Twitch has over 15 million every day dynamic users
- Twitch has between 2.2 and 3.2 million months to month broadcasters
- Over 1 million individuals observed a single occasion-ELEAGUE`s Counterstrike: Global Offensive Major Grand Final
- Twitch clients spend on normal 44 billion minutes per month observing streams
- In 2018, there have been 9,006.466 channels on Twitch Among all live-streaming stages, Twitch leads the way because it accounts for 72.2% of all hours observed live on the internet.

2.7. Amazon Live:

Amazon is the extreme virtual commercial center for access to buyers. At this point, in case your merchandise is not accessible through Amazon, you are losing on more than 1.5 billion buyers. After the advertisement of your items on Amazon, contributing to Amazon marketing in 2019 is additionally inevitable. During the prime day, this year amazon unveiled the Amazon live app wherein influencers could talk about their favourite products which were on sale on Prime day.

2.8. Instagram Live:

Instagram Live is relatively newer than Facebook or YouTube. It allows Instagram users to integrate Livestream within a story. It also notifies the followers about the Livestream as soon as it starts.

3. CURRENT STATUS BASED ON LITERATURE REVIEW:

Shopping exposures have a big role in a customer's decision to buy something online. Brand and quality exposure are positively connected to online purchase intention, according to Ling et al., (2010) [9]. However, (Thamizhvanan and Xavier, 2013 [10]) do not establish a link between brand and quality exposure and online purchase intent. As a result, previous research has yielded inconsistent results when it comes to whether brand and quality exposure influence online purchase intent. Dhanalakshmi et al., (2017) [11] investigated customer perceptions of online buying. The investigation used 150 repliers as a sample size. The data was gathered in an arbitrary convenience slice fashion by the experimenters. Simple chance analysis and ANOVA (analysis of dissonances) approaches were used to anatomize the data. The experimenters concluded that the consumer's impression of online buying differs from person to person, that perception is limited to a degree by the lack of sufficient connectivity and that exposure to online shopping needs to be improved to satisfy the client.

4. OBJECTIVES :

The survey was treated as qualitative research compounding both literature review and empirical research.

- To understand more about the Livestream tools available.
- To structure a framework to understand the benefits and limitations of Livestream.
- A brief overview about the global progress of Livestream
- To effectively plan and conduct a Livestream
- To investigate diverse regions that a Livestream can be utilized to advance a brand/organization
- To decide why a Livestream is required for a brand

5. CHARACTERISTICS AND FRAMEWORK :

Before the Event – Planning, and Execution, producing a live stream takes big efforts. It all starts with the script, rehearsals, and excellent coordination between the organizing teams as well. One should always plan a Livestream event with the least tech-savvy customers in mind. The login procedure and internet speeds of users also need to be considered before conducting an event. The technical elements need to be in sync to share the video live in real-time on the internet. Wongkitrungrueng and Dehouche (2020) [12] specified that live streaming has as of late gotten to be a well-known coordinate offering channel, which offers little, self-employed vendors concealed levels of customer interaction and engagement, whereas the degree of the investigation centered on customer inspiration and deliberations to shop using live gushing, less is known from seller`s point of view. Livestream helps promote authenticity- build trust in the brand; resonance – real engagement; bigger reach – wider approach. A few advantages of online spilling incorporate the estimate of the group of onlookers, superior introduction, wealthy substance, different stages, and way better interaction with the aimed market.

Fig. 1: Positives and Negatives of Live Stream- Source: Analysis prepared by Researcher

6. LIVESTREAM GLOBALLY :

Livestream market size is multiplying year on year. The Livestream concept was developed in 1990; however, it gathered steam post-2010 alongside social media channels. YouTube has also played a pivotal role in the rise of live streaming which is added as a feature on YouTube in 2011. The first live streaming service was launched in 2015 by Twitter called Periscope. From there on Facebook and Instagram introduced live streaming in 2016. MA Gilbert announced that Portable video could be an especially promising stage to communicate to buyers; 80% of Web activity will be video by 2019 and 74% of buyers are more likely to purchase an item or benefit after observing a branded video. One of the most developed Livestream markets globally is China. The Livestream market has grown 98% to \$125 billion in 2020 from \$63 billion in 2019. In the US, it is estimated to be a \$5 billion market in 2020.

7. OVERVIEW OF LIVESTREAMING APPS :

Steps to Perfecting the live stream

Good video quality and showing the product from all angles. If live-streaming is in the Middle East, always include Arabic subtitles in case the show is in English and vice versa. Influencers can be invited to the Livestream as a host or to review different products. Tien et al., (2020) [13] expressed that a computerized promoting procedure may be an arrangement of activities that offer assistance to supervisors accomplish their company’s objectives through carefully chosen online promoting channels. These channels incorporate paid, earned and claimed media, and all of them can back promoting plans around a particular commerce line.

8. STREAMLINE ORGANIZATION PLANNING TIMELINES & PROCESS :

Svart (2018) [14] found that live streaming also gives a plausibility to communicate, both existing and potential future clients, in an advanced environment. It is additionally utilized in internal communication to keep representatives educated straightforwardly and move forward mental dynamics. In addition, live spilling made it conceivable to advance items and services and help the company to upgrade and shine its brand.

Determine

- Objective
- Streaming Type
- Audience
- Set a Date

Timeline - Different Areas to use Livestream

Fig. 2: Planning for Live Stream- Source: Analysis prepared by Researchers

Computerized transformation in sports broadcasting has changed viewer’s insight and brought the live streaming of sports to our living rooms and portable phones. Computerized media, and in an expansive portion, social media have had an enormous part to play in the execution of advanced promoting procedures for an athletic event as detailed by (Bagchi, 2016 [15]).

Fig. 3: Live Stream Communication Plan Internal and External - Source: Analysis prepared by Researchers

Corporate Communication- > Integrated Marketing Channels; Communication-> Channels
 When more and more companies are working from home and looking at remote working options, Livestream is a great way to keep the team connected with management.

During Livestream, customer engagement must be considered as a serious parameter. Questions and answers on the chat boxes and the presenter admit the questions of the audience and answer them in real-time.

In terms of engaging the partners, the customers can put a face to the brand. It is great to promote internal talent to be the face of the Livestream. It makes helps make better brand loyalty. It also allows listening to feedback from partners and consumers. It is also a good playground to try out new ideas and get feedback from customers. Zhang et al., (2020) [16] investigated that E-retailers are grasping unused advanced promoting procedures to supply more true data to their clients. This probe analyses the effect of live video spilling (LVS), characterized as broadcasts in genuine time to the viewers over the Web for business –to–consumer and business –to –business communication.

9. LIVESTREAM METRICS :

Livestreaming assistance (e.g., Facebook Live), whereby video is broadcast in genuine time, has been embraced by numerous dealers as a direct selling apparatus. Drawing on writing in retailing, selection behavior, and electronic commerce, this paper proposes a comprehensive system to test the connections among the customers estimated value of live gushing, client’s credibility, and engagement said by (Sang., 2020) [17].

9.1. Average Minute Audience:

A total number of minutes watched by the audiences live and within 24 hours divided by the number of minutes that the event was broadcast. This rating is similar to the TRP rating in Television Broadcasting.

9.2. Live to On-Demand ratio:

Percentage of audiences who watched the event live vs. the number of audiences who watched it on-demand after the event.

9.3. Viewer Demographics:

Right from the devices used by consumers to watch livestreams to their location, this information is pivotal to understanding home the consumers are consuming data. The bit rate or the transmission speed is also another important metric that needs to be understood prior to the Livestream planning.

9.4. Social Media Sharing:

The pre and post Livestream social media talk metrics need to be analyzed. It is important to track how consumers are sharing invites and feedback through social media posts, messages, and Mobile messenger communication.

9.5. Viewers Online:

This is one of the most important metrics to understand how many audiences are watching the stream at the current moment. This number is visible to audiences as well as the hosts during the Livestream event.

10. IDENTIFYING THE OBJECTIVE OF LIVESTREAM :

With the popularity of live streaming skyrocketing around the world, various live streaming solutions have emerged, ensuring that material is delivered with convenience and quality. Brands, marketers, organizations, content creators, and even educational institutions are jumping on the bandwagon to expand and reach a wider audience. This is owing to the advantages that these live streaming apps bring, such as social network integration, preset content, good quality, a large audience, and the ability to add creativity to live streams.

Fig. 4: Summary of Live Stream Objectives - Source: Analysis prepared by Researchers.

11. ANALYSIS OF LIVESTREAM MODEL USING ABCD STAKEHOLDERS FRAMEWORK :

The ABCD Framework is a popular way to research different business models and to see how good they are at providing value to stakeholders and ensuring long-term profitability through multiple profit generations. ABCD stands for advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages, with A denoting advantages, B denoting benefits, C denoting constraints, and D denoting disadvantages.

The fashion devised by Aithal et.al. (2015) [18], whose operation results in a structured matrix format with an ordered study of functional advantages, benefits, restrictions, and downsides. The entire analysis is further broken down into different issues/focus areas and different functional aspects that affect the function. By linking their critical rudiments, the generality can be explored and analyzed beneath each item.

This basic analytical method provides extremely useful recommendations for identifying and evaluating the applicability and efficacy of any new business models or generalizations produced. The generality, system, strategy, technology, model, and idea are further investigated in the Qualitative Analysis Using ABCD frame by linking indigenous critical components.

The appropriate score weightage is given to each element critical factor under each construct in the quantitative analysis using the ABCD frame, the total score is calculated for each construct through empirical disquisition, and the generality, idea, system, technology, and strategy can be accepted or

rejected by assessing the scores. As a result, the ABCD analysis frame may be utilized as a disquisition tool in various fields, and it is a simple yet consistent analyzing style for business models, systems, generalities, ideas, technology, and strategy analysis (Shenoy et al., 2017) [19].

11. CONCLUSION :

Live streaming, the fastest growing industry, with comparatively small investment helps you to ambit a much broader audience. When you relate with your viewers on a personal level, you make a reliable connection with them. You won't be able to produce this kind of relationship with your viewers through any other content. Thus, live streaming is very important. Brands have come into a juncture wherein they should be adopting Omni channel experiences, or they should partner with an agency that provides Omni channel experiences.

The objective of this finding is to test the part of live spilling in promoting communications and corporate branding in Finnish B2B and B2C companies. Despite the findings on unused computerized marketing communications strategies are rising there's a precise requirement for a superior understanding of the subject. Particularly recordings and live spilling within the content marketing context need legitimate investigation expressed by (Keinanen, 2017) [20]. Livestream is the most effective when the target consumers are a young audience.

12. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE POSSIBILITIES :

The overview is unequivocally related to advanced showcasing communications and doesn't cover offline showcasing communications. Delimitation hasn't been made with the nature of the market or the kind of the industry. Since live spilling is a comparatively unused showcasing communications channel for companies, and additional strict delimitations would have blocked the large survey.

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Digital Marketing Strategy in Admitting New Students during COVID 19 in Maritime Educational Institutions-An Empirical Study

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Area/Section: Education Management.

Type of the Paper: Applied Research.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E](#) guidance.

Indexed in: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7153490>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJMITS](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Rajasekar, D., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Digital Marketing Strategy in Admitting New Students during COVID 19 in Maritime Educational Institutions-An Empirical Study. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMITS)*, 7(2), 341-346. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7153490>

International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMITS)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

CrossRef DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJMITS.2581.6012.0224>

Received on: 15/09/2022

Published on: 06/10/2022

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Digital Marketing Strategy in Admitting New Students during COVID 19 in Maritime Educational Institutions- An Empirical Study

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The goal of this study is to determine how digital marketing affected student enrollment at maritime educational institutions in the year COVID 19.*

Design/Methodology/approach: *Students at Chennai's marine educational institutions made up the target demographic. Data gathered from 96 students using an electronic questionnaire.*

Findings: *Results showed that digital marketing is positively related to students' admission to the business administration degree.*

Practical Implications: *This study has specific implications for colleges that will help them create a digital marketing strategy to help them admit more students to their business administration programmes during COVID 19. In order to make it easier for students to enroll in maritime education, it offers advice for maritime educational institutions on how to execute digital marketing extremely efficiently.*

Originality/Value: *This paper makes a significant literary addition to the field of digital marketing. It is distinctive in that it incorporates the use of various marketing techniques with pupils, strengthening the maritime education in the process.*

Type of Paper: *Case Study & Analysis.*

Keywords: Digital marketing, Student satisfaction, Maritime education, University reputation

1. INTRODUCTION :

In this pandemic circumstance, educational institutions choose digital online work and study since the nations cannot afford any form of disaster or loss. For reasons of health and safety at these critical periods, digital platforms and mediums were the ideal choices for carrying out the normal task. Worldwide, digital marketing has been incredibly significant. Recently, the majority of workplaces across the world underwent a digital transition. Maintaining distance when working in such a setting has become extremely crucial with the advent of the term "social distance."

In order to work more conveniently and support employees who work from home, many businesses and educational institutions have shifted to digital platforms and applications like Zoom, Google Meet, and MS Team (Reem Zaheer Khan and Haque Nawaz, 2021 [1]). The education sector is currently recovering from the blow they sustained at the start of the pandemic. Private higher education institutions faced a significant challenge in determining whether they were ready to take on this new role in pandemic education. Everyone has a high opinion of public institutions due to their reputation for superior technology and effective digital marketing management (Vicente-Ramos and Cano-Torres, 2022 [2]). Research on digital marketing has been done by a sizable number of researchers. One of them is (Yuliana, 2000 [3]), who examines the impact of social media on seller-to-seller sales competition. This study intends to provide answers to the concerns of how each institution has handled its marketing initiatives, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, what challenges they have when implementing digital marketing, and how they attract students after doing so. This research has significantly advanced the marketing discipline in universities, particularly in the area of digital marketing (Prihadini et.al 2020 [4]).

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

Sanjoy Kumar Paul et al., (2021) [5] conducted a study on For the dynamic situation, a realistic system with time-dependent and dynamic demand, supply, and warehouse capacity is developed for investigating the impacts of the COVID-19 outbreak. This system makes use of a number of strategies, including working with emergency suppliers, expanding warehouse capacity, and taking back-orders and lost sales into account to form recovery strategies. Additionally, Munarsih et al. (2021) [6] examined a different study that focused on a promotion strategy for the admission of new students through digital marketing during the COVID 19 pandemic and presented new findings on the topic. This strategy was carried out during the pandemic and involved digital marketing. Many people had easy access to it, including through websites, YouTube video commercials, and social media.

Data were gathered using the snowball sampling approach on 930 newly enrolled students during the academic year 2020–21 at numerous colleges in India's western region, according to Bapat et al report (2021) [7]. The results demonstrate a negative correlation between the student's age group and the effectiveness of Internet advertisements for university admission. Surprisingly, the study found that students from rural and urban areas showed equal interest in online advertisements and that family status had no bearing on that receptivity.

Additionally, according to Mishra and Madaan's (2020) [8] study, students' perceptions of the variables influencing the success of digital marketing on university admissions are also important. The findings show that the effectiveness of digital marketing depends on influencing elements such student videos on the website, hashtags, alumni reviews, event pages, mobile marketing, virtual tours, blogs, and use of WhatsApp and Pinterest. In addition to making a contribution to the literature on digital marketing, the study suggests findings that private universities can use to manage their admissions processes. It does this by suggesting a cutting-edge methodology for handling student admission by analysing mutually exclusive indicators pertaining to present and future opportunities for the organisation.

In a different study, Kusumawati (2019) [9] analyses the findings and explores how university marketing management uses digital media because it has become popular among businesses everywhere, including HEIs. Most often, students use social media to research universities before selecting the best one. Given that the communication platform is based on the ideas and experiences of students and other stakeholders, the collaborative and engaging nature of social media presents a chance to balance educational control.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM :

The study would also offer higher education administration ways and techniques for drawing students to the school. The study will offer a cutting-edge digital marketing and communication strategy for higher education in India that makes use of a collective channel model. This study is being conducted for the first time in India because these difficulties and problems have not been thoroughly investigated or analysed, nor has any attempt been made to build a digital marketing model for higher education institutions in the nation (Kumar et al., 2021) [10].

4. NEED OF THE STUDY :

Administrators have the opportunity to identify and analyse social interactions pertinent to their campus through the practise of social listening as social media and online conversations continue to shape public perception of institutions. Strategic objectives like reputation and enrollment management, crisis communication, and audience research and insight can all be supported and informed by social listening on campus. Applying social listening across campus makes it a crucial source of intelligence for enhancing and achieving outcomes, from branding to student engagement to fundraising initiatives. 2017 (Gross & Horn) [11].

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

Studying the concept of digital marketing, analyzing the effect of COVID 19 on digital marketing, and identifying the factors influencing the use of digital marketing to admit new students during COVID 19 are among the study's objectives.

6. RESEARCH TECHNIQUES :

Study location and data collection: Email replies from students enrolled in business administration programmes in marine education were used for the study.

Study type: This investigation is entirely exploratory and conclusive in nature.

Data collection technique: Both primary and secondary data were used in the study. Review of websites, books, and reputable publications made up the secondary sources.

The Questionnaire Development

Initial questionnaire draughts were created through cordial conversations with students. The three elements of the closed-ended questionnaires were then developed and improved. The first section of the questionnaire asked general inquiries about Name, Address, Age, Gender, Income Level, and Marital Status. The second section presented questions pertaining to digital marketing. The final section covered the variables influencing new admission during a pandemic condition using a Likert scale.

Sample Nature

96 respondents (out of 107 respondents) who received structured questionnaires for data collection made up the study's sample.

Sampling Procedure

The respondents were chosen from the designated strata depending on their convenience and cooperation during the sampling process.

Tools for statistics used: Test of Chi-square

Hypothesis testing:

H₁: There is no association between factors influencing digital marketing such as management program with regard to digital marketing Covid 19

H₂: There is no association between factors influencing digital marketing and students pursuing business administration

Period of the Study:

The survey was conducted from June to November 2017.

Limitations of the study

Study was conducted through email and with a sample of 96 respondents only.

Data analysis and Interpretation

Chi-square Test-1

H₁: There is no association between factors influencing digital marketing such as management program with regard to digital marketing and Covid 19

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic significance
Pearson Chi-square	49.703a	72	0.979
Likelihood Ratio	52.265	72	0.961
N of Valid Cases	176		

a. 80 cells (84.2%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 05.

Inference: The null hypothesis is maintained because the calculated value of 0.979 is greater than the p-value of 0.05 in the aforementioned chi-square test. As a result, there is no connection between students talking about management programme concerns with digital marketing and Covid 19.

Chi-square Test-2

H₂: There is no association between factors influencing digital marketing and students pursuing business administration.

Chi-Square Test			
	Value	Df	Asymptotic significance
Pearson Chi-square	3.213 ^a	4	0.523
Likelihood Ratio	3.325	4	0.519
N of Valid Cases	178	-	-

a. 4 cells (40%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 2.39.

Inference: The null hypothesis is maintained because the estimated value of 0.523 is greater than the p-value of 0.05, according to the aforementioned chi-square test. Because of this, there is no connection between variables affecting digital marketing and students pursuing business administration.

7. FINDINGS :

The null hypothesis is accepted for both the elements influencing the digital marketing with reference to COVID 19 and students pursuing business administration, it can be deduced from the aforementioned chi-square test that the computed value of p-value is more than 0.05. The majority of respondents claimed that they could base their admissions decision on information found online. Respondents prefer websites to other digital marketing channels when searching for information. The decision-making process for students choosing to pursue higher education in India is primarily influenced during the stage of option evaluation, which is followed by information search.

8. CONCLUSION :

Higher education's use of digital management tactics draws students who are looking for information about admission and leads to the post-admission process. Students' awareness of the institution is raised, and they are actively involved in communication. According to research, overseas students still favour traditional sources over social media while doing their searches. Friends, family, and university websites ranked best among traditional media sources. Facebook, Instagram, Google+, and YouTube had the top rankings among social media platforms. In fact, the majority of students have used social networking sites to contact a friend or a member of the university staff for information on university courses (Vrontis et al., 2018) [12]. In order to accomplish its goals, including selecting the ideal freshman class each year, HEIs have turned to social media promotional methods. Admissions offices have developed complex recruitment programmes and set aside a sizable budget for digital marketing initiatives to ensure they get it correctly (Osbon, 2019) [13]. This study can be used by online academics to generate future research after the pandemic and to assess how it affected people both during and after the virus spread (Alshaketheep, 2020) [14]. Researchers and professionals in the field of digital marketing [15-16] will also find this study helpful in their understanding of the adoption of social media marketing in educational institutions. Additionally, this study will assist colleges in evaluating the methods for attracting and keeping students in different programmes (Harbi & Ali, 2022) [17].

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Study on Cadet Satisfaction towards E-Marketing Promotion in Private Maritime University (Study with reference to rural cadets, Chennai)

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Area of the Paper: Management.

Type of the Paper: Case Study.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E|](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7269480>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJCSBE](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Rajasekar, D., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Study on Cadet Satisfaction towards E-Marketing Promotion in Private Maritime University (Study with reference to rural cadets, Chennai). *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 6(2), 489-495. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7269480>

International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJCSBE.2581.6942.0212>

Paper Submission: 20/10/2022

Paper Publication: 31/10/2022

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *With the use of marketing strategies, particularly internet marketing, this study seeks to shed light on how rural cadets are growing more concerned with choosing private universities.*

Design/Methodology/approach: *As respondents, 412 rural marine engineering cadets from private maritime universities took part in the survey. This study demonstrates the importance of e-marketing in promoting private maritime colleges to rural cadets of maritime programmes. The significance of the finding was examined using the Descriptive and Chi-Square Analysis. As a result, the current study was limited to students at Chennai's private maritime universities.*

Findings: *The research reveals that online retailers' emails, promotions of their admittance policies, visits to their websites, and encouragement to enrol via email all constitute forms of electronic marketing. Cadets are persuaded to enrol by reading emails supplied by online businesses.*

Practical Implications: *Overall, all respondent groups agreed that more e-marketing should be conducted to gain admission for private marine universities.*

Originality/Value: *The study emphasises that the cadets' distribution of e-marketing appears to be successful; it is seen that for the factor of "email sent by online companies", the cadets recorded the greatest degree of satisfaction for all chosen marketing activities.*

Type of Paper: *Case Study.*

Keywords: E- Marketing, Online Retailers, Private Maritime Universities and Cadets

1. INTRODUCTION :

In order to draw cadets from remote areas, digital marketing efforts like e-marketing have emerged as the most important factor in persuading private maritime institutions to take part in the admissions process. In contrast, cadets are also benefiting from knowing the advantages and technologies of email marketing about universities in depth in order to select the University for the Right Programme [1]. It was also noted in a different study that, with regard to higher education institutions, particularly maritime universities, the competitive advantage not only influences the product or idea but also has a greater impact on real marketing and the use of internet technologies [2]. Additionally, numerous scholars have cited and valued higher education institutions as being comparable to the promotion of corporate identity [3]. The researcher [4] also covered the use of e-marketing for a variety of products, including emails sent by online companies, followed by interest in emails promoting marine engineering programmes from online, regular email visits with online, and influence to make a decision as a result of receiving emails.

The goal of this study is to examine email marketing and the degree of trust that has a big impact on how college students absorb advertisements on websites. Observation, interviewing, and studying the findings of the literature are all approaches for gathering data. Descriptive qualitative analysis is the type of analysis used. Due to the limited network availability in rural areas of different sections of

Chennai, the results revealed a problem in the private maritime universities where many cadets were unaware of email marketing [5].

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

Table 1: Review of literature on related research

S. No.	Area/Focus	Outcome	Reference
1	Website	Reluctant to Buy Things Online due to the Increasing Trend Of Online Frauds And The Websites	George, C. C., & Education, B. E. U. (2010). [6]
2	E-Marketing & Consumer	Important Impact to Reinforce Consumer Buying Behavior	Mullen, J., & Daniels, D. (2011). [7]
3	E-Marketing	Quality of Websites and on the Possibilities of the use of E-Marketing Tools for Marketing Communication	Krombholz, K., Merkl, D., & Weippl, E. (2012). [8]
4	Online University	Online Reputation to Ensure they Maximize all Opportunities to Maintain, and Improve Student Enrolment And Retention	Kuzma, J., Philippe, T. W., Koehler, J. W., & Coronel, R. S. (2016). [9]
5	Linkage between E-marketing and Cadets behaviour	More Studies needed to be Conducted to Examine the Linkage of E-Mail Marketing and Consumer Buying Behavior	Waheed, A., & Jianhua, Y. (2018). [10]
6	Strategy of E Marketing	Improve the University Brand Image and Inspire the Interest of Students to Choose the Program	Machmud, R., Saerang, D. P., Soegoto, A. S., & Wenas, R. S. (2018). [11]
7	Internet Marketing or Web Marketing	Dominated Business in the Modern World	Kaushik, R., & Prativindhya, M. (2019). [12]
8	New trends in e-marketing	Strategic and Operational Level in which different techniques ease the Buying Behavior of Consumers	Babalola, H. B., Lateef, S. A., & Zekeri, A. A. (2020). [13]
9	Attract students to Private University	Universities to Determining the Impact of E-Marketing on Attracting Students	Al Assaf, D., Tawfeq, K., Al-Momani, D., & Musa, M. (2020). [14]
10	E-Marketing improvement in higher education institutions	Pay Attention to Websites' Design and Security for Universities and the Services and Information	Al Showa, S. H., & Ghadeer, B. G (2020). [15]

2.1 Summary of the Review of Literature:

In choosing private maritime colleges and programmes for a particular subject of maritime education, private maritime universities must take into account advances in digital technology, including marketing efforts. Search engine optimization, content marketing, influencer marketing, e-marketing, marketing automation, campaign, and e-commerce marketing are just a few of the numerous activities that make up digital marketing. For this study, the four most significant criteria in e-marketing were used to analyse the process for selecting marine programmes at private maritime universities by cadets from remote areas. Additionally, it has been determined from earlier study that the approach taken by colleges to entice admission is highly important and influences the most crucial factors, such as social media marketing and e-marketing. However, when selecting the educational institution for the current study, the researcher took into consideration e-marketing elements.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM :

Due to their poor high school averages, private maritime institutions have seen a decline in enrollment in recent years, and the facilities offered by public maritime universities are on par with those of private maritime universities in terms of marine education. Additionally, private institutions must step up their efforts to use cutting-edge E-Marketing strategies to draw in more students using contemporary technologies [16]. As a result, this study examines the role of website features and e-marketing technology in luring students to maritime private institutions. However, e-marketing technology has a good impact on drawing students to private colleges and could have a negative impact on the institution if not employed properly and scientifically [17]. Therefore, it is crucial for the advancement of maritime education to examine how e-marketing promotes private maritime institutions.

4. NEED OF THE STUDY :

In the current situation, students are using e-marketing more and more frequently. Due to the cadets' decision to enrol in the marine programme during the past few years, e-marketing has experienced enormous development in the Indian market [18]. Private maritime universities must meet the needs of its students due to the large increase in usage, thus they implement innovative e-marketing methodologies to draw in students as compared to other forms of marketing. A university's website appears to be a crucial component of this marketing process, assuming that institutions are a brand of educational marketing [19].

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

To determine the degree to which rural cadets in private maritime institutions are satisfied with the e-marketing promotion offered to them

Research Question:

What aspects of private marine universities do rural cadets consider when making e-mail marketing decisions?

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

Table 2: Research Methodology used in this work

Type of Research	Descriptive Research
Research Design	Survey Method
Questionnaire	Structured Questionnaire-Used to collect the data
Development of Questionnaire	Both Electronic and Printed Format Questionnaire was developed by the researcher and its content were checked by senior academic
Sampling Method	Convenience sampling – Convenient source of data for researchers
Sample Size	Sample of 412 was taken for the study in Chennai
Data Collection	Both Primary and Secondary Data Primary Data – Rural Cadets of Private Maritime University Secondary Data – Journal, Magazines, Websites, Books, Online resources, Blogs etc.
Statistical Tools	Descriptive and Chi-Square Analysis

Hypothesis

H1: To determine whether there is a correlation between e-marketing characteristics and rural cadets at private maritime universities.

Study's drawbacks include:

The study only applies to students attending private colleges who are from rural areas; it does not apply to students attending other universities who are from metropolitan areas.

The sample size is restricted to 412.

Data analysis and Interpretation:

Descriptive Statistics -Mean and Standard Deviation:

Table 3: Factors Influencing the E-Mail Marketing With Regard to Satisfaction of Rural Cadets in Private Maritime University

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Emails from Online Companies	412	4.53	0.719
Interest in Emails Promoting Marine Engineering Programmes from Online	412	4.47	0.883
Regular email with online	412	4.41	0.858
Internet emails can persuade to make a decision.	412	2.19	1.574
Valid N	412		

It may be inferred from Table 1's mean scores for the things that influence e-marketing when rural cadets choose a private maritime university for its marine curriculum. The highest mean score is given to emails sent by online companies (4.53), followed by interest in emails promoting marine engineering programmes from online (4.47), regular email visits with online (4.41), and influence to make a decision as a result of receiving emails (2.19)

Chi-square Test:

Table 4: Association between Factors Influencing the E-Marketing and Rural Cadets of Private Maritime Universities

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1294.599 ^a	1064	0.000**
Likelihood Ratio	790.998	1064	1.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	32.126	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	412		
a. 1131 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.			

** Significant at 1% level

According to Table 2, there is a very significant correlation between rural cadets attending private maritime universities and the elements impacting e-marketing. At a 1% level, the null hypothesis is rejected, as indicated by the Chi-Square value of 0.00. The data reveal a strong correlation between rural cadets of private maritime universities and elements influencing e-marketing.

7. FINDINGS :

Researchers learned from the investigation they conducted that information is a crucial primary resource in e-marketing [20]. Product information quality, online information quality, and service information quality are all included in this information. Because they represent the institution's reputation, it is essential that these three pieces of information be of high quality [21]. According to the analysis's findings, rural cadets at private maritime universities and factors influencing e-marketing are closely related [22].

8. CONCLUSION :

From the aforementioned data analysis, it can be inferred that e-marketing is crucial for promoting private maritime universities and increasing cadet admissions [23]. The hiring of knowledgeable employees in information technology is also crucial [24]. This is also evident from the fact that, with regard to the marine engineering programme, the percentage of cadets admitted to private maritime institutions did not show a decline, but rather experienced considerable growth among those from remote areas.

In addition, private maritime universities have recently begun concentrating more on e-mail marketing to draw applicants from rural areas, and for future research, researchers [25] advice conducting a study

on digital marketing at maritime universities in higher education with a different strategy with regard to applicants from rural as opposed to urban areas for the marine engineering programme.

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Influencing Choice of Private Maritime University: Enrolment factors for cadets at Maritime Educational Institutions using Digital Marketing

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Subject Area: Business Management.

Type of the Paper: Case Study.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [C|O|P|E](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7269504>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJAEML](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Rajasekar, D., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Influencing Choice of Private Maritime University: Enrolment factors for cadets at Maritime Educational Institutions using Digital Marketing. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 6(2), 264-270. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7269504>

International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJAEML.2581.7000.0157>

Received on: 10/10/2022

Published on: 31/10/2022

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Influencing Choice of Private Maritime University: Enrolment factors for cadets at Maritime Educational Institutions using Digital Marketing

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *This study's goal was to identify the variables that affect cadet's decisions in maritime educational institutions.*

Design/Methodology/approach: *One hundred cadets in the marine engineering programme has participated in the study as respondents. The study made use of the non-probability sample method and the Likert five scale evaluation. The self-administered questionnaire was created following validation by marine engineering experts. For gathering data, the questionnaire was emailed to the cadets. The T-Test was used to ascertain the elements that influenced cadets' university selection.*

Findings: *Most students polled and recommended that friends and family were among the most crucial considerations in determining which university they would attend.*

Practical Implications: *In general, all participant groups concurred that social media, particularly, Instagram, Facebook, and Snapchat, should be used more to raise awareness of university life and programmes.*

Originality/Value: *Higher education admission officers can better serve the demands of their schools by comprehending and utilising data on influencing elements in cadet's decision-making in maritime educational institutions in order to raise enrolments while responding to reducing funds.*

Type of Paper: *Case Study.*

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Admissions, Enrolment management, Cadets and Higher Education

1. INTRODUCTION :

The way Indian students make decisions is evolving. Prior to now, the primary sources of information about university courses have been conventional sources including friends, family, websites, print and broadcast media, and others [1]. To make students competent in their individual marketplaces, competitive pressure has led higher education institutions to look for more aggressive marketing tactics [2]. After applying and receiving admission from several schools, a student must choose which school to enrol in. This decision is affected by a variety of circumstances [3].

Institutions are better able to persuade potential students to enrol at their school when they are aware of the elements that affect a student's decision to enrol. Also identified perceptions of price in the form of the price/quality connection as the most relevant criteria [4]. While recognised academic reputation, cost/time issues, and programme issues as the determinants of university choice [5].

The existing advertising landscape must be completely replaced by internet-based advertising. Even though certain institutions could still host forums, virtual tours, and information sessions, the level of participation varied amongst colleges and universities [6]. However, little study has been done on digital marketing and the expectations of students enrolled in these programmes [7]. Needs Identification, Information Search, Alternative Evaluation, Purchasing Decisions, and Post-Buying Behavior make up the specific decision-making process [8]. To close this educational gap, efforts have

been made to promote maritime education and analyse the worth of undergraduate maritime programmes from the viewpoint of the students, with a focus on digital marketing [9]. There is now a system in place for online student selection [10] to get around this.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

Table 1: Review of literature on related research

S. No.	Area/Focus	Outcome	Reference
1	Higher Education Institutions	Prospective Students have more institutional options in Digital Marketing	Comfort, W. W. (1925). [11]
2	College Choice	College choice and the opportunity to choose which college to attend began to become increasingly common, allowing students to select a specific institution with explicitly desired qualities	Ripperger, H. S. (1933). [12]
3	Social Media	In a different study, the researchers discovered that prospective students have been using the internet to explore universities more frequently during the previous few years	Poock, M. C., & Andrews Bishop, V. (2006). [13]
4	University Website	According to another studies, university websites serve as students' main information source while selecting a college	Martin, S. P. (2006). [14]
5	Attributes	First year university students regarded the availability of the required programme as "the very important attributes" when deciding which higher education institution to attend.	Bin Yusof, M., Binti Ahmad, S. N. B., bin Mohamed Tajudin, M., & Ravindran, R. (2008). [15]
6	Academic Recognition	Students are content with their college selection based on their knowledge satisfaction with regard to academic recognition (external influence).	Ismail, N., Hassan, F. H., & Sheriff, N. M. (2015). [16]
7	Individual Interest	Researchers have discovered over the past ten years that most potential junior and master students visit university websites to find out specific information about the institution they wish to attend	Gregory, S., & Bannister-Tyrell, M. (2017). [17]
8	Strategic Role of Digital Marketing	Show that these universities have social media presences, but that none of them now appears to have a deliberate plan to improve contact with students. Digital marketing, such as social media marketing and mobile marketing, has a significant impact on consumer purchasing decisions.	Kumar, D., Rajyalakshmi, K., & Asadi, S. S. (2017). [18]
9	Instruments of Digital Marketing	Search Engine Optimization (SEO); Search Engine Marketing (SEM); Content Production Techniques;	Matosas-López, L. (2021). [19]

		Emailing Techniques; and Social Network Services	
10	Digital Marketing & Traditional Marketing	In order to support universities' strategic marketing initiatives in the current digital era, it is important to understand which traditional and digital resources students utilise most frequently at the university preference stage and how much these resources influence their preferences.	Ocak, A. (2021). [20]
11	Digital Marketing in Higher Education	Administrators feel that digital marketing, especially for young people getting ready to graduate from high school, has a significant impact on attracting students.	Makrydakias, N. S. (2021). [21]
12	Purchasing Decision	Consumer purchasing decisions are significantly impacted by digital marketing techniques like social media marketing and mobile marketing.	Al-azzam, A. F., & Al-Mizeed, K. (2021). [22]

Summary of the Review of Literature

The literature on the selection criteria for private marine educational institutions that employ digital marketing is included in these areas. Even if the researcher only examines certain literature, this study article summarises the review of the literature and highlights the knowledge gap (Higher Education, College Choice, Academic Recognition, and Digital Marketing connected to it from earlier researchers). The first provide an overview of the factors in relation to maritime educational institutions using digital marketing and also ending section interpreted other factors when choosing maritime educational institutions such as (Digital Marketing, Traditional Marketing, Higher Education and Purchasing Decision). Universities must have a compelling online presence because students today tend to do their research on universities online rather than in person. For a student to make an informed decision about attending a university, they must be able to conveniently obtain information about the university's mission and services online.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM :

Private Maritime University spends a tremendous amount of money each year on enrolment and admissions [23]. Higher education maritime institutions must use their finance wisely to entice potential students in light of the elements that significantly impact private maritime university decisions. Decision-makers can concentrate on the factors that can affect a cadet's decision by being aware of the factors that an institution cannot change.

4. NEED OF THE STUDY :

This study aims to provide light on the factors that influence cadet's choices at maritime educational institutes. Similar studies on cadets can be conducted by maritime educational institutions, and data analysis can be used to develop projects and programmes that help them better understand their incoming cadets and the characteristics they can affect to draw more cadets to their institution.

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

To determine what factors, at maritime educational institutes, affect cadet choice.

Research Question:

What aspects affect a cadet's decision to enrol at Chennai's private maritime university?

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

Table 2: Research methodology used in this work

Type of Research	Descriptive Research
Research Design	Survey Method
Questionnaire	Structured Questionnaire- Specifies the exact wording and order of the questions, for gathering information from cadets
Sampling Method	Convenience sampling – Convenient source of data for researchers
Sample Size	100
Data Collection	Both Primary and Secondary Data Primary Data – Cadets of Private Maritime University Secondary Data – Journal, Magazines, Websites, Books, Online resources, Blogs etc.
Statistical Tools	

Hypothesis:

H₁: To determine the element influencing a cadet's choice at a marine educational facility.

Limitations of the study:

The study is only applicable to colleges of marine engineering, hence it could not be applicable to other universities.

Because there were only 100 responses in the sample, the results are limited.

Data analysis and Interpretation:

Descriptive Statistics -Mean and Standard Deviation:

Table 3: Factors influencing the aspiration of Cadets in selecting the Maritime University

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Social Network	117	4.20	1.026
University Website	117	3.26	0.687
Counsellor Visit	117	3.80	0.712
Reputation of University	117	3.33	0.692
Scholarship/Grant	117	3.16	0.546
Valid N	117		

It is concluded from the table 1 shows the mean scores of items influencing the factors choosing the maritime educational institution by the cadets. The highest mean score is given to social network (4.20) followed by Counsellor Visit (3.80), followed by University Website (3.26), reputation of the university (3.33), and scholarship/grant (3.16).

Chi-square Test:

Table 4: Association between Institutional Influence and Promotional method

Chi-Square Tests			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	76.880 ^a	756	.000
Likelihood Ratio	87.477	756	1.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	1.856	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	117		

a. 812 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .00.

** Significant at 1% level

According to Table 2, there is a strong correlation between Institutional Influence and Promotional Methods. At a 1% level, the null hypothesis is rejected, as indicated by the Chi-Square value of 0.00. According to the investigation, institutional influence and promotional strategy are closely related.

7. FINDINGS :

Notable of the study's findings were consistent with earlier research, but there were also some differences. The variables that the researcher included in the survey instrument served as the sole basis for the analysis and findings of the study. The primary determinant of which maritime educational institutions cadets choose is social media, followed by visits with counsellors, the university website, the school's reputation, and scholarships and grants. Another study [24] discovered that students heavily rely on the internet while choosing a university. The recent study also discovered evidence that the internet and the college website may have an impact on a student's decision to enrol at a specific college.

8. CONCLUSION :

To be competitive and flourish among higher education providers, a higher education institution, like any other marine educational institution, must comprehend its cadets' needs and wants. The students are worried about a variety of things, including location, amenities, and financial aid. A top-tier institution's library is yet another resource in addition to its professors. For students, the pricing schedule, loan options, and scholarship programme are also crucial considerations. The deserving pupils should receive the scholarship. Peers or high school alums played a big role in promoting the university and influencing prospective students' enrollment and application decisions. To have a greater impact on cadet recruitment and enrollment in the marine engineering programme, the office should collaborate more closely with current students to solicit their opinions and suggestions [25-26].

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Channels of Digital Marketing in Maritime Education –A Review on Cadets Decision Making

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Area/Section: Management.

Type of the Paper: Empirical Study.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [|C|O|P|E|](#) guidance.

Indexed in: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7295999>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJMSTS](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Rajasekar, D., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). Channels of Digital Marketing in Maritime Education –A Review on Cadets Decision Making. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMSTS)*, 7(2), 490-496. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7295999>

International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMSTS)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

CrossRef DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJMSTS.2581.6012.0234>

Received on: 18/10/2022

Published on: 05/11/2022

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *With reference to cadets' decision-making on a maritime career, the goal of this research is to identify the digital marketing channels in maritime education.*

Design/Methodology/approach: *The data for the descriptive study was gathered from maritime education cadets attending in private maritime universities. Using a structured questionnaire and the convenience sampling approach, 60 respondents were chosen as the study's sample size.*

Findings: *The results of the empirical investigation show that the target group under study has a high level of awareness regarding digital marketing channels in maritime education.*

Practical Implications: *To be familiar with digital marketing platforms and their profound influence on cadets' decision-making in maritime education.*

Originality/Value: *The impact of cadet decision-making in maritime education utilizing digital marketing has been examined using descriptive and t-test analysis.*

Type of the Paper: Empirical Study.

Keywords: Cadets Decision Making, Digital Marketing, Maritime University and Education.

1. INTRODUCTION :

In India, the growth of digital marketing is still occasionally quite encouraging. She notes that higher education has been in transition for a long time in her article, "Digital Marketing in Higher Education." HEIs around the world encounter difficulties from both the inside and the outside. To meet this challenge, higher education marketing must transition from glossy brochures to social media and the internet. Universities and colleges are getting more picky with their spending and aggressive with their student recruitment efforts [1]. The sustainability of colleges and universities depends on enrollment growth. The difficulty for colleges and universities is to remain relevant to students who are becoming more dependent on technology for communication. According to research, students frequently go to social media after first seeing a website for an institution. That implies that institutionally sponsored social media profiles receive a tremendous amount of daily, round-the-clock traffic [2]. Educational institutions are now making an effort to make their curriculum engaging and in a readily accessible style, in order to attract this specific population, in order to avoid missing out on any prospective income. In higher education, digital marketing is regarded as crucial, especially in light of the strain that the fierce global competition put on HEIs. Government funding for higher education is no longer necessary because of competitive marketplaces. Universities must compete for students in the recruitment markets because higher education has transitioned from being dependent on government funding to a competitive market [3]. As a result, it's critical that institutions comprehend student recruitment strategies and self-promotion techniques.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

Table 1: Literature Review on Channels of Digital Marketing

S. No.	Area/Focus	Outcome	Reference
1	Students' Perceptions	Plays a vital role in their choosing a Particular Institution	Chapman, D. W. (1981). [4]

2	Marketing	Promotion's (marketing's) significance in influencing students' decision to study in PIHEs	Sampson, H. (2004). [5]
3	Services Marketing Mix	These elements can be categorised as "product" and "process" in marketing terms.	Chew, B. H., Zain, A. M., & Hassan, F. (2013). [6]
4	Online Education	Teachers who deliver courses also have difficulties in adapting to online education methods	Erdogan, O., & Demirel, E. (2017). [7]
5	Academic education	Dilemmas for Curriculum Development, for Training Legislation in a Global Industry	Manuel, M. E. (2017). [8]
6	Social Media	Improve the Learning Outcomes of Cadets	Trust, T. (2017). [9]
7	Cadet Satisfaction	understand student use and satisfaction with clickers in a large undergraduate digital marketing	Rana, N. & Dwivedi, Y. (2018). [10]
8	Admission And Enrollment	Digital initiatives in terms of during admission and enrollment, course delivery for teaching and learning, skill development, etc	Suhasini, B., & Kumar, N. S. (2018). [11]
9	Covid-19 pandemic	Excellent Opportunity to Shift to Real and Honest Marketing that can Actually Tackle Urgent Environmental and Social Challenges	Alshaketheep, K. M. et al. (2020). [12]
10	Private University	Number of Students Enrolling in Private University with Professional Digital Marketing	Prihadini, D., et al. (2020). [13]
11	Learning Proces	Does not require Face to-Face Interaction between Lecturers and Students but Utilizes Internet Networks	Astriawati, N., & Pratama, H. A. (2021). [14]
12	Online Marketing	search engine optimization, search engine marketing, content marketing, payper-click advertising, social media marketing, affiliate marketing, and email marketing	Patil, D., & Kumar, M. (2021). [15]
13	Digital System	Impact in the future with Globalization with communication and with changes in education systems such as online learning and availability of information	Luksanato, S. (2022). [16]

Summary of the Review of Literature:

With cadets becoming more dependent on digital marketing, it is difficult for maritime universities to stay relevant in their engagement initiatives. Higher education in marine has started to realise that social media is one of the digital marketing platforms that has a greater impact on learning outcomes in maritime education and also influences cadets' university selection. Additionally, the cadets and professors are impacted by the use of digital marketing, such as social media, online marketing, and search engine optimization, in terms of admission and enrollment, course delivery for teaching and learning, skill development, etc. The maritime education sector has become increasingly aware of how cadets use social media as well as possible techniques for reaching them. Determining the best noted uses of social media is also necessary. Additionally, while advertising was expanding steadily, the

Covid-19 epidemic unexpectedly gave it a boost while also encouraging a rapid shift in behaviour toward digital platforms, digital media, and digital content.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM :

Digital marketing is the promotion of all services and goods using the Internet, mostly using digital technologies. Mobile phones, display ads, and other digital media are also included [17]. How to strategically include social media into your overall plan for attracting prospective students is the challenge encountered by higher education social media administrators. In order to comprehend the kinds of interactions practitioners in maritime education hope to build with cadets and to investigate their perceived effectiveness [18], this study also looks at their social media outreach tactics.

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY :

To comprehend the idea of digital marketing and the role it would play in deciding the channels used for it in maritime education. Additionally, representatives from various colleges involved in maritime education who use digital marketing channels indicate that social media and email may be used for multiple purposes and also offer a faster or more effective method of communication when connecting with their cadets [19]. Institutions must not only comprehend the communication preferences of new cadets but also how digital marketing is used in order to adjust their admissions procedures and outreach plans. This study's goal is to investigate the internet marketing strategies employed by private marine colleges to enrol undergraduate students in their programs [20].

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

To examine how cadets' decisions are influenced by digital marketing channels in maritime education.

Research Question:

To assess various digital marketing tools used in maritime education and determine how cadets at private maritime colleges make decisions?

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

Table 2: Research Methodology

Type of Research	Descriptive Research
Research Design	Survey Method
Questionnaire	Structured Questionnaire-Used to collect the data
Development of Questionnaire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both Electronic and Printed Format • Questionnaire was developed by the researcher • Questions related to social media, e-mail and online marketing • 5 point likert scales ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree has been used for the study
Sampling Method	Convenience sampling – Convenient source of data for researchers
Sample Size	60 Sample Size selected for the study
Data Collection	Both Primary and Secondary Data Primary Data – Cadets of Private Maritime University Secondary Data – Text books, journals, magazines and through the blogs and articles published in websites.
Statistical Tools	Descriptive and T-Test

Hypothesis:

H1: T-test to determine whether there is a statistically significant difference between male and female cadets with regard to factors like online, email, and social media marketing.

Limitation of the Study :

The study may not be applicable to any other university because it is limited to private marine universities exclusively.

Due to the difficulty and specificity of the inquiry, the responses of the respondents frequently exhibit bias.

There can only be 60 cadets in the sample.

Data analysis and Interpretation:

Descriptive Statistics -Mean and Standard Deviation:

Table 3: The influence of digital marketing channels on cadets' decision-making in maritime education

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Social Media Marketing	60	4.61	0.558
E-mail Marketing	60	4.55	0.904
Online Marketing	60	4.15	0.734
Valid N	60		

According to the mean score, social media marketing (4.61) is the most effective channel for influencing cadets decisions about which marine programme to enroll in for their maritime education followed by e-mail marketing (4.55), followed by Online marketing.

T- Test:

Table 4: T-test for statistically significant differences between male and female cadets with regard to factors like online, email, and social media marketing.

Channels of Digital Marketing	Gender				T-value	P-value
	Male		Female			
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Social Media marketing	20.73	3.54	17.42	4.23	8.158	<0.001**
E-mail marketing	19.62	4.49	15.23	4.74	8.415	<0.001**
Online marketing.	19.41	4.84	18.73	5.67	6.582	<0.001**

** Significant at 1% level

7. FINDINGS :

The current study also sought to examine how cadets' decision-making and digital marketing channels interacted [21]. Regarding digital marketing channels like social media marketing, email marketing, and web marketing, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 1% level since P-Value is less than 0.01. As a result, there are notable differences between male and female cadets in terms of digital marketing channels. Male cadets do better than female cadets in all of the aforementioned categories, according to the mean score. Additionally, it has been discovered that social media marketing plays a significant role in digital marketing for maritime education in influencing the cadets' decision to enrol in a maritime professional programme.

8. CONCLUSION :

The current study looked at the interaction between digital marketing platforms like social media, email, and online marketing as well as the part played by cadets' demographic traits in the admissions process to maritime education [22]. According to the results of the current study, the researcher found that choosing a school and a subject of study are both heavily influenced by perceptions discovered through social media [23]. The findings also supported the hypothesised association between the variables of the study, which included demographic data, digital marketing platforms, and cadets' decision-making [24]. This study also covered how much gender influences admission-related decision-making [25]. These results not only demonstrated the importance of digital marketing channels in cadets' daily lives, but they also identified the most significant digital platform that influences cadets' decisions to enrol in maritime institutions.

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A Cross-Sectional Study among Cadets at Maritime Institutions: Factors influencing the study participation during the COVID-19 Epidemic towards Online Education

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Area of the Paper: Management.

Type of the Paper: Descriptive Research.

Type of Review: Peer Reviewed as per [\[C|O|P|E\]](#) guidance.

Indexed In: OpenAIRE.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7331706>

Google Scholar Citation: [IJCSBE](#)

How to Cite this Paper:

Rajasekar, D., & Aithal, P. S., (2022). A Cross-Sectional Study among Cadets at Maritime Institutions: Factors influencing the study participation during the COVID-19 Epidemic towards Online Education. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 6(2), 531-537. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7331706>

International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT and Education (IJCSBE)

A Refereed International Journal of Srinivas University, India.

Crossref DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47992/IJCSBE.2581.6942.0216>

Paper Submission: 08/10/2022

Paper Publication: 18/11/2022

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A Cross-Sectional Study among Cadets at Maritime Institutions: Factors influencing the study participation during the COVID-19 Epidemic towards Online Education

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The goal of this research is to investigate the factors influencing study engagement while the COVID-19 outbreak is occurring by using online platforms to provide educational concepts.*

Design/Methodology/approach: *There were 412 cadets present. The questionnaire was divided into sections to find out about each cadet's unique traits, needs, proficiency with online tools, and preferences for high-quality online education.*

Findings: *Young students live in a digital environment, and they have been using online education and digital applications as a form of instruction for a long time.*

Practical Implications: *The academic curricula was created for in-person instruction, and because there were not enough facilities to enable unexpected virtual education, universities were not ready for a sudden change. This caused anxiety among students.*

Originality/Value: *The data were analyzed using SPSS version 22 (Statistical Package of Social Science). The data's constructs were compared using chi-square analysis.. This study fills a vacuum in Indian research on this topic by examining the cadets' mental health state under situations like lockdown, which was recognized as a need.*

Type of Paper: *Descriptive Research.*

Keywords: *Cadets, Online Marketing, Maritime University and Education.*

1. INTRODUCTION :

The concept of education has changed significantly with the advent of tech and social Media, and several queries regarding the best delivery method for learning have been discussed [1]. Institutions all over the globe have been forced to shut down premises where classes are now being taught online due to a new pandemic [2]. Universities are increasingly engaged in asynchronous and synchronized classroom instruction to provide their students with excellent course materials. [3]. Lessons for these times have been provided by prior research on switching to online course delivery during emergencies. Numerous colleges made efforts during the COVID-19 epidemic, and some research revealed how challenging COVID-19 was for these universities to manage [4]. In the end, universities' main goals are to increase student satisfaction and provide them with a worthwhile output. Student, faculty, access, learning efficacy, and cost effectiveness are the five pillars of quality in online education [5]. As a result, student satisfaction must be taken into account when evaluating how effective a course is because it will increase levels of participation, motivation, learning, and success. Greater access to online digital resources is one of the main areas where faculty members have highlighted a need for assistance in maritime educational institutions. This study details large-scale initiatives for teaching and learning continuity and offers some suggestions for future maritime education research and practice [6].

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE :

Table 1: Literature Review on COVID-19 Epidemic towards Online Education

S. No.	Area/Focus	Outcome	Reference
1	Weakness of online teaching	Literature emphasizes a number of flaws, including the inadequate infrastructure for online education, the educator incompetence, a learn new, a complex home context, and other factors.	Mirza Jani, H., et al. (2016). [7]
2	Pedagogical	Tutors use pedagogical techniques that are unique to online learning for instruction, student engagement, and assessment.	Ali, W. (2020). [8]
3	Instructional methods and tech	As a result of this modification, presenters and educators are now expected to swiftly pick up on both instructional methods and tech.	Sukmawati, S., & Nensia, N. (2019). [9]
4	Distance Learning	For teachers, using distance learning platforms presented more difficulties.	Bojović, Ž., et al (2020). [10]
5	Offline Learning	Therefore, the problem of the limited offline learning activities can be handled by quickly switching from an offline to an online learning system.	Nuere, S., & De Miguel, L. (2021). [11]
6	Broadband Connectivity	Contrarily, rural areas' issues with broadband connectivity made it difficult for pupils to benefit from programmes for online usage.	Muthuprasad, T., et al. (2021). [12]
7	Socioeconomic Impact of Covid-19	Covid-19's multifaceted socio economic Impact affects the poor and vulnerable disproportionately.	Azubuike, O. B., Adegboye, O., & Quadri, H. (2021). [13]
8	E-learning product	The perception of Moodle's convenience and students' motivation had a direct impact on usage.	Pertiwi, Y., et al. (2021). [14]
9	Facilities And Quality Teaching	Both formal and informal learning staff members need to be trained to run efficient facilities and have top-notch teaching skills.	Budur, T., Demir, A., & Cura, F. (2021). [15]
10	Interactive Learning Sources.	Tools like Google Meet, Zoom Meeting, and Google Classroom are used by interactive learning sources.	Puspitacandri, A., & Sutoyo, S. (2022). [16]

Summary of the Review of Literature:

While attempting to maintain the core functions, educational institutions worked to put in place more efficient and strategic decision-making processes that would enable them to deal with large-scale, disruptive crises in the future. Furthermore, providing lecturers and students with professional facilities requires careful planning on the part of the institution, staff, and departments. This is due to the fact that how instructors educate for the sites, services, or software they use to interact with learners has a significant effect on how instructors and learners alike perceive digital learning. Increasing access to digital resources online, providing direction for working from home, and providing support for students were the three key areas where educators and managers felt assistance was needed. This hypothetical

situation served as a quick outline to digital sites like surveys, Zoom meetings, video conferencing, and Google Classroom. The interest of institutions in both synchronous and non-synchronous education is increasing in order to provide their students with high-quality course material. The findings also suggest that online and remote learning will be essential during lockdowns and social isolation brought on by the epidemic of COVID-19.

3. AN OUTLINE OF THE PROBLEM :

Development of teaching models that enhance training outcomes could be based on the understanding that student perception has a significant role in student behaviour [17]. In addition, there are four categories of obstacles that must be overcome during organisational change in order for universities to adopt online learning: interpersonal, institutional, training, and technological, as well as cost-benefit obstacles. They consequently remarked that being aware of these issues aided faculty and lecturers in their adaptation to the new system and structure [18]. However, based on those factors, public university teachers gave their school a near-poor rating, whereas private university lecturers gave their school an above-average rating [19].

4. SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

Faculty members' openness to online learning, which helps them gain a competitive edge in the marketplace [20]. The effectiveness of virtual classrooms is also influenced by virtual strategies, the ability to involve cadets and increase their involvement, and the capability for communicating effectively, according to researchers [21]. However, it has been made clear that the setting of online instruction and learning has a number of disadvantages. Due to this, many people have expressed concerns about the divisive subject of instruction and learning digital education during COVID-19 [22]. Additionally, the COVID-19 epidemic forced educational activities at universities and colleges throughout the world to move to digital sites and eventually close their institutions. Academic institutions weren't ready for this change, so they gradually improved their online teaching and learning methods [23].

5. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY :

To investigate the variables affecting study participation during the COVID-19 Epidemic toward online learning in maritime educational institutions.

Research Question:

To gauge how stressed out the cadets felt about how online learning in maritime educational institutions is affecting their health and social lives?

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

Table 2: Research Techniques

Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Descriptive Research
Research Design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey Method
Questionnaire	Structured Questionnaire-Used to collect the data
Development of Questionnaire	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both Electronic and Printed Format • Questionnaire was developed by the researcher • Questions related to online education • Qualitative and Quantitative • Google form & In-depth Interview
Sampling Method	Simple random sampling
Sample Size	412
Collection of Data	Primary as well as Secondary Data Cadets of Private & Public Maritime University Text books, journals, magazines and through the blogs and articles published in websites.
Statistical Tools	Chi-Square Test

Limitation of the Study:

The study's conclusions might not be applicable to the other departments because it was only conducted in the department of marine engineering with reference to private and public maritime educational institutions. Using random sampling approach, the sample was taken. As a result, the sample may not be accurately represented. Lack of time is another factor contributing to illegibility.

Data analysis and Interpretation:

Table 3: Association between cadet’s individual characteristics and Cadet Satisfaction in using Online Education

Analysis of Chi-Square			
	Value	df	Statistical Importance (2-sided)
Chi-Square Pearson	2423.223 ^a	1260	0.001**
Ratio- Likelihood	944.513	1260	1.000
Association of Linear Functions	166.879	1	0.001**
N of Valid Cases	412		

According to Table 3, there is a substantial correlation between the individual qualities of the cadet and their satisfaction with the online education they received. At a 1% level, The Chi-Square analysis of 0.001 indicates that the null hypothesis is not true. The data reveals a strong correlation between the individual traits of the cadets and their satisfaction with online education.

Table 4: Association between Cadets Needs and Cadet Satisfaction in using Online

Analysis of Chi-Square			
	Value	df	Statistical Importance (2-sided)
Chi-Square Pearson	1698.721 ^a	700	0.001**
Ratio- Likelihood	702.493	700	0.466
Association of Linear Functions	182.352	1	0.001**
N of Valid Cases	412		

According to Table 4, there is a strong correlation between cadet needs and cadet satisfaction with online education. The Chi-Square analysis of 0.001 indicates that the null hypothesis is not true. The data reveals a strong correlation between cadets' needs and their satisfaction with online education.

Table 5: Association between Cadets Knowledge and Cadet Satisfaction in using Online

Analysis of Chi-Square			
	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Chi-Square Pearson	1396.333 ^a	532	0.001**
Ratio- Likelihood	736.265	532	0.001**
Association of Linear Functions	219.898	1	0.001**
N of Valid Cases	412		

According to Table 5, there is a strong correlation between the knowledge of the cadets and their satisfaction with online education. The Chi-Square analysis of 0.001 indicates that the null hypothesis is not true. The data reveals a strong correlation between the knowledge of the cadets and their satisfaction with online education.

7. FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS :

The association between cadet individual characteristics, cadet needs, and cadet knowledge on cadet satisfaction in the Marine Engineering Program towards employing online education in maritime was examined in this research work using the chi-square test. According to the investigation, there is a strong correlation between cadets' individual traits, their demands, and their knowledge of their satisfaction

with using online education for maritime education. Consider the following recommendations for this study. Additionally, online education needs to be improved. To stream the video live and in real time online, the technical components must be in sync. Even public universities encourage the use of web based learning in maritime educational establishments, particularly in the marine engineering curriculum and among cadets from rural locations.

8. CONCLUSION :

Online education is not a brand-new method of imparting knowledge. It has long been utilised by various other academic institutions, either fully or partially. But the Covid-19 Pandemic compelled all academic institutions to use [25]. There were many different experiences recounted, including teaching classes through online. There were also many other experiences reported, such as studying digital sites, teaching or developing blended courses, completing doctor of philosophy work through online, completion of various educational training or professional development for integrating technology into the classroom, and regularly using their E - Learning systems of organization or other digital sites when enabling in-person coursework in maritime academic institutions[26]. The concepts presented in this article can be used to create the marine engineering curricula that will become the new standard. However, converting completely to online application may not be feasible in the marine education system because many subjects are practical, necessitating the development of a hybrid approach.

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CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This certificate is awarded to

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for participation in the One-day workshop on

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY held at Srinivas University on 30th October, 2021.

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